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TURLI TIKUV MASHINALARIDA MAHSULOTLARNI TIKISHGA VAQT SARFI ME'YORINI O'RGANISH

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada yengil sanoat korxonalaridada mavjud bo'lgan vaqt meyorlari va asosiy turgan vazifalar, uskunalar, ishlab chiqarish hajmini ko'paytirish va yangi oqim liniyalarini qurish va ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini oshirish bo'yicha ish ko'rilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: trikotaj, nafas olish qobiliyati, gigroskopiklik, issiqlik uzatish, fiziologik sharoitlar, funktsional trikotaj matolar, kaput, kamuflyaj.

STUDYING THE TIME CONSUMPTION FOR SEWING PRODUCTS ON DIFFERENT SEWING MACHINES

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Abstract: his article deals with time standards and main tasks, equipment, production volume increase and construction of new flow lines and production efficiency improvement in light industrial enterprises.

Key words: knitwear, breathability, hygroscopicity, heat transfer, physiological conditions, functional knitted fabrics, hood, camouflage.

Kirish. Respublikamiz sanoat korxonalari oldida hozirgi kunda turgan asosiy vazifalardan biri: uskunalarini zamonaviylashtirish, yuqori sifatli, chiroyli kiyimlarni ishlab chiqarish hajmini ko'paytirish, tezda moslashuvchi yangi oqim liniyalarini qurish, tikuvchilik tarmog'ini jadal rivojlantirish hisobiga ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini oshirishdan iborat.

Ushbu vazifalarni muvaffaqiyatli bajarish uchun korxonalarni qayta qurish, ishlab chiqarishni kompleks mexanizatsiyalashtirish va avtomatlashtirish, texnologiyani takomillashtirish talab qilinadi.

Zamonaviy kam operatsiyali texnologiyalar yaratish tikuvchilik mahsulotlariga ishlov berishni takomillashtirishdagi istiqbolli yo‘nalishlardan biri hisoblanadi.

Shundan kelib chiqib kiyim detallariga va uzellarining konstruksiyasida choklarni iloji boricha kamaytirish, namlab isitib ishlov berish, uskunalarni vibromaniken singari bir jarayonli turlarida materiallarga ularning termoplastik xususiyati hisobiga shakl berish, biriktirish va bezash jarayonlarini birlashtirish, yelim materiallardan keng foydalanish va hokazolar ana shunday kam operatsiyali texnologiyalarga kiradi.

Bugungi kunda tikuvchilik sanoatida kiyimni modellash bosqichida ham qo‘l mehnatining salmog‘i katta bo‘lib, bu mehnat unumdorligini o‘shirishni sekinlashtiradi. Shuning uchun, ishlab chiqarishni mexanizatsiyalashtirish borasida ko‘pgina ishlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Bular tezyurar tikuv mashina va yarim avtomatlari, namlab isitib ishlash jihozlaridan iborat.

Quyida keltirilgan vazifalarni amalga oshirish bilan bir qatorda zamonaviy tikuv mashinalarida vaqt sarfi me‘yori ishlab chiqish tikuvchilik ishlab chiqarish korxonalarining oldidagi dolzarb muammolardan biridir.

Vaqt sarfini aniqlashda avvalom bor mehnat sarf vaqti me‘yori-bu ishlab chiqarilayotgan mahsulotning normasi (me‘yori) yoki tikish jarayonidagi har bir operatsiyaga ketadigan vaqt sarf normasini nazariy asoslashdan iborat.

Shunday ekan tikuvchilik korxonalarining texnologik jarayonlari mahsulot ishlab chiqarishning barcha jarayonlarini o‘z ichiga oladi va mehnat unumdorligini 85-90% ni tashkil qiladi.

Ushbu ishlarni quyida keltirilgan jadvallarda Moskva Davlat Universitetining olimlari tomonidan turli mahsulotlarni tikishga sarflanadigan vaqt me‘yori ishlab chiqilgan va ular ko‘rsatilib o‘tiladi.

1.1-jadval

Erkaklar ko'ylaklari va ustki kiyimlarini ishlab chiqarishga sarflanadigan vaqt

Mahsulotning nomi	Maishiy xizmat uyida mahsulot tikishga sarflanadigan vaqt, minutda							Yakka tartibdagi tikuvchi			Bichuvchi ishiga sarflanadigan vaqt, minutda	
	Eng yuqori razryad	I-razryadli brigada quvvati			II-razryadli brigada quvvati			Eng yuqori razryad	I razryad	II razryad	Eng yuqori razryaddagi korxon	I va I I razryadlar
		pas t	o'rt a	yuq o ri	pas t	o'rt a	yuq o ri					
Qishki palto	26,0	18,2	16,5	14,8	16,8	15,3	13,8	31,2	21,8	20,2	3,76	2,20
Mavsumiy palto	24,0	16,9	14,5	13,0	14,9	13,5	12,1	28,8	19,2	17,9	3,76	2,2
Pidjak	23,5	15,5	14,1	12,7	14,5	13,2	11,9	28,2	18,6	17,4	3,36	1,96
Shim	4,5	3,5	3,2	2,9	3,3	3,0	2,7	5,4	4,2	4,0	1,17	0,75
Jilet	10,8	7,7	7,0	6,3	7,2	6,5	5,9	13,0	9,2	8,6	1,76	1,01
O'rt a mavsumiy palto	15,0	12,1	11,0	9,9	11,2	10,2	9,2	18,0	14,5	13,4	2,10	1,50
Plash	14,5	11,0	10,0	9,0	10,5	9,5	8,6	17,4	13,2	12,6	2,10	1,50
Qadalmali kurtka	12,0	9,4	8,5	7,7	8,7	7,9	7,1	14,4	11,3	10,5	1,62	1,15
Astarli kurtka	9,0	7,3	6,6	5,9	6,6	6,0	5,4	10,8	8,8	7,9	1,62	1,15
Qadalmali jilet	9,1	7,2	6,5	5,9	6,4	5,8	5,2	10,9	8,6	7,7	1,32	0,95
Tabiiy mo'ynali palto	26,0	18,2	16,5	14,8	16,5	15,0	13,5	31,5	21,8	19,8	3,76	2,20
Yarim kombinzon	6,9	4,6	4,2	3,8	4,3	3,9	3,5	8,3	5,5	5,2	1,56	0,84
Erkaklar sarochkasi	5,0	4,6	4,2	3,8	4,4	4,0	3,6	6,0	5,5	5,3	1,36	0,94

1.2-jadval

Ayollar ustki kiyimlarini ishlab chiqarishga sarflanadigan vaqt

Mahsulotning nomi	Maishiy xizmat uyida mahsulot tikishga sarflanadigan vaqt, minutda							Yakka tartibdagi tikuvchi			Bichuvchi ishiga sarflanadigan vaqt, minutda	
	Eng yuqori razryad	I-razryadli brigada quvvati			II-razryadli brigada quvvati			Eng yuqori razryad	I razryad	II razryad	Eng yuqori razryadagi korxonalar	I va II razryadlar
		past	o'rta	yuqori	past	o'rta	yuqori					
Qishki palto	27,0	18,5	16,8	15,1	17,6	16,0	14,4	32,4	22,2	21,1	4,17	2,4
Mavsumiy palto	25,1	17,4	15,8	14,2	16,2	14,7	13,2	30,1	20,9	19,5	4,17	2,4
Jaket	22,0	14,9	13,5	12,2	14,3	13,0	11,7	26,4	17,9	17,2	3,4	1,95
Yubka	5,7	3,8	3,4	3,1	3,5	3,16	2,8	6,8	4,6	4,2	1,30	0,63
Ayollar shimi	4,8	3,5	3,2	2,9	3,3	3,0	2,7	5,6	4,2	4,0	1,50	0,80
O'rtamavsumiy palto	15,5	12,1	11,0	9,9	11,7	10,6	9,5	13,6	14,5	14,0	2,49	1,60
Qadalmali kurtka	15,0	9,9	9,0	8,1	9,0	8,2	7,4	13,0	11,9	10,8	2,20	1,30
Astarli kurtka	9,6	7,2	6,5	5,9	6,6	6,0	5,4	11,5	8,6	7,9	2,20	1,30
Qadalmali jilet	10,0	7,7	7,0	6,3	6,0	5,5	5,0	12,2	9,2	7,2	1,55	1,00
Tabiiy mo'ynali palto	27,0	18,2	16,5	14,8	17,6	16,0	14,4	32,4	21,8	21,1	4,17	2,40
Charmli palto	18,0	16,0	14,5	13,0	14,9	13,5	12,1	21,6	19,2	17,9	2,80	2,10
Plash	16,0	12,7	11,5	10,4	11,8	10,7	9,6	19,2	15,2	14,2	2,40	-

1.3-jadval

Ayollar yengil kiyimlarini ishlab chiqarishga sarflanadigan vaqt

Mahsulotning nomi	Maishiy xizmat uyida mahsulot tikishga sarflanadigan vaqt, minutda							Yakka tartibdagi tikuvchi			Bichuvchi ishiga sarflanadigan vaqt, minutda	
	Eng yuqori razryad	I-razryadli brigada quvvati			II-razryadli brigada quvvati			Eng yuqori razryad	I razryad	II razryad	Eng yuqori razryadagi korxon a	I va I I razryadlar
		pas t	o'rt a	yuqor i	pas t	o'rt a	yuqor i					
Ko'ylaklik guruhlar												
Jun va ipak tolali gazlamalardan tayyorlanadigan ko'ylaklar	11,0	8,3	7,5	6,8	7,7	7,0	6,3	13,2	10,0	9,2	3,27	1,64
Xalat	10,8	7,9	7,2	6,5	7,5	6,3	6,1	13,0	9,3	7,5	3,27	1,64
Sarafan	9,5	7,5	6,8	6,1	6,9	6,3	5,7	11,9	9,0	8,3	3,27	1,60
Ko'ylak-palto	11,8	8,8	8,0	7,3	8,5	7,7	6,9	14,2	10,6	10,2	3,76	1,89
Paxtali gazlamalardan tayyorlanadigan ko'ylaklar	7,5	6,9	6,3	5,7	6,5	5,9	5,1	9,0	8,3	7,8	-	1,23
Jaketli guruh												
Jaket	9,0	7,7	7,0	6,3	7,2	6,5	5,9	10,8	9,2	8,6	2,42	1,22
Bluzka	9,5	7,3	6,6	5,9	6,8	6,2	5,6	11,4	8,3	8,2	2,42	1,22
Jilet	7,0	5,5	5,0	4,5	5,7	5,2	4,7	8,4	6,6	6,8	2,42	1,22
Belli buyumlar guruhi												
Yubka	4,9	3,5	3,2	2,9	3,3	3,0	2,7	5,9	4,2	4,0	1,3	0,65
Ayollar shimi	4,8	3,5	3,2	2,9	3,3	3,0	2,7	5,8	4,2	4,0	1,3	

Xulosa. Yuqorida keltirilgan jadvallardan xulosa qilib shuni ta’kidlash joizki, Rossiyalik olimlar tomonidan tikish jarayonidagi o’rtacha sarf vaqt me’yori maishiy xizmat uyining tikuvchi va yakka tartibdagi (uy sharoitida ishlaydigan) chevarlar shuningdek, bichuvchilari uchun ishlab chiqilgan bo’lib, unda qo’llanilgan tikuv mashina jihozlarining markasi va nomi keltirilmagan. Keyingi yillarda tikuvchilik ishlab chiqarish korxonolari texnik darajasi va imkoniyatlaridan kelib chiqqan holda turli xildagi assortimentlar sarf vaqt me’yorini tavsiya etildi.

Fan-texnika va ijtimoiy ishlab chikarishdagi o’zgarishlar, yangilanish davri texnika va texnologiyalarni yangi avlodini joriy etish, iqtisodiyotning yangi asosini yaratishdek murakkab sharoitda bormoqda. Bunday o’zgarishlar albatta, soha mutaxassisini bilim darajasini keng qamrovli, mukammal ayni paytda aniq mutaxassislikni egallashga qaratilgan bo’lishini taqozo etadi.

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XABARCHI MILLIY IJTIMOYIY TARMOG'INING TAHLILI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqola, O'zbekistonning milliy ijtimoiy tarmog'i hisoblangan "Xabarchi"ning tahlili va uning jamiyatdagi o'rni hamda ahamiyatini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. "Xabarchi" tarmog'i foydalanuvchilarga yangiliklar, ijtimoiy muloqot va ma'lumot almashinuvini taqdim etish orqali milliy axborot maydonini kengaytirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Maqolada, ushbu tarmoqning texnik xususiyatlari, foydalanuvchi interfeysi, kontent yaratish jarayonlari va ulardagi innovatsion yondashuvlar tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, "Xabarchi"ning ijtimoiy tarmoqlar orasidagi o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va foydalanuvchilar uchun qulayliklar yaratishdagi strategiyalari ham ko'rib chiqiladi. Tarmoqning rivojlanish istiqbollari va kelajakdagi rejalari haqida ham fikr yuritiladi. Maqola, shu bilan birga, "Xabarchi"ning milliy axborot tizimida tutgan o'rni va uning ijtimoiy himoya tizimiga qo'shgan hissasini ham o'rganadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Xabarchi, ijtimoiy tarmoq, veb-kontent yaratish, O'zbekiston milliy axborot, foydalanuvchi interfeysi, texnik xususiyatlar, innovatsion strategiyalar

ANALYSIS OF Khabarchi NATIONAL SOCIAL NETWORK

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the analysis of Khabarchi, which is considered the national social network of Uzbekistan, and its place and importance in society. The Khabarchi network plays an important role in expanding the national information space by providing users with news, social communication and information exchange. The article analyzes the technical characteristics of this network, user interface, content creation processes and innovative approaches in them. Also, Khabarchi's unique features among social networks and user-friendly strategies will be considered. The network's development prospects and future plans are also discussed. The article also examines Khabarchi's role in the national information system and its contribution to the social protection system.

Keywords: Messenger, social network, web content creation, national information of Uzbekistan, user interface, technical features, innovative strategies.

Zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalari jamiyatimizning barcha jabhalarida tobora muhim rol o'ynayotgan bir paytda, milliy ijtimoiy tarmoqlar ham o'zining o'rinlarini mustahkamlamoqdalar. Ushbu maqola, O'zbekistonning milliy ijtimoiy tarmog'i, "Xabarchi"ning tahliliga bag'ishlangan bo'lib, uning veb-kontent yaratish jarayonlari, foydalanuvchi interfeysi va texnik xususiyatlarini o'rganadi. "Xabarchi"ning milliy axborot maydonidagi ahamiyati va uning jamiyatdagi o'rni hamda ijtimoiy tarmoqlar orasidagi o'ziga xos xususiyatlari tahlil qilinadi.

Bu tahlil orqali, "Xabarchi"ning foydalanuvchilarga taqdim etayotgan yangiliklar, ijtimoiy muloqot va ma'lumot almashinuv imkoniyatlari hamda bu jarayonlarda qo'llanilayotgan innovatsion yondashuvlar ko'rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, tarmoqning kelajakdagi rivojlanish istiqbollari va uning milliy axborot tizimida tutgan o'rni ham baholanadi. Maqola, "Xabarchi"ning jamiyatimizdagi o'zgarishlarga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatayotgani va bu o'zgarishlar bilan qanday integratsiyalashayotgani haqida ham fikr yuritadi.

"Xabarchi"ning tahlili, shu bilan birga, O'zbekistonning milliy axborot tizimida qanday muhim rol o'ynashi mumkinligini ko'rsatib beradi va bu borada qo'yilgan strategik maqsadlar hamda ularning amalga oshirilishi yo'llarini tahlil qiladi. Maqola, milliy ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning rivojlanishida duch keladigan qiyinchiliklar va to'siqlarni ham ko'rib chiqadi va bu borada amaliy yechimlar taklif etadi.

"Xabarchi" milliy ijtimoiy tarmog'i O'zbekistonning axborot maydonida yangi bir qadam hisoblanadi. Ushbu tarmoqning tahlili, nafaqat texnik va dizayn jihatdan, balki ijtimoiy va madaniy o'lchovlarda ham muhimdir. Tarmoqning texnik xususiyatlari va foydalanuvchi interfeysi, uning ommabopligi va samaradorligini belgilaydi. Shu bilan birga, "Xabarchi"ning milliy madaniyatimizni aks ettirishdagi roli ham e'tiborga molikdir.

Adabiyotlar tahlilida, "Xabarchi"ning vujudga kelishi va rivojlanish bosqichlari, uning ijtimoiy funksiyasi va ijodiy jarayon qonuniyatlarini o'rganish muhimdir. Shuningdek, adabiyot nazariyasi, adabiyot tarixi va adabiy tanqid kabi sohalarda ham "Xabarchi"ning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va paydo bo'lish sabablari ko'rib chiqilishi kerak.

Milliy adabiyotimizning rivojlanishi doirasida, "Xabarchi"ning o'ziga xos milliy shaklni yuzaga keltirishdagi ahamiyati ham tahlil qilinishi lozim. Bu borada, adabiyot tomonidan uzoq davr mobaynida yig'ilgan tajriba va an'analar,

hamda xalq hayotidagi yangi davrlar adabiyotni yangi, yuqoriroq bosqichga ko'tarishda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Bundan tashqari, "Xabarchi"ning pedagogik jihatdan ham o'rganilishi kerak, chunki u ta'lim-tarbiya, ta'limiy va tarbiyaviy tizimlarni boshqarish sohasiga doir qonuniyatlarni aniqlash va o'rganishda yangi imkoniyatlar yaratadi. Pedagogikaning rivojlanish manbalariga turmush tarzi, an'analar va marosimlar, xalq pedagogikasida aks etgan ko'p asrlik amaliy tajriba, hamda jahon va milliy tarbiya amaliyoti kabi omillar kiradi.

"Xabarchi" milliy ijtimoiy tarmog'ining afzalliklari:

1. Milliylik: "Xabarchi" O'zbekistonning milliy axborot maydonini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan bo'lib, mahalliy aholining madaniyati va tiliga moslashtirilgan.

2. Foydalanuvchi Interfeysi: Foydalanish oson va intuitiv interfeysga ega, bu esa keng foydalanuvchi bazasini jalb qilish imkonini beradi.

3. Axborot Xavfsizligi: Mahalliy serverlarda joylashganligi sababli, foydalanuvchilarning shaxsiy ma'lumotlari yaxshi himoyalangan.

4. Ijtimoiy Integratsiya: Tarmoq orqali turli ijtimoiy qatlamlar o'rtasida muloqot va hamkorlikni rag'batlantiradi.

5. Ta'limiy Resurslar: Ta'lim va o'qitish uchun mo'ljallangan kontentlar bilan boyitilgan, bu esa foydalanuvchilarga bilim olishda yordam beradi.

6. Iqtisodiy Imkoniyatlar: Mahalliy bizneslar uchun reklama va marketing platformasi sifatida xizmat qiladi.

7. Ijtimoiy Himoya: Ijtimoiy himoya milliy agentligi va boshqa tashkilotlar bilan hamkorlikda ijtimoiy muammolarni hal qilishda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Ushbu afzalliklar "Xabarchi"ni nafaqat O'zbekiston ichida, balki xalqaro miqyosda ham tan olingan ijtimoiy tarmoq sifatida ajralib turishiga yordam beradi.

"Xabarchi" milliy ijtimoiy tarmog'ining kamchiliklari:

1. Texnik Cheklovlari: Ba'zi hollarda, tarmoqning texnik imkoniyatlari cheklangan bo'lishi mumkin, bu esa foydalanuvchilarga noqulayliklar tug'dirishi mumkin.

2. Xavfsizlik Masalalari: Raqamli xavfsizlik va ma'lumotlarni himoya qilish bo'yicha qo'shimcha chora-tadbirlar talab etiladi.

3. Kontent Sifati: Tarmoqda taqdim etilayotgan kontentning sifati va uning foydalanuvchilarga ta'siri doimiy nazorat va yaxshilanishni talab qiladi.

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4. Foydalanuvchilar Soni: "Xabarchi"ning foydalanuvchilar soni hali keng emas, bu esa uning ijtimoiy tarmoq sifatida samaradorligini cheklashi mumkin.

5. Xalqaro Integratsiya: Xalqaro darajada tan olinishi va integratsiyalashuvi uchun qo'shimcha sa'y-harakatlar zarur.

6. Qonuniy Cheklovlari: Qonuniy me'yorlar va cheklovlar tufayli ba'zi xizmatlar va imkoniyatlar cheklangan bo'lishi mumkin.

7. Moliyaviy Resurslar: Tarmoqni rivojlantirish va yangilash uchun zarur bo'lgan moliyaviy resurslar cheklangan.

Bu kamchiliklar tarmoqni yanada takomillashtirish va foydalanuvchilarga yaxshi xizmat ko'rsatish yo'lida diqqat qilinishi kerak bo'lgan jihatlar hisoblanadi.

"Xabarchi" yoshlar va katta yoshdagi aholi o'rtasida muloqotni rag'batlantirish orqali O'zbekistonning noyob demografik holatidan foydalanishga yordam beradi. Tarmoq, aholini ijtimoiy himoya qilish milliy strategiyasi doirasida ijtimoiy nafaqa olish jarayonini soddalashtirish va ijtimoiy himoyaga yo'naltirilgan xarajatlarni oshirishga hissa qo'shadi. "Xabarchi"ning faoliyati, yoshlarning huquqlarini ta'minlash va ishsizlik darajasini kamaytirish orqali siyosiy va diniy ekstremizmga qarshi kurashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Tarmoq, yoshlar uchun ta'lim va bandlik imkoniyatlarini yaxshilashga qaratilgan milliy tadqiqotlar va dasturlar orqali ta'lim va ish bilan ta'minlash sohalarida yordam beradi. "Xabarchi" yoshlarni jamiyatning siyosiy va iqtisodiy hayotida faol ishtirok etishga undaydi va ularning ovozini hukumat tomonidan eshitilishini ta'minlaydi.

Bu natijalar "Xabarchi"ning O'zbekiston jamiyatidagi muhim o'rni va uning kelajakdagi rivojlanish istiqbollari ko'rsatib beradi. Tarmoqning kelajakdagi yutuqlari va rivojlanishi, davlatning yoshlar siyosatini takomillashtirishga qaratilgan sa'y-harakatlarga bog'liq bo'ladi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, "Xabarchi"ning tahlili, uning texnik va ijtimoiy jihatdan rivojlanishini, shuningdek, milliy madaniyatimizni qanday aks ettirishini va jamiyatimizdagi o'zgarishlarga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatishini chuqurroq tushunishimizga yordam beradi. Bu tahlil, shu bilan birga, O'zbekistonning milliy axborot tizimida qanday muhim rol o'ynashi mumkinligini ko'rsatib beradi va bu borada qo'yilgan strategik maqsadlar hamda ularning amalga oshirilishi yo'llarini tahlil qiladi.

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RAQAMLASHTIRISHNING RIVOJLANGAN DAVLATLARDA FOYDALANISH DARAJASI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola raqamlashtirishning rivojlangan davlatlarda foydalanish darajasi haqida. Raqamlashtirishning afzalliklari, tezlik va samaradorlik, raqamlashtirishning rivojlanishdagi ahamiyati va imkoniyatlari, davlatlar o'rtasidagi raqamlashtirish texnologiyalari bilan aloqahaqida ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Raqamli iqtisodiyot, dunyo tajribasi, iqtisodiy o'sish, raqamli Qozog'iston, raqamli transformatsiya, reteyl (chakana savdo), media sektori.

THE LEVEL OF USE OF DIGITIZATION IN DEVELOPED COUNTRIES

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Abstract. This article is about the level of use of digitization in developed countries. The advantages of digitization, speed and efficiency, the importance and opportunities of digitization in development, the relationship between countries with digitization technologies are given.

Key words: Digital economy, world experience, economic growth, digital Kazakhstan, digital transformation, retail (retail), media sector

Kirish. "Raqamli" davlatlar bugungi kunda Norvegiya, Shvetsiya va Shvetsariya hisoblanishadi. Raqamli iqtisodiyot rivojlangan 10 ta davlatlar qatoriga AQSH, Buyuk Britaniya, Daniya, Finlandiya, Singapur, Janubiy Koreya va Gonkong kiradi.

Dunyo tajribasini o'rganish natijasida shu narsa aniq bo'ldiki, raqamli iqtisodiyoti rivojlangan mamlakatlarda raqamli iqtisodiyotda davlat(hukumat) bozor "o'yin" qoidalarini o'yinning barcha ishtirokchilari uchun belgilaydi va bunda davlatning eng muhim vazifasi sifatida o'yin ishtirokchilari uchun bir xil, teng huquqli va imkoniyatli sharoit yaratib berish hisoblanadi. Ya'ni, bozorda katta kompaniya bo'ladimi yoki kichik biznes, ular teng huquqli hisoblanadi. Ularga bir xil imkoniyatlar beriladi. Davlat qoidalarga amal qilinishi va oxir oqibatda oddiy iste'molchi sifatli, zamonaviy xizmat yoki mahsulot olishi ta'minlanadi.

Demak, raqamli iqtisodiyot rivojlanishi uchun davlat hamma uchun teng sharoit yaratib berishi, iloji boricha bozor qoidalari, qonunlar, shartnomalar shaffof bo'lishi, qonunlar bozor talabidan kelib chiqqan holda(ya'ni bozordagi rivojlanish tendensiyalarini oldindan aniqlay olishi va kerakli normativ hujjatlarni qabul qilishi) o'yin ishtirokchilari uchun erkinlik berishi zarur.

O'zbekistonda davlat ishtirokidagi kompaniyalar iqtisodiyotning anchagina ulushini egallaydi. Shuning uchun ularni raqamlashtirish mamlakat YAIM o'sishiga bevosita ta'sir qiladi. Boshqacha qilib aytganda, davlat sektorining raqamli transformatsiyasi O'zbekistonda iqtisodiy o'sishning muhim drayverlaridan biri bo'la oladi.

O'zbekistonda davlat ishtirokidagi kompaniyalar iqtisodiyotning anchagina ulushini egallaydi. Shuning uchun ularni raqamlashtirish mamlakat YAIM o'sishiga bevosita ta'sir qiladi. Boshqacha qilib aytganda, davlat sektorining raqamli transformatsiyasi O'zbekistonda iqtisodiy o'sishning muhim drayverlaridan biri bo'la oladi.

2020-yilda pandemiya tufayli jahon iqtisodiyoti hajmi 4,4 foizga kamaydi. Shu bilan birga, butun dunyoda raqamlashtirish jarayoni tezlashdi. Ya'ni mamlakatlar o'zlarini «bloklab», maktablar va sanoat tarmoqlari yopildi, raqamli sektorlar – masofaviy ta'lim, elektron tijorat yoki uydan ishlash xizmatlari – muhim ahamiyat kasb etib qoldi...

Ushbu tendensiya qaysi mamlakatda qanday namoyon bo'ldi?

Tafts universiteti qoshidagi fletcher maktabi xodimlari mastercard bilan hamkorlikda digital evolution scorecardning uchinchi nashrini ishlab chiqishdi. Quyida 4 ta asosiy omil: talab, taklif, institutlar va innovatsiyalarni kuzatib boradigan 160 ta ko'rsatkichga ko'ra, 45 dan ortiq turli manbalar to'plamidagi davlat va tijorat ma'lumotlaridan foydalanilgan tahlil natijalarini e'tiboringizga havola etamiz.

Taklif: raqamli ekotizimni yaratish uchun raqamli muhit va jismoniy infratuzilma qanchalik rivojlangan (bu keng polosali internetning mavjudligi, onlayn-do‘konlardan tovarlarni yetkazib berishda yo‘llarning sifati va boshqa omillarni o‘z ichiga oladi)?

Talab: iste‘molchilar raqamli iqtisodiyotda ishtirok etishga tayyormi va bunga qodirmi? Ularda buning uchun zarur vositalar va ko‘nikmalar bormi?

Institutlar: mamlakat qonunlari (va hukumat harakatlari) raqamli texnologiyalarni rivojlantirishga yordam beradimi yoki to‘sqinlik qiladimi? Rasmiylar raqamlashtirishga sarmoya kirityaptimi? Davlat tomonidan qabul qilingan tartibga solish choralari ma‘lumotlardan foydalanish va saqlashni sekinlashtiradimi yoki aksincha?

Innovatsiyalar: innovatsion ekotizimning asosiy komponentlari qanchalik yetuk: a) iqtidor va kapitalga kirish, b) jarayonlar (masalan, universitetlar va biznes o‘rtasidagi hamkorlik) va c) mijozlarga yetib borish (yangi raqamli mahsulotlar va xizmatlar).

Ushbu ma‘lumotlar asosida iqtisodiyotning ikkita ko‘rsatkichi baholangan: mamlakatdagi raqamlashtirishning hozirgi holati va uning tezligi (12 yil davomida reyting ballari o‘sishi sur‘ati baholangan – 2008 yildan 2019 yilgacha). Quyidagi diagrammada hosil bo‘lgan «xarita» iqtisodiyotni to‘rtta zonaga ajratadi: yetakchilar, sekinlashuvchi, istiqbolli va muammoli.

Raqamli evolyusiya: holat va tezlik

Liderlar

Bu tarkibga raqamlashtirishning yuqori boshlang‘ich darajasi va sohada kuchli rivojlanish sur‘atlari bilan ajralib turadigan iqtisodiyotlar kiradi. Ayniqsa, uchta davlat alohida ajralib turadi. Bular: janubiy koreya, singapur va gongkong.

Estoniya, tayvan va baa esa innovatsiyalarga moslashish va institutsional yordam ko‘rsatish hamda doimiy ravishda indekslar bo‘yicha yetakchilar qatoriga kiradi. Qizig‘i shundaki, aqsh raqamli evolyusiyada singapurdan keyin ikkinchi o‘rinda turadi: bu hajmli va murakkablikdagi iqtisodiyot uchun ajoyib o‘shish sur‘atidir.

Bu mamlakatlar nimasi bilan ajralib turadi? Har biri o‘ziga xosdir, ammo tahlillar shuni ko‘rsatdiki, eng muvaffaqiyatlilari quyidagi ustuvorliklarni tanlagan:

- Raqamli iste‘molchi loyihalarini (elektron tijorat, raqamli to‘lovlar, ko‘ngilochar va boshqalar) amalga oshirishni qo‘llab-quvvatlash;
- It xodimlarni jalb qilish, o‘qitish va ushlab turish;
- Raqamli startaplarni rivojlantirish;

- Internetdan tez va ommaviy foydalanishni ta'minlash – ham yer usti (masalan, optik tolali), ham mobil;
- Raqamli tovarlar, xizmatlar yoki mediani eksport qilishga ixtisoslashuv;
- Muvofiqlashtirilgan innovatsion jarayon: universitetlar, biznes va raqamli rivojlanishga mas'ul vazirliklar.

Istiqbollilar

Ushbu tarkibda raqamli iqtisodiyot infratuzilmasi hamon cheklangan. Ammo ularni tez raqamlashtirilayotganlar safidan deyish mumkin. Masalan, xitoy raqamli evolyusiya sur'ati bo'yicha jadal o'sib bormoqda, talab va innovatsiyalar uyg'unligi tufayli boshqa mamlakatlardan sezilarli darajada oldinda. Guruhning yana ikki taniqli a'zosi – indoneziya va hindistondir: ular o'sish sur'ati bo'yicha dunyoda uchinchi va to'rtinchi o'rinda. Shuningdek, keniya, vetnam, bangladesh, ruanda va argentina kabilar ham raqamli rivojlanishning jadal sur'atlarini boshdan kechirishmoqda. Bu raqamlashtirishning iqtisodiy tiklanishga foydasi katta ekanligidan dalolatdir.

Tahlillarga asoslanib, muvaffaqiyatli iqtisodlar quyidagi vazifalarga e'tibor qaratishi aniqlandi:

- Innovatsiyalarni kengroq targ'ib qilish uchun mobil internet tarmog'iga ulanish, uning mavjudligi va sifatini oshirish;
- Institutsional muhitni mustahkamlash va raqamli qonunchilikni rivojlantirish;
- Raqamli korxonalariga sarmoya kiritishni rag'batlantirish, raqamli ilmiy-tadqiqotlarni moliyalashtirish, it xodimlarini o'qitish va ish o'rinlarini yaratish uchun ilovalardan foydalanish;
- Gender, sinf, etnik kelib chiqish va geografiya bo'yicha raqamli vositalardan foydalanishdagi nomutanosiblikni kamaytirish bo'yicha chora-tadbirlar.

Sekinlashib qolganlar

Bu tarkibga yaxshi raqamli tizimlarga ega, ammo rivojlanish sur'ati pastlagan mamlakatlar kiradi. Ularning aksariyati yevropa ittifoqiga a'zo. Bu qisman yetuk bo'lgan, lekin o'sishning tabiiy kechikishi bilan bog'liq. Bundan tashqari, mintaqadagi ko'plab davlatlar mas'uliyatli va inklyuziv rivojlanish uchun ataylab o'sishni qurbon qilishni tanlashdi. Tezlikni tiklash uchun (o'z qadriyatlaridan voz kechmagan holda) bu mamlakatlar quyidagilarga ahamiyat berishi kerak:

- Raqamli platolardan himoya qilish: keyingi innovatsiyalarni qo'llab-quvvatlash uchun barqaror institutsional ustunlarga, tartibga solish muhitiga va kapital bozorlariga qo'shimcha investitsiyalar;

Raqamli imkoniyatlardan teng foydalanishni ta'minlash va barcha iste'molchilarni maxfiylik buzilishi, kiberhujumlar va boshqa tahdidlardan himoya qilish uchun siyosat hamda tartibga solish vositalaridan foydalanishni davom ettirish (yangi raqamli ilovalar uchun ma'lumotlar mavjud bo'lganda);

- Raqamli ko'nikmalarga ega bo'lgan mutaxassislarni jalb qilish, o'qitish va saqlab qolish – ko'pincha immigratsiya siyosati islohotlari orqali;

- Yangi texnologik bo'shliqlarni aniqlash va ushbu sohalarda innovatsiyalarga yordam beradigan ekotizimlarni yaratish.

Qiyinchilikni boshdan kechirayotganlar

Nihoyat, afrika, osiyo, lotin amerikasi va janubiy yevropa mamlakatlarini o'z ichiga olgan oxirgi tarkib mavjud raqamli ekotizimdagi muammolar va past o'sish bilan ajralib turadi. Ushbu zonadagi davlatlar raqamli o'sishni iqtisodiy barqarorlik vositasi sifatida qo'llashda rivojlanayotgan iqtisodlardan namuna olishlari kerak. Xususan, raqamli segmentga talab yuqori bo'lgan muammoli iqtisodlarda quyidagi ustuvorliklar belgilanishi zarur:

- Asosiy infratuzilma muammolarini hal qilish uchun uzoq muddatli investitsiyalar;

- Raqamli mahsulotlar va xizmatlarning iste'molchilarga xavfsiz va keng tarqalishini qo'llab-quvvatlovchi institutsional muhitni yaratish – ayniqsa, bu mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarish va ish o'rinlarini yaratishga hissa qo'shsa;

- Aholining tarixan nochor qatlamlari uchun raqamli foydalanishni rivojlantirish tashabbuslarini qo'llab-quvvatlash (ayniqsa, davlat-xususiy sherikchilik orqali);

- Haqiqiy muammolarni hal qiladigan va shu tariqa raqamli vositalarni (masalan, raqamli to'lov platformalari) tarqatish uchun katalizatorlik vazifasini o'tovchi ilovalarni qo'llab-quvvatlash.

Misol uchun, "Raqamli Qozog'iston" davlat dasturini ko'rib chiqish mumkin. Rasmiy ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, uni amalga oshirishdan jami iqtisodiy samaradorlik 2018-2019-yillarda 2 mlrd. AQSH dollaridan ko'proqni tashkil etdi. Mana shuning o'zi axborot texnologiyalarini yoppasiga joriy etish foydasiga salmoqli dalil bo'la oladi, nazarimda.

Jahonda raqamli transformatsiya hali davom etmoqda. Hatto ilg'or mamlakatlarda ham bu jarayon tugallanmagan va raqamlashtirish darajasi tarmoqdan tarmoqqa qadar juda kuchli o'zgarib boradi. Ba'zi sohalar allaqachon

ATning anchagina ta'siriga uchragan (moliyaviy xizmatlar, telekommunikatsiyalar, reteyl (chakana savdo), media sektori), boshqalari esa bu yo'lning boshida turibdi va raqamli texnologiyalarni ayrim jarayonlargagina (neft-gaz va tog'-kon tarmog'i, qishloq xo'jaligi, mudofaa sanoati) joriy etmoqda. Bu bilan birinchilardan bo'lib jadal transformatsiyalash ular uchun raqobatbardoshlikning garovi bo'lgan korxonalar shug'ullana boshladilar.

Transformatsiya — juda murakkab jarayon. To'qson to'qqiz foiz holatda kompaniyalarda ishni nimadan boshlash kerakligi haqida tushuncha bo'lmaydi. "Expera-Suntronix" alyansi O'zbekistonda 20 yildan ko'proq vaqtdan beri kompleks axborot tizimlarini qurib kelmoqda va jarayonni tarkibiy qismlarga bo'lishi, loyihani amalga oshirish rejasini tuzishi, loyiha ofisini tashkil etishi mumkin. Lekin bu bilan xalqaro va mahalliy ekspertlarning butun bir jamoasi shug'ullanadi. Ana endi bugungi kungacha butkul boshqa vazifalarni bajarib yurgan korxonalar menejerini tasavvur qilib ko'ring. Albatta, u qo'yilgan vazifaga qanday yondashishni tushunmaydi.

Asosiy qism. Jahon banki hisob-kitoblari binoan, tezkor internet foydalanuvchilarining 10 foizga ko'payishi yillik YaIM ko'lamini 0,4 foizdan 1,4 foizgacha oshirishi mumkin ekan. Shuningdek, raqamli iqtisodiyotning mamlakat YaIMdagi ulushi har yili taxminan 20 foizga o'sishi (rivojlangan mamlakatlarda bu ko'rsatkich 7 foiz atrofida) uning ahamiyati belgilaydigan ko'rsatkich sifatida qaraladi.

2010 yilda Boston Consulting Group kompaniyasi raqamlashtirish ko'lamini 20ta mamlakatdan iborat guruh uchun 2,3 trillion dollarga (4,1 foiz YaIM) baholagan. Agar bu tendensiya saqlanib qolsa, 10-15 yildan keyin bunday iqtisodiyotning jahon YaIMidagi ulushi 30-40 foizga yaqinlashadi.

Rivojlanayotgan iqtisodiyotlarda IT sohasida taxminan 1 foiz aholi mehnat qiladi, ushbu sektor ish o'rinlarini boshqalarga solishtirganda nisbatan qamroq yaratadi. Biroq IT yo'nalishining yuksalishi yangi texnologiyalarni o'zlashtirayotgan boshqa sohalarda ish o'rinlarining yaratilishiga turtki beradi (IT sohasida yaratilgan har 1ta yangi ish o'rni uchun yondosh sohalarda 4,9ta ish o'rni to'g'ri keladi).

Raqamli iqtisodiyot tadbirkorlar va o'zi uchun ishlaydigan insonlarga yangi ufqlarni dadil ochib bermoqda. Ko'pincha IT sohasining rivojiga qo'shilgan hissa iqtisodiyotning rivojlanishi, yangi ish o'rinlarining yaratilishi, odamlar va biznes uchun yangi turdagi xizmatlarning paydo bo'lishi, elektron hukumat loyihalari doirasida xarajatlarning qisqarishiga zamin yaratadi. Shu bilan bir vaqtda,

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axborot texnologiyalarini tatbiq etishdan hosil bo'lgan umumiy effekt kutilganidan samarasizroq bo'lib chiqadi va bir xil tartibda taqsimlanmaydi.

Bu kabi investitsiyalardan maksimal natija olish uchun texnologiyalarning Jahon banki tayyorlagan ma'ruzasida «analog to'ldiruvchilar» deb nomlangan boshqa omillar bilan o'zaro ta'sirini yaxshi tushunish talab etiladi.

Ular qatorida: faol ishbilarmonlik muhitini qo'llab-quvvatlaydigan hamda biznes va insonlarga raqamli iqtisodiyot texnologiyalaridan raqobat va innovatsiyalar, xarajatlarni qisqartirish, shuningdek, turmush farovonligini oshirish uchun foydalanishga imkon beradigan normativ-huquqiy baza;

- biznes menejmenti va davlat xizmatchilarida axborot texnologiyalarini qo'llashga doir to'laqonli ko'nikmalar;
- axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish yo'nalishida konsalting xizmatlarini ko'rsatadigan institutlar (davlat va xususiy) o'rin olgan.

Raqamli iqtisodiyot hosil qiladigan effektlarni to'liq sanab o'tish ancha murakkab ish, binobarin, elektron servislari va metama'lumotlardan foydalanish imkoniyati iqtisodiy obektlarga taqdim etadigan aloqalarni to'laqonli tarzda baholash ancha mushkuldir. Shu bois axborotlashtirishga sarflanadigan investitsiyalarning muhimligini, ayniqsa davlat darajasida asoslash bir qadar qiyin vazifa hisoblanadi. U yoki bu sohada yaratilgan gigibayt axborotni real holatda har doim ham hisoblab chiqishning imkonsizligi o'z-o'zidan tushunarli hodisadir.

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FIZIKA FANINI O'QITISHDA LABORATORIYA ISHLARINING O'RNI VA ROLI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Fizika fanini o'qitishda laboratoriya ishlarining o'rni va roli haqida fikr yuritiladi. Fizika o'qitish jarayonida fundamental ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan fanlarning o'qitilishiga alohida e'tibor qaratish lozimligiga alohida e'tibor berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Laboratoriya, fizik, virtual, ma'ruza, ilmiy-texnik, masalalar, DTS, elektrodinamika

THE PLACE AND ROLE OF LABORATORY WORK IN TEACHING PHYSICS

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Abstract: This article discusses the place and role of laboratory work in the teaching of Physics. In the process of teaching physics, special attention has been paid to the teaching of fundamental subjects.

Keywords: Laboratory, physical, virtual, lecture, scientific and technical, issues, DTS, electrostatics

Fizika kursi o'quvchilarni fanning turli sohalari bo'yicha nazariy tayyorlash asoslarini ta'minlash bilan birga ularni hozirgi axborotlar oqimi barq urib o'sayotgan davrda ishlashga ham tayyorlaydi. Bundan kelib chiqib, fizikadan doimiy takomillashtirib turiladigan barcha o'quv mashg'ulotlarini (ma'ruza, laboratoriya ishlari, masalalar yechish) o'tkazish metodikasiga yuqori talablar qo'yiladi. Ayniqsa bu, ilmiy-texnik taraqqiyot bilan bog'liq ravishda jihozlari o'zgarib turadigan laboratoriya praktikumi mazmuniga tegishlidir. Laboratoriya praktikumi o'quvchilarning quyidagi nazariy-eksperimental ma'lumotlarni egallashlarini nazarda tutadi: fizik hodisalarning asoslari va ularning

qonuniyatlari bilan tanishtiradi, zamonaviy fizik o'lchash asboblari bilan ishlash ko'nikma va malakalarini hosil qiladi, fizik o'lchash metodlari va eksperiment natijalarini qayta ishlash usullari bilan tanishtiradi. Bundan tashqari, fizika ta'limining ma'ruza va boshqa shakllari bilan chambarchas bog'liq ravishda umumlashtirish, mustahkamlash, rivojlantirish va nazariyaning asosiy holatlarini chuqur o'zlashtirishni ta'minlash vazifalarini bajaradi. Fizik praktikum bir qator o'quv-tarbiyaviy masalalarni hal qiladi: - o'quvchilarni bilish metodologiyasi bilan amaliy va nazariy tanishtiradi (nazariya va eksperimentning birligi, o'lchash nazariyasi, absolyut va nisbiy xatoliklarni hisoblash va boshq.);

1. Fizika o'qitishda laboratoriya ishlarining o'rni va roli. Laboratoriya jihozlari va ular bilan ishlash.

2. Maktab darsliklarida berilgan laboratoriya ishlarini bajarishdagi muammolar. Virtual laboratoriya ishlari.

3. Namoyishli tajribalar va unga qo'yiladigan didaktik talablar. eksperimentni rejalashtirish va uni o'tkazishni o'rgatadi, o'quvchilarning tadqiqiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi; - fizika kursining katta bo'limlari bo'yicha o'quvchining bilimlarini umumlashtiradi va sistemaga soladi; - o'quvchilarning fizika laboratoriyasidagi faoliyatini maksimal individuallashtiradi, mustaqil ishlash ko'nikmalarini shakllantiradi; - o'quvchilarning ijodiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantiradi (konstruktorga, texnik qurilmalarni yig'ish, ularning ishlash tamoyilini o'rganish, asboblarni darajalash va b.). Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablari o'quvchilariga umumta'lim fizikasi Davlat ta'lim standarti (DTS) ga mos keluvchi minimal bilim, ko'nikma va malakalarni egallashlariga erishish uchun o'quvchilarni ularning qobiliyatlariga yarasha quyi bosqich ta'lim tizimidagi DTS ga mos ravishda izchil davom ettiradigan bilim, ko'nikma va malakalarni egallashlariga imkoniyat yaratish talab etiladi. O'quv jarayonini takomillashtirish, nafaqat o'quvchilar ko'z o'ngida, o'qituvchilar foydalanadigan tadqiqot metodlarining mohiyatini ochib berish, balki ular ongida o'zlari egallagan nazariy va amaliy bilimlarni boshqalarga, ya'ni o'quvchilarga tushuntirish va o'rgata olish malakalarini tarbiyalovchi metodlarni o'zlashtirishlarini ham nazarda tutadi. Hozirgi sharoitda pedagogika oliy ta'lim muassasalarining texnika, tabiiy-matematika, jumladan fizika, yo'nalishlarida tahsil olayotgan o'quvchilarga fizik praktikumdan mashg'ulotlar tashkil etishda bir muncha qiyinchiliklarga duch kelinmoqda. Olib borilgan kuzatishlar, shuni ko'rsatdiki, buning asosiy sabablaridan biri, laboratoriya mashg'ulotlari o'tkazilayotgan bunday guruhlarda fizika va matematikadan tayyorgarligi va boshlang'ich eksperimental ko'nikmalarining shakllanganlik darajalari turlicha

bo‘lgan o‘quvchilarning tahsil olayotganliklarida ekanligini ko‘rsatmoqda. Bundan tashqari guruhlarda eksperimental ishlarga layoqatli va, aksincha, eksperimental ishlarga nisbatan moyilligi bo‘lmagan o‘quvchilar hamma vaqt ham topiladi. Shunga qaramasdan, pedagogika oliy ta‘lim muassasalari fizikamatematika fakultetining bitiruvchilari, fizikadan eksperimentni o‘tkaza olish ko‘nikmalarini egallashlari albatta zarur. Umumiy o‘rta ta‘lim maktablarida har bir o‘qituvchi, o‘quvchilarga faqat fan asoslarini o‘rgatish bilangina chegaralanib qolmasdan, ularning politexnik saviyalarini kuchaytirishi, olgan bilimlarini turmushga tatbiq qila bilish va ularning amaliy faoliyatlari uchun keng sharoit yaratib berishlari lozim. O‘qitishni politexnikalashtirishda fizika fani muhim o‘rin egallaydi. Fizika kursining «Elektrodinamika» bo‘limi, xususan elektr toki mavzui bu sohada muhim o‘rin tutadi, chunki turmushda va texnikada elektr asboblardan keng foydalanilmoqda. O‘quvchilar fizika kursining har bir mavzusiga oid asosiy qonunqoidalar haqida talab darajasidagi bilimlarga ega bo‘lishi uchun, o‘qituvchi dars materiallarini og‘zaki bayon etish bilan bir qatorda shu mavzuga doir tajribalarni o‘tkazishi, o‘rganilayotgan hodisani ular ko‘z oldilariga keltirishlariga va bu borada tafakkur faoliyatini rivojlantirishga erishishlari zarur. Laboratoriya ishlarining har biri o‘ziga xos xarakterga ega bo‘lib, ma‘lum bir maqsadni ko‘zda tutadi. Shuning uchun laboratoriya ishlari o‘tilgan yoki yangi bayon etiladigan mavzuga doir fizik hodisa va jarayonlarning mohiyatini aniq anglab olishga imkon berishi hamda nazariy bilimlarni amalda tasdiqlashi lozim. Fizika kursida shunday mavzular ham borki, ularga doir tajribalar o‘tkazishda yakka asbob emas, balki bir qancha asbob va detallardan tashkil topgan qurilmalardan foydalanishga to‘g‘ri keladi. «Elektrodinamika» bo‘limiga tegishli ko‘pgina mavzular (ayniqsa, elektr toki) bo‘yicha o‘tkaziladigan tajribalarning deyarli hammasi ana shular jumlasidandir. Fizikadan laboratoriya mashg‘ulotlarini o‘tkazishdagi ko‘p yillik tajriba natijalarimiz quyidagi xulosaga olib keldi: o‘quvchilarning fizikadan laboratoriya praktikumiga «kirish»dagi tayyorgarlik darajasi turlicha, mulohazalari tarqoq bo‘lib, «chiqish»da esa, hamma bu masalada ma‘lum «umumiy maxrajga keltiriladi». Laboratoriya ishlarini fizik praktikum tarzida bajarishning foydali ekanligi bir qator tadqiqotlarda o‘z tasdig‘ini topgan. Unda laboratoriya ishlarini bajarish, o‘quvchilarning individual moyilligi, qiziqishlarini hisobga olish va ularning ijodiy qobiliyatlarining rivojlanishi uchun katta imkoniyat yaratadi. Fizik praktikum ko‘rinishidagi laboratoriya ishlari, tanlangan ishlarga tegishli kurs, qism o‘rganilgandan keyin qo‘yiladi. Unda o‘quvchilar ikki kishidan bo‘lib, oldindan olingan topshiriq bo‘yicha butunlay mustaqil ishlaydilar. Bunda ular

maxsus qo‘llanmalardan foydalanadilar. Praktikum ishlari nisbatan murakkab, ularni bajarish uchun ishlatiladigan asbobuskunalar, ayrim hollarda, ilmiy-tekshirish laboratoriyalarida va ishlab chiqarishda ishlatiladigan texnik asboblardan bo‘ladi. Fizik praktikum - fizikaga oid bilimlarni mustahkamlash, kasbiy va eksperimental tayyorgarlik sifatini oshirishdagi eng istiqbolli metoddir. Uning o‘z oldiga qo‘ygan eng asosiy maqsadlaridan biri – muayyan o‘lchash metodini va o‘lchash natijalarini to‘g‘ri tahlil va talqin qilishga o‘rgatish orqali bo‘lajak fizika o‘qituvchilarining eksperimental ko‘nikmalarini shakllantirishdan iborat. Fizik praktikumning umumiy masalalari sifatida quyidagilarni ta’kidlash lozim: fizika o‘qitishdagi umumiy masalalarning optimal bajarilishiga yordam berish (fikrlashni rivojlantirish, bilish qobiliyatlarini shakllantirish va boshqalar); fizikadan bilimlar tizimligini ta’minlash, mavzular, bo‘limlar va predmetlararo bog‘lanishlarni o‘rnatish; fizika kursining eng muhim masalalari bo‘yicha bilimlarni umumlashtirish va mustahkamlash (chuqurlashtirish); politexnik ta’limni amalga oshirishga yordam berish (o‘quvchilarni ba’zi bir texnik asboblardan bilan tanishtirish, texnikada uchraydigan fizik kattaliklarni aniqlash metodlarini o‘rgatish va boshqalar). Fizika kursidan praktikum o‘tkazishda esa, quyidagi maqsadlar nazarda tutiladi: a) o‘quvchilarga fizikaning asosiy qonunlarini va fizik hodisalarni chuqurroq o‘zlashtirishlariga yordamlashish; b) o‘quvchilarni ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlariga ijodiy yondashishga, eksperimental metodni to‘g‘ri tanlay bilishga, fizik kattaliklarning qiymatlarini o‘lchashga va ularni nazariya bilan taqqoslashga, xulosalar chiqarishga o‘rgatish; v) zamonaviy asbob-uskunalar, hamda fizik o‘lchash natijalarini matematik jihatdan ishlab chiqish metodlari bilan tanishtirish. Bu umumiy maqsad, fizika praktikumida o‘quvchilarning bilim darajasiga qarab, har bir konkret holda turlicha yo‘llar bilan amalga oshiriladi. Fizika praktikumida laboratoriya ishlarini bajarayotgan o‘quvchilar oldiga qo‘yiladigan masalalar quyidagi uch xil ko‘rinishda bo‘lishi mumkin: 1) fizik kattalikni o‘lchashning eng ma’qul metodi va o‘lchash asboblari kompleksini o‘quvchilarga ko‘rsatib beriladi; 2) o‘lchash metodi ko‘rsatiladi, o‘lchash uchun kerakli asboblarni o‘quvchining o‘zi tanlashi lozim; 3) o‘quvchidan muayyan fizik kattalikni ko‘rsatilgan aniqlikda o‘lchash talab qilinadi. Eksperimentdan olingan ma’lumotlar hamma vaqt ma’lum xatolikka ega bo‘ladi. Bu xatolikning yuzaga kelishiga, asosan, tajriba sharoiti, o‘lchash usulining yoki fizik asboblarning nomukammalligi sabab bo‘ladi. Eksperimentator sezgi organlarining tabiiy holda xatolikka yo‘l qo‘yishi va o‘lchov asboblarning nomukammalligi tufayli har qanday o‘lchashda fizik kattaliklarning taqribiy qiymatlari aniqlanadi. O‘lchash aniqligi, avvalo o‘lchov asboblarning o‘lchash

aniqligi bilan belgilanadi. Fizik kattalikni asbobning o'lchash aniqligidan katta aniqlikda o'lchash mumkin emas. Har bir laboratoriya ishida, turli fizik kattaliklar turlicha aniqlikda o'lchanadi. Biror o'lchashning aniqligi, boshqalarinikiga ta'sir qiladi. Xatoliklar hisoblab ko'rsatilgandagina o'lchash natijasi, ya'ni tajribadan olingan ma'lumotlar, muayyan ma'no kasb eta boshlaydi. Shunday tarzda ishlangan eksperiment natijasini nazariy yoki jadval ma'lumotlari bilan taqqoslab ko'rish mumkin. Xatoliklarni hisoblashning qator usullaridan, ayniqsa konkret tajribaning fizik mohiyatini to'g'ri va yaqqol ochib beradiganini tanlay bilish muhimdir. Bu ijodiy jarayon o'quvchidan muayyan eksperimental ko'nikmani, sinchkovlikni, mantiqiy tahlil malakasini talab qiladi. Fizik praktikumga doir ishlar frontal laboratoriya ishlariga nisbatan keyingi bosqichdagi qiyin ishlar turiga kiradi. Hammadan avval bu eksperimental tadqiqot masalasining o'zidan iborat. Masalaning nazariyasini mustaqil o'rganish va takrorlash, qurilmani yig'ish, tajribani bir necha marotaba qayta bajarish, eksperiment natijalarini yozib olish, baholash va ularning to'g'rilik darajasini tekshirib ko'rish talab qilinadi. Praktikumning har bir ishi ilgari o'zlashtirib olingan ma'lumotlarni qo'llash va yangi bilimlar olishga imkon beradigan eksperimental masalalarni hal qilishni taqozo qiladi. Bu ishlar o'quvchilarni keng tarqalgan texnik asboblardan va maxsus laboratoriya asbob-uskunalari, hozirgi zamon fan va texnikasida foydalaniladigan o'lchash metodlari bilan tanishtiradi, o'lchov asboblarining qo'llanilish chegarasini aniqlay olish, hamda eksperimental qurilmani tushungan holda mustaqil yig'ish ko'nikma va malakalarini hosil qiladi. Fizika tabiat haqidagi fundamental va yetakchi fanlardan biridir.

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DIAGNOSIS AND INTENSIVE TREATMENT OF TYPE 2 DIABETES TO ACHIEVE THE TARGET LEVEL OF GLYCED HEMOGLOBIN AND REDUCE THE RISK OF VASCULAR COMPLICATIONS

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Annotation. Control of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) requires multifactorial behavioral and pharmacological treatment to prevent the development or slow the progression of complications. The main characteristics of T2DM - hyperglycemia and insulin resistance in combination with oxidative stress, low-level inflammation, epigenetic changes, genetic predisposition, activation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system, causing endothelial dysfunction, from the earliest stages are responsible for the metabolic environment that increases vascular risk in patients. Almost all patients with T2DM are at high and very high cardiovascular risk. The largest studies of the late 20th - early 21st centuries. demonstrated a significant reduction in intensive care complications early in the disease and a "legacy effect" with long-term historical significance of HbA1c control during their observational extensions. Reductions in HbA1c levels may also play a role in mediating the beneficial effects on cardiovascular risk observed with newer glucose-lowering drugs. The desires for glycemic control and organ-specific protection do not exclude, but complement each other. Reassessing individual glycemic goals and achieving them at regular intervals with early intensification of therapy is key to overcoming clinical inertia.

KEYWORDS: diabetes mellitus type 2; glycohemoglobin HbA1c; vascular complications; clinical inertia; Gliclazide MB

ДИАГНОСТИКА И ИНТЕНСИВНОЕ ЛЕЧЕНИЕ САХАРНОГО ДИАБЕТА 2 ТИПА ДЛЯ ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ ЦЕЛЕВОГО УРОВНЯ ГЛИКИРОВАННОГО ГЕМОГЛОБИНА И СНИЖЕНИЯ РИСКА СОСУДИСТЫХ ОСЛОЖНЕНИЙ

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Аннотация. Контроль сахарного диабета 2 типа (СД2) требует многофакторного поведенческого и фармакологического лечения для предотвращения развития или замедления прогрессирования осложнений. Основные характеристики СД2 - гипергликемия и инсулинорезистентность в сочетании с окислительным стрессом, вялотекущим воспалением, эпигенетическими изменениями, генетической предрасположенностью, активацией ренин-ангиотензин-альдостероновой системы, вызывающей дисфункцию эндотелия, с самых ранних стадий ответственны за метаболические процессы. окружающей среды, которая увеличивает сосудистый риск у пациентов. Практически все пациенты с СД2 относятся к группе высокого и очень высокого сердечно-сосудистого риска. Крупнейшие исследования конца 20 - начала 21 веков. продемонстрировали значительное снижение осложнений интенсивной терапии на ранних стадиях заболевания и «наследственный эффект» с долгосрочной исторической значимостью контроля HbA1c во время их наблюдательного расширения. Снижение уровня HbA1c также может играть роль в обеспечении положительного влияния на сердечно-сосудистый риск, наблюдаемого при применении новых сахароснижающих препаратов. Стремление к гликемическому контролю и органоспецифической защите не исключают, а дополняют друг друга. Переоценка индивидуальных целей гликемии и их достижение через регулярные промежутки времени при ранней интенсификации терапии является ключом к преодолению клинической инерции.

Ключевые слова: сахарный диабет 2 типа; гликогемоглобин HbA1c; сосудистые осложнения; клиническая инерция; Гликлазид МВ.

Introduction. Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a heterogeneous disease with varying age of onset, degree of obesity, insulin resistance, and tendency to develop complications. Maintaining normal glucose homeostasis is determined by a high degree of interaction between the liver, muscles, adipocytes, pancreas, kidneys and the neuroendocrine system, ensuring a stable level of glycemia [1]. Control of T2DM involves multifactorial behavioral and pharmacological treatment to prevent the development or slow the progression of complications and maintain quality of life. Synergistic effects on multiple pathophysiological mechanisms, potentially leading to long-term therapeutic efficacy without increasing the risk of adverse events, are important for successful therapy. Hyperglycemia and insulin resistance - the main characteristics of T2DM - in combination with oxidative stress, low-level inflammation, epigenetic changes, genetic predisposition, activation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system, causing endothelial dysfunction, from the earliest stages are responsible for the metabolic environment that increases vascular risk in patients [2]. The organic interaction between the microvasculature and resident tissue cells becomes dysfunctional under the influence of these factors. Microvascular dysfunction in diabetes precedes anatomical microvascular complications in the heart, brain, blood vessels, kidney, retina, nervous tissue, muscles and other organs. The assumption of the reversibility of microvascular damage with concomitant dysfunction in the early stages of the disease, provided adequate interventions, is substantiated. Unfortunately, even when diagnosing T2DM, vascular pathology is detected - up to 50% of cases [3]. Moreover, according to the UK Biobank, with a median follow-up of 11 years, the risk of developing such clinical outcomes as chronic kidney disease (CKD), chronic heart failure (CHF), atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD) increases gradiently even in people with prediabetes , according to glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) indicators, which do not yet have diagnostic values for T2DM [4]. According to the European Society of Cardiology (European Society of Cardiology), almost all patients with T2DM and type 1 diabetes (T1DM) over 40 years of age are at high and very high cardiovascular risk [5]. How should patients with diabetes be treated from the onset of the disease and what indicators should be followed? The cornerstone in assessing the effect of glycemic control on the development of complications in patients with T1DM during intensive treatment was laid by the DCCT (Diabetes Control and Complications Trial) study [6]. The DCCT study (mean glycosylated hemoglobin HbA1c level ~7% (53 mmol/mol)) showed a reduction in the development and progression of early microvascular and neurological

complications associated with diabetes, by 34–76% compared to the traditional treatment group (HbA1c at ~9% (75 mmol/mol)) for an average of 6.5 years of therapy. Intensive therapy was associated with weight gain and a threefold increase in the risk of hypoglycemia. At the end of DCCT, a long-term observational study, EDIC (Epidemiology of Diabetes Interventions and Complications study), was initiated. Despite the convergence of HbA1c levels between the two groups, the development and progression of complications was still significantly less in the intensive treatment group compared with the conventional treatment group; this phenomenon has been called "metabolic memory". The DCCT trial demonstrated a significant reduction in early complications with intensive care, and the phenomenon of metabolic memory during the EDIC period contributed to a significant reduction in the burden of complications over time—a 57% risk of cardiovascular events and a 33% mortality rate in the intensive treatment group compared with traditional treatment group [6]. Follow-up up to 29 years identified HbA1c as the strongest modifiable risk factor for a first cardiovascular event (RR 1.38; 95% CI 1.21–1.56 per 1% HbA1c); serious cardiovascular event (MACE) - non-fatal myocardial infarction (MI), non-fatal stroke, cardiovascular death (RR 1.54; 95% CI 1.30–1.82) [7]. In T2DM, the importance of early targeting (from the onset of the disease) on glycemic control to prevent complications was shown in the UKPDS (United Kingdom Prospective Diabetes Study) study [8, 9]. This research, initiated almost 50 years ago when routine therapeutic interventions of today were not yet available (eg, the use of statins), has had a tremendous impact on the practice of treating T2DM. The UKPDS study, initiated in 1977 at the John Radcliffe Hospital in Oxford (UK), had three stages: the first - from 1977 to 1997. (almost 43,000 patient-years of observation), the second - from 1997 to 2007. (67,000 patient-years), the third - from 2001 to 2021. (78,000 patient-years). In summary, a 44-year follow-up period has now been reached, and data are available on the long-term effects of intensive glycemic control in T2DM. A total of 4209 people (23 clinical sites) with newly diagnosed T2DM, mostly white men, were randomized at baseline. The effect of intensive glycemic control with either insulin or sulfonylureas (metformin in overweight patients) was studied compared with traditional therapy. Diabetes complications, diabetes-related mortality, and all-cause mortality were recorded. The results of the first period of UKPDS are well known and have formed the basis of the global concept of treatment of T2DM: intensive glycemic control reduced the risk of all diabetes-related endpoints, microvascular complications, MI and all-cause mortality. And

treatment with metformin was associated with a greater reduction in risk, making the drug a first-line treatment for many years. Although the glycemic differences between the intensive control and usual care groups disappeared soon after the end of the study, the benefits of the former were maintained during the observation period. However, UKPDS continues to be a source of data influencing the global concept of T2DM treatment. The main question after 44 years of UKPDS research, highlighted at the 2022 EASD Congress, is whether there is a “legacy effect”, i.e. Does the effect of strict glucose control persist after the end of the initial active phase of the trial? First identified in the 30-year UKPDS analysis [10], this effect remains virtually unchanged up to 44 years of follow-up. Data were presented for all endpoints related to diabetes, MI, microvascular complications, and all-cause mortality. In the sulfonylurea/insulin group compared with conventional therapy, the relative risk reduction after 44 years was 10, 15, 26 and 11%, respectively, and for metformin compared with conventional therapy the corresponding figures were: 19, 31, 10 and 25% [11]. . These significant results highlight the critical importance of identifying and aggressively treating T2DM “at the earliest opportunity.” One of the study coordinators, Professor Ruri Holman, when explaining the “legacy effect”, emphasized the long-term historical importance of HbA1c control, as a potential increase in all-cause mortality was identified for a 1% increase in HbA1c levels (Figure 1). Prof. R. Holman suggested that the “legacy effect” is essentially a protection against hyperglycemia, which activates oxidative stress, the formation of proteins, advanced glycation end products, and epigenetic changes leading to the effects of inflammatory proteins. He added that the larger size of metformin's "legacy" effect suggests that additional drug-related protective mechanisms, such as inhibition of inflammatory pathways, may be at play. Later N. Laiteerapong et al. [12] determined the effect of delayed glycemic control in a cohort study of 34,737 patients with newly diagnosed T2DM. The authors examined the associations between HbA1c 9.0% (>75 mmol/mol) and various periods of early exposure (0–1, 0–2, 0–3, 0–4, 0–5, 0–6, and 0–7 years), the incidence of micro- and macrovascular complications and mortality in these patients with an average follow-up of 13 years. Compared with HbA1c 6.5% (>48 mmol/mol) was associated with more frequent micro- and macrovascular events, and HbA1c >7.0% (>53 mmol/mol) was associated with increased mortality. These results support the idea that immediate treatment, aimed at careful and long-term glycemic control immediately after diagnosis, necessary to prevent the long-term risk of diabetes complications and increased mortality. The significance of the

first UKPDS results for the scientific community and practical medicine is illustrated by the fact that after their presentation, a whole cascade of multicenter studies on similar issues was launched. In order to evaluate the protective role of effective glycemic control to prevent fatal and non-fatal cardiovascular events in patients with T2DM, but with a long history of the disease and high cardiovascular risk, several large-scale prospective studies with a similar design were initiated almost simultaneously - ACCORD (Action to Control Cardiovascular Risk in Diabetes), VADT (Veterans Affairs Diabetes Trial) and ADVANCE (Action in Diabetes and Vascular Disease: Preterax and Diamicron Modified Release Controlled Evaluation) [13–15]. The ACCORD and VADT trials used a strategy of rapid intensification of therapy with the introduction regimens of multiple oral antihyperglycemic agents and insulin, whereas the ADVANCE trial used a much more cautious escalation strategy with the original gliclazide MB (Diabeton MB®) and other drugs, resulting in a much faster reduction in HbA1c (within 3–6 months) in ACCORD and VADT compared with 2 years in the ADVANCE study. This resulted in significant weight gain in patients in the intensive glycemic control groups in the ACCORD (3.5 kg) and VADT (8.4 kg) studies, but not in the ADVANCE study (0.1 kg). In addition, the incidence of severe hypoglycemia in the ACCORD and VADT studies was 6 times higher than in the ADVANCE study.

Conclusion. We can conclude that the second decade of the 21st century. has already become routinely characterized as a time of paradigm shift in the treatment of T2DM. The cardio-reno-metabolic approach and the expansion of NGLT-2 drugs into other areas of medicine (primarily cardiology and nephrology) open up promising prospects for improving the prognosis of patients. At the same time, the above data on the importance of early achievement of target glycemic control emphasize that in T2DM, it is the combination of approaches that provides maximum benefits for patients: providing organ protection with glucose-lowering drugs with proven properties to influence outcomes and prognosis, as well as achieving adequate glycemic control throughout the course of the disease (the duration of which is often measured over several decades), with the inevitable need to both overcome clinical inertia and take into account the dynamically changing individual characteristics of the status of a particular patient.

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IGG4-RELATED DISEASES IN THE BACKGROUND OF DIABETES MELLITUS

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Annotation. *IgG4-related disease (IgG4-CD) is characterized by the appearance of tumor-like foci in one or more organs, occurring synchronously or metachronously, due to fibroinflammatory changes with hypersecretion of immunoglobulin G subclass 4 (IgG4) in tissues and/or serum. Diabetes mellitus (DM) develops in 43–68% of patients with IgG4-related pancreatitis. Diabetes in the setting of IgG4-SD can be caused by both damage to the endocrine pancreas and the use of glucocorticosteroids, but its course is moderate, with a rare need for insulin therapy. In both cases, the use of genetic engineering biological therapy with rituximab may be accompanied by an improvement in carbohydrate metabolism. This article presents a clinical observation of the course of diabetes and the characteristics of the need for antidiabetic therapy over a period of 1.5 years in a patient receiving treatment for IgG4-CD.*

KEYWORDS: *IgG4-related disease; diabetes; autoimmune pancreatitis; glucocorticoids; rituximab*

IGG4-АССОЦИИРОВАННЫЕ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯ НА ФОНЕ САХАРНОГО ДИАБЕТА

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***Аннотация.** IgG4-ассоциированное заболевание (IgG4-CD) характеризуется появлением опухолеподобных очагов в одном или нескольких органах, протекающих синхронно или метакронно, вследствие фибровоспалительных изменений с гиперсекрецией иммуноглобулина G подкласса 4 (IgG4) в тканях и/или сыворотке крови. Сахарный диабет (СД) развивается у 43–68% больных IgG4-ассоциированным панкреатитом. Сахарный диабет на фоне IgG4-SD может быть обусловлен как поражением эндокринной системы поджелудочной железы, так и применением глюкокортикостероидов, но течение его умеренное, с редкой необходимостью инсулинотерапии. В обоих случаях применение генно-инженерной биологической терапии ритуксимабом может сопровождаться улучшением углеводного обмена. В статье представлены клиническое наблюдение течения сахарного диабета и особенности необходимости антидиабетической терапии на протяжении 1,5 лет у пациента, получающего лечение по поводу IgG4-CD.*

Ключевые слова: IgG4-ассоциированные заболевания; диабет; аутоиммунный панкреатит; глюкокортикоиды; ритуксимаб.

Introduction. IgG4-related disease (IgG4-S3) is an immune-mediated chronic systemic disease characterized by the appearance of tumor-like foci in one or more organs, occurring synchronously or metachronously, due to fibroinflammatory changes with hypersecretion of immunoglobulin G of the 4th subclass (IgG4) in tissues and/or blood serum [1]. Endocrine manifestations of IgG4-CD include pancreatitis with the development of diabetes mellitus (DM), as well as Riedel's fibrosing thyroiditis and lymphocytic hypophysitis. Autoimmune pancreatitis within the framework of IgG4-C3 (AIP type 1) is often accompanied by damage to other target organs with the development of sialadenitis, biliary stenosis, interstitial lung disease, orbital pseudotumor, nephritis, etc. In such cases, a biopsy of these organs with the detection of characteristic histological signs of the disease, such as moiré-like fibrosis, obliterating phlebitis, lymphoplasmacytic infiltration, makes it possible to verify the diagnosis. Similar histological changes can be detected in the tissues of the pancreas, but its biopsy is not performed in routine clinical practice for IgG4-C3 [2]. In the early stages of the disease, clinical symptoms may be absent. As the disease progresses, signs of cholestasis appear, which forms when the pancreas compresses the common bile duct, as well as such nonspecific clinical manifestations as mild or moderate

abdominal pain, general fatigue, and weight loss. In 17% of patients, the disease may be asymptomatic [3]. In such cases, damage to the pancreas may be an incidental finding during instrumental examination of the abdominal organs. AIP type 1 is characterized by a diffuse increase in the size of the pancreas with the formation of a “sausage-shaped appearance”, a rectangular shape at the tail (“clipped tail sign”). Involvement of the main duct of the gland is also noted with damage to more than 1/3 of its length in one fragment or in the form of a multifocal lesion with alternating areas of narrowing or disappearance of the duct without previous dilatation or other signs of obstructive pancreatitis [4]. Laboratory data show signs of cholestasis, increased levels of total protein and gammaglobulins, IgG4 in the blood, and increased ESR [5]. According to studies, diabetes develops among 43–68% of patients with IgG4-AIP, but its course is moderate, with a rare need for insulin therapy. Diabetes may be the first and only manifestation of type 1 AIP [6]. Glucocorticosteroids (GCS) are used as first-line drugs for the treatment of AIP type 1, and in fairly high doses - 0.6 mg/kg/day. Interestingly, during GCS therapy, a “paradoxical” effect of improving glycemic parameters may be observed [7]. This article describes the course of diabetes and changes in antidiabetic therapy over 1.5 years in a patient treated with IgG4-SD.

CASE DESCRIPTION The patient is a Caucasian man, 41 years old, who applied to the Federal State Budgetary Institution “Research Institute of Rheumatology named after. V.A. Nasonova” in October 2020 with complaints of severe general weakness, jaundice of the skin, diffuse skin itching, discomfort in the epigastrium, nausea, and weight loss of 26 kg since January 2020. Since 2017, he has noted the emergence and increase of general weakness and fatigue. In March 2019, attacks of hepatic colic appeared and he received symptomatic therapy. At the end of 2019, a hematologist diagnosed acquired hemophilia with deficiency of factors IX, XI, XII. Due to the absence of a specific hemorrhagic clinical picture, it is recommended to refrain from specific therapy. Also, at the end of 2019, swelling of the eyelids appeared in the morning. According to computed tomography (CT) of the orbits from March 2020, a massive enlargement of the lacrimal glands on both sides and hyperplastic polysinusitis was detected. In May 2020, an MRI of the abdominal cavity revealed a large hypodense formation in the pancreas with edema of the parapancreatic tissue, lymphadenopathy in the area of the parapancreatic tissue, and multiple low-density foci in both kidneys. The IgG4 value in the blood was 3 g/l (0.1–1.35 g/l). In August 2020, he applied for a correspondence consultation at the Federal State Budgetary Institution “NIIR named after. V.A. Nasonova”, the diagnosis was established: IgG4-S3

(autoimmune pancreatitis? dacryoadenitis, sialadenitis?). At the end of August 2020, with clinical manifestations of obstructive jaundice, the patient was hospitalized in a surgical hospital at his place of residence. Due to acquired hemophilia, surgical treatment was refused. A number of studies were completed in October 2020. According to positron emission tomography combined with CT (PET-CT): accumulation of a radiopharmaceutical (^{18}F -FDG) was recorded in the spleen, thickened lacrimal glands, and kidneys; totally in the enlarged pancreas; in the lymph nodes: cervical-supraclavicular, retromammary and axillary, mediastinal (upper paratracheal, preaortic at the level of the left main bronchus, bifurcation bronchopulmonary), hepatic hilum, common and external iliac on both sides. On a CT scan of the abdominal organs, attention is drawn to a diffuse increase in the size of the pancreas. As part of the differential diagnosis, lymphoproliferative disease was excluded, however, due to the atypical clinical picture (severe, extensive multiorgan damage), BCL2-negativity, the absence of mutations involving the BCL6/3q27, cMYC/8q24, BCL2/18q21 gene loci, the absence of B-cell clonality, the diagnosis of lymphoma was excluded. In October 2020, due to deterioration of his condition - severe general weakness, icteric skin, diffuse skin itching, feeling of discomfort in the epigastrium, nausea, weight loss (by 26 kg since January 2020), he was hospitalized in the hospital of the Federal State Budgetary Institution "NIIR named after. V.A. Nasonova" for verification of diagnosis and correction of therapy. During the examination: total bilirubin 285.5 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, direct bilirubin 274.51 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, alkaline phosphatase 214.0 U/L, fasting glucose 11.7 mmol/L (Table 1). Immunological blood test: rheumatoid factor - negative, IgG4 12.5 g/l (normal) Considering the severity of the condition, the active inflammatory process, insulin therapy was chosen for the initial treatment of diabetes: Glulisine 6 U 3 times a day, Glargine 20 U/day (Table 2). During subsequent hospitalizations in October-November, rituximab 500 mg was reintroduced intravenously. A total of 2000 mg of rituximab was administered, and pulse therapy with methylprednisolone was performed twice (250 mg with a gradual reduction in the dose of methylprednisolone, first to 24 mg/day, then 22 mg /day for 1 month). Subsequently, Glimepiride 4 mg/day, Linagliptin 5 mg/day were used as antidiabetic therapy in October 2020; in December 2020, the dose of methylprednisolone was reduced to 12 mg. To correct hyperglycemia, he was again transferred to Glulisine 6 U 3 times / day, Glargine 12 U / day. In December 2020, he was hospitalized at the NIIR. Before admission to the hospital, the patient was objectively noted to have swelling of the feet, and subsequently a decrease in pastosity. The occurrence of this condition was regarded as an effect

of the therapy. Since December 2020, over the course of several weeks, positive dynamics of edema have been noted, as well as a decrease in the intensity of jaundice, and an improvement in overall well-being. PET-CT was performed in March 2021. Compared with PET-CT from October 2020, pronounced positive dynamics were observed in the form of resorption of all previously determined changes in the lymph nodes, lacrimal glands, pancreas, liver, kidneys, prostate gland, seminal vesicles, and resolution of pericardial effusion. In March 2021, he was hospitalized at the Research Institute of Rheumatology for the planned administration of rituximab 500 mg, pulse therapy with methylprednisolone 250 mg followed by methylprednisolone 1 mg/day, a change in hypoglycemic therapy - a reduction in insulin doses - Glargine 7 U 1 r/day, Actrapid 5 U 2 times a day, and in December 2021 he was hospitalized again for the planned administration of rituximab 500 mg. DM therapy was changed - insulin was canceled and Ipragliflozin 50 mg/day was prescribed. Currently, therapy with long-acting metformin 500 mg/day is being carried out with full achievement of individual glycemic targets. The choice of glucose-lowering therapy was made based on the severity of the patient's condition, and subsequently, at the outpatient stage, based on the indicators of carbohydrate metabolism and medications available for obtaining. Subsequently, Glimepiride 4 mg/day, Linagliptin 5 mg/day were used as antidiabetic therapy in October 2020; in December 2020, the dose of methylprednisolone was reduced to 12 mg.

CONCLUSION. Diabetes developing against the background of IgG4-D3 can be caused by both damage to the endocrine part of the pancreas and the use of corticosteroids. In both cases, the use of genetic engineering biological therapy with rituximab may be accompanied by an improvement in carbohydrate metabolism, either due to a reduction in the dose of GCS, or against the background of regression of pancreatitis. Features of the course of diabetes in patients with IgG4-CD require further study with the study of larger samples of patients.

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OLIV TA'LIM TALABALARI O'RTASIDA JISMONIY RIVOJLANISHNI OSHIRISHDA VOLEYBOLNING O'RNI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola oliy ta'lim tizimida talabalar o'rtasida jismoniy rivojlanishni rag'batlantirishda voleybolning ahamiyatini o'rganadi. Dunyo miqyosida mashhur sport turi bo'lgan voleybol ko'plab jismoniy imtiyozlarni taklif etadi, jumladan yurak-qon tomir tizimi, mushaklarning kuchi, chaqqonlik, muvofiqlashtirish va moslashuvchanlik. Voleybolda muntazam ishtirok etish orqali talabalar o'zlarining umumiy salomatligi va farovonligini yaxshilashlari, muvozanatli turmush tarzini shakllantirishlari mumkin. Bundan tashqari, sport ijtimoiy o'zaro ta'sirni, jamoada ishlashni va etakchilik qobiliyatlarini rivojlantiradi va har tomonlama rivojlanishga hissa qo'shadi. Ushbu maqola voleybolning oliy o'quv yurtlari talabalariga ta'sirini o'rganadi va uning umrbod jismoniy tayyorgarligini oshirishdagi rolini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: voleybol, oliy ta'lim, jismoniy rivojlanish, yurak-qon tomir sog'ligi, mushaklarning kuchi, epcillik, muvofiqlashtirish, moslashuvchanlik, ijtimoiy o'zaro ta'sir, jamoada ishlash, yetakchilik qobiliyatlari.

ROLE OF VOLLEYBALL IN INCREASING PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT AMONG STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article examines the importance of volleyball in promoting physical development among students in higher education. A globally popular sport, volleyball offers many physical benefits, including cardiovascular, muscular strength, agility, coordination and flexibility. By regularly participating in volleyball, students can improve their overall health and well-being, and build a balanced lifestyle. In addition, sports develop social interaction, teamwork and leadership skills and contribute to all-round development. This article examines the impact of volleyball on college students and highlights its role in lifelong fitness.

Key words: volleyball, higher education, physical development, cardiovascular health, muscular strength, agility, coordination, flexibility, social interaction, teamwork, leadership skills.

Kirish. Jismoniy faollik shaxsning umumiy rivojlanishida, ayniqsa oliy ta'limning shakllanish yillarida hal qiluvchi rol o'ynaydi. Sport va ko'ngilochar mashg'ulotlar bilan shug'ullanish nafaqat jismoniy tayyorgarlikni yaxshilaydi, balki ijtimoiy muloqot va shaxsiy o'sishni ham rag'batlantiradi. Turli sport turlari orasida voleybol o'quvchilarning jismoniy rivojlanishini rag'batlantirish uchun ajoyib tanlov sifatida ajralib turadi.

1. Kardiovaskulyar Fitness

Voleybolda muntazam ishtirok etish doimiy harakatni talab qiladi, bu yurak-qon tomir salomatligini sezilarli darajada yaxshilaydi. Sakrash, sho'ng'in va tez yo'nalishni o'zgartirish kombinatsiyasi yurak tezligini oshiradi va shu bilan chidamlilik va chidamlilikni oshiradi. Voleybol bilan doimiy shug'ullanish orqali talabalar mustahkam yurak-qon tomir tizimini rivojlantiradilar, bu esa keyingi hayotda yurak bilan bog'liq kasalliklar xavfini kamaytiradi.

2. Mushaklar kuchi va chidamliligi

Voleybol yuqori va pastki tananing mushaklarini, jumladan qo'llar, elkalar, oyoqlar va yadrolarni tez-tez ishlatishni o'z ichiga oladi. Spiking, blokirovka va sho'ng'in kuch va quvvatni talab qiladi, bu esa ozg'in mushak massasining rivojlanishiga olib keladi. Bundan tashqari, o'yin davomida harakatlarning takroriy tabiati mushaklarning chidamliligini oshiradi, bu esa o'quvchilarga o'yinlar va mashg'ulotlar davomida optimal ishlash imkonini beradi.

3. Chaqqonlik va muvofiqlashtirish

Voleybolning dinamik tabiati tezkor reaksiyalar va aniq harakatlarni talab qiladi. O'yinchilar to'pning traektoriyasini oldindan bilishlari, o'z pozitsiyalarini mos ravishda o'zgartirishlari va turli xil ko'nikmalarni mohirlik bilan bajarishlari kerak. Bunday talablar chaqqonlik, muvofiqlashtirish va fazoviy ongni kuchaytiradi, motorni boshqarish va sezgirlikni yaxshilaydi.

4. Moslashuvchanlik

Voleybol to'pini qabul qilish, uzatish ko'nikmalarni bajarish uchun keng ko'lamlil harakatni talab qiladi. Sport bilan shug'ullanadigan muntazam cho'zilish mashqlari va dinamik harakatlar moslashuvchanlik va bo'g'imlarning harakatchanligini yaxshilaydi, jarohatlar xavfini kamaytiradi. Kengaytirilgan moslashuvchanlik, shuningdek, umumiy jismoniy sifatlar va boshqa jismoniy faoliyatda ishlashni yaxshilaydi.

5. Ijtimoiy hamkorlik va jamoaviy ish

Voleybolda ishtirok etish o'quvchilar o'rtasida do'stlik va jamoaviy hamkorlikni rivojlantiradi. Strategiyalash, muloqot qilish va o'yin rejalarini amalga oshirish uchun jamoadoshlar bilan hamkorlik qilish qimmatli shaxslararo

ko'nikmalarni singdiradi. Bundan tashqari, jamoaviy sportning qo'llab-quvvatlovchi muhiti o'zaro hurmat, hamdardlik va hamkorlikni rivojlantiradi va akademik hamjamiyatda ijobiy ijtimoiy muhitga hissa qo'shadi.

6. Yetakchilik mahorati

Voleybol o'quvchilarga maydonda ham, maydon tashqarisida ham yetakchilik fazilatlarini rivojlantirish imkoniyatini beradi. Sardorlar va jamoa rahbarlari qaror qabul qilish, jamoadoshlarini rag'batlantirish va hamjihatlikni rivojlantirish kabi rollarni o'z zimmalariga oladilar. Bunday tajribalar o'quvchilarni turli sohalarda kelajakdagi yetakchilik rollariga tayyorlab, ishonch, chidamlilik va mas'uliyatni rivojlantiradi.

Xulosa

Xulosa qilib aytadigan bo'lsak, voleybol oliy o'quv yurtlari talabalari o'rtasida jismoniy rivojlanish va yaxlit farovonlikni oshirish uchun samarali vosita bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Sport yurak-qon tomir tizimini, mushaklar kuchini, chaqqonlikni, muvofiqlashtirishni va moslashuvchanlikni yaxshilaydigan keng qamrovli mashqlarni taklif qiladi. Bundan tashqari, voleybol ijtimoiy o'zaro ta'sirni, jamoaviy ish va etakchilik qobiliyatlarini rivojlantiradi va umumiy kollej tajribasini oshiradi. Voleybolni talabalar shaharchasidagi dam olish dasturlari va maktabdan tashqari mashg'ulotlarga kiritish orqali ta'lim muassasalari talabalarga faol, sog'lom turmush tarzini olib borish va muhim hayotiy ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish imkonini beradi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yhati

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11-12 YOSHLI O'QUVCHI QIZLAR UCHUN VOLEYBOLNING FIZIOLOGIK VA PSIXOLOGIK FOYDALI XUSUSIYATLARI

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O'zbekiston davlat jismoniy tarbiya va sport universiteti Farg'ona filiali Sport o'yinlari nazariyasi va uslubiyati kafedrsi assistent o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya: Voleybol o'ynash 11-12 yoshli o'quvchi qizlarning tanasi va ongiga katta ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin. Yurak-qon tomir sog'lig'ini, tayanch-harakat tizimini mustahkamlash, suyak zichligi va psixologik farovonlikni mustahkamlash orqali voleybol o'smir qizlar uchun jismoniy faoliyatga yaxlit yondashuvni taklif etadi. O'qituvchilar, ota-onalar va siyosatchilar sog'lom va baxtli avlodni tarbiyalash uchun qizlarni voleybol kabi sport turlariga jalb etish muhimligini tan olishlari kerak.

Kalit so'zlar: ota-onalar, voleybol, jismoniy faollik, o'quvchi qizlar, o'smirlik, sog'likka foyda, o'qituvchilar, sog'lom va baxtli, avlod, tarbiyalash.

PHYSIOLOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL BENEFITS OF VOLLEYBALL FOR SCHOOLGIRLS AGED 11-12 YEARS.

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Abstract: Playing volleyball can have a great positive effect on the body and mind of 11-12-year-old schoolgirls. By promoting cardiovascular health, musculoskeletal health, bone density, and psychological well-being, volleyball offers a holistic approach to physical activity for teenage girls. Educators, parents and policy makers need to recognize the importance of getting girls involved in sports like volleyball to raise a healthy and happy generation.

Key words: parents, volleyball, physical activity, schoolgirls, adolescence, health benefits, teachers, healthy and happy, generation, parenting.

Kirish

Muntazam jismoniy faollik maktab yoshidagi bolalarning jismoniy va ruhiy salomatligini mustahkamlashda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Biroq, ko'plab qizlar o'g'il bolalarga qaraganda kamroq jismoniy faoliyat bilan shug'ullanishadi, bu esa keyinchalik hayotda potentsial salomatlik nomutanosibligiga olib keladi. Dinamik

jamoaviy sport turi bo'lgan voleybol 11-12 yoshli o'quvchi qizlarning faolligi uchun qiziqarli va samarali usulni taklif etadi. Ushbu maqola voleybolning ushbu yosh guruhidagi qizlarning tanasi va ongiga ijobiy ta'sirini o'rganishga qaratilgan.

Umuman olganda, voleybol 11-12 yoshli maktab o'quvchilarining jismoniy va ruhiy rivojlanishiga yaxlit yondashuvni ta'minlaydi, sog'lom va faol turmush tarzini targ'ib qiladi, shuningdek, qimmatli hayotiy ko'nikmalarni beradi.

Yurak-qon tomir salomatligi: Voleybol bilan shug'ullanish yurak-qon tomir tizimini yaxshilashga yordam beradigan yugurish, sakrash va sho'ng'in kabi doimiy harakatni talab qiladi. Voleybol bilan muntazam shug'ullanish yurak va o'pka faoliyatini yaxshilaydi, keyingi hayotda yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari xavfini kamaytiradi. Bundan tashqari, voleybolning intervalgacha tabiati, yuqori intensiv mashg'ulotlardan so'ng qisqa dam olish intervallari bilan yurak-qon tomir chidamliligi va samaradorligini oshiradi.

Muskul-skelet tizimining kuchi: Voleybol turli mushak guruhlarini, jumladan, oyoqlar, yadro, qo'llar va elkarni o'z ichiga oladi va bu umumiy mushak-skelet tizimining kuchiga hissa qo'shadi. To'pni to'sish yoki to'sish uchun sakrash tananing pastki kuchini oshiradi, tepadan o'tish va xizmat ko'rsatish esa tananing yuqori mushaklarini rivojlantiradi. Bundan tashqari, voleybolda zarur bo'lgan yo'nalishning tez o'zgarishi va tez reflekslar chaqqonlik va muvofiqlashtirishni kuchaytiradi, bu esa umumiy jismoniy tayyorgarlikni yaxshilaydi.

Suyak salomatligi: O'smirlik suyak rivojlanishi uchun juda muhim davr bo'lib, voleybol kabi og'irlikni ko'taruvchi mashg'ulotlarda qatnashish suyak salomatligiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin. Voleybol mashqlari va o'yinlari paytida sakrash va qo'nishning takroriy ta'siri suyaklarning o'sishi va zichligini rag'batlantiradi, keyinchalik hayotda osteoporoz xavfini kamaytiradi. Muntazam voleybol mashg'ulotlari bilan shug'ullanadigan maktab o'quvchilarining suyaklari kuchliroq bo'ladi, bu tez o'sish va rivojlanishning ushbu bosqichida ayniqsa muhimdir.

Psixologik farovonlik: Jismoniy salomatlikdan tashqari, voleybol 11-12 yoshli o'quvchi qizlar uchun ko'plab psixologik afzalliklarni taklif etadi. Voleybol kabi jamoaviy sport turlari ijtimoiy o'zaro ta'sir, hamkorlik va muloqot qobiliyatlarini rivojlantiradi, o'yinchilar o'rtasida tegishlilik va do'stlik tuyg'usini rivojlantiradi. Qolaversa, voleybolning raqobatbardoshligi shaxsning rivojlanishi uchun qimmatli bo'lgan chidamlilik, qat'iyat, sport mahorati kabi fazilatlarni singdiradi. Voleybol bilan muntazam shug'ullanish, shuningdek, stress va

tashvishlarni kamaytirishga yordam beradi, maktab o'quvchilarining umumiy ruhiy farovonligini oshiradi.

Fiziologik foydalari

Yurak-qon ishlab chiqaradi: Voleybol doimiy harakat, sakrash va tez yugurishni o'z ichiga oladi, bu yurak-qon ishlab chiqarishligi va yurak sog'lig'ini yaxshilaydi.

Mushaklar rivojlanishi: Voleybol o'ynashni turli mushaklarni davolash, shu va hokazolarni yo'qotishlar, muntazamning kuchini va ishlashini o'ziga olib kelishi mumkin.

Suyakning mustahkamligi: Voleybolning og'irlikni ko'taruvchi tabiati, ayniqsa sakrash va qo'nish, suyaklarning rivojlanishi va zichligiga yordam beradi.

Muvofiqlashtirish va tozalash: Voleybol qo'llar va tanani o'rtada aniqlashtirish talab qiladi. Ush ko'rinishini mashq qilish uchun ishlatish mumkin bo'lgan tozalash va tozalash mumkin.

Moslashuvchanlik: Voleybolda sho'ng'in, blokirovka va to'p bilan muomala qilish kabi dinamik harakat bo'g'inlar va harakat doirasini rag'batlantiradi.

Og'irlikni boshqarish: Voleybol muntazam jismoniy faollik sog'lom vazni saqlashga yordam beradi, semirishni va u bilan bog'liq sog'liq muammolarini nazorat qiladi.

Psixologik foydalari

Jamoaviy ish: Voleybol o'yinchilar o'rtasida hamkorlik, muloqot va o'zaro yordamni rag'batlantiradigan jamoaviy sport turidir. Bu qizlarga jamoada ishlashning ko'rishni rivojlantirishga yordam beradi va tuyg'usini rivojlantirish.

O'z-‘ziga ishonch: Voleybol mahoratini egallash va jamoao muvaffaqiyatiga yosh qizlarda o'ziga bo'lgan hurmat va ishonchni qo'shish.

Intizom va diqqat: Voleybol texnikani samarali ishlash uchun konsentratsiya va intizomni talab qiladi. Muntazam amaliyot diqqatni jamlash va intizomni yaxshilash mumkin, bu esa hayotning sohalariga, masalan, akademiklarga boshqa mumkin.

Stressni bartaraf etish: Jismoniy faollik, shu narsa voleybol o'ynash stressni kuchaytirishgan va kayfiyatni yaxshilaydigan endorfinlarni hosil qiladi.

Xulosa

Xulosa qilib aytadigan bo'lsak, jismoniy faollik, ayniqsa, o'smirlik davridagi bolalarning umumiy farovonligi uchun juda muhimdir. Ommaviy jamoaviy sport turi bo'lgan voleybol 11-12 yoshli o'quvchi qizlar uchun ko'plab

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fiziologik va psixologik imtiyozlarni beradi. Ushbu ilmiy maqolada voleybol o'ynashning organizmga ijobiy ta'siri, jumladan, yurak-qon tomir tizimi, mushak-skelet tizimining mustahkamligi, muvofiqlashtirish va ruhiy farovonlik yaxshilanishi ko'rib chiqiladi. Ushbu imtiyozlarni tushunish o'qituvchilar, ot-onalar va siyosatchilarni maktab yoshidagi qizlar o'rtasida voleybol va shunga o'xshash jismoniy mashg'ulotlarni ommalashtirish muhimligi haqida xabardor qilishi mumkin.

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TURLI TIKUV MASHINALARIDA CHOKLASHDA PARALLEL SAKROVCHI IGNALARNING MATEMATIK MODELI

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Annotatsiya: Taklif etilayotgan tikuv-trikotaj sanoatida, trikotaj matolaridan tayyorlangan erkaklar vetrovkasi, bolalar polo ko'ylagi, hamda, futbolka mahsulotlarini tikish va choklashda, elastikli xususiyati yuqori bo'lgan materiallarni choklari sifatli mustahkam bo'lishida, parallel sakrovchi ignalarning roli katta ahamiyatga egadir.

Bunday parallel ignali tikuv mashinalarini tadbiq etish natijasida respublikamizda import o'rnini bosa oladigan arzon va raqobatbardosh trikotaj matolardan tayyorlangan maxsulot ishlab chiqarish bilan bir vaqtda tikuv-trikotaj sanoatida, foydalanish imkoniyati tikuv texnologiyalariga yangi qadam bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: integral-differensial, fizik-matematik model, parallel ignalar, tikuv mashinasi, tayyor mato

MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF PARALLEL JUMPING NEEDLES IN SEWING MACHINES

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Abstract: In the proposed sewing-knitting industry, in the sewing and stitching of men's windbreakers, children's polo shirts, and t-shirts made of knitted fabrics, the role of parallel knitting needles is of great importance in the quality and durability of seams of materials with high elastic properties. .

As a result of the implementation of such parallel needle sewing machines, the possibility of using them in the sewing-knitting industry will be a new step in sewing technologies, along with the production of products made of cheap and competitive knitted fabrics that can replace imports in our republic.

Key words: integral-differential, physical-mathematical model, parallel needles, sewing machine, finished fabric

Kirish. Elastikli xususiyati yuqori bo‘lgan materiallarni tikishda sifatli tikilish va nuqsonsiz choklash uchun mavjud mashinaning vaqt birligida harakat mexanizimini konstruksiyasini takomillashtirish orqali ham erishish mumkin. Mavjud mashinada parallel ignalar oyoqning ko‘tarish balandligi 5-13 mm gacha, tikuv uzunligi 5 mm, parallel ignalar soni bitta, iplar soni ikkita bo‘lib. avtomatik ravishda ishlaydi.

Buning uchun tajriba o‘tkazish maqsadida Jack A4 B-C tikuv mashinasining tezligi 6000 rpm, ignalar orasidagi masofa 5,6 (6,4) mm, tikuv uzunligi 4,4 mm, oyoq ko‘tarish 5 mm. Joylashtiruvchi o‘rnatilgan doimiy servomotor, doimiy o‘zgaruvchan tezlikni boshqarish qulay bo‘lib, mexanik tikuv mashinasi tashqi va yashirin, ichki shikastlanishlarsiz har qanday matolarni tikish va choklash eng yaxshi va sifatli sanoat tikuv mashinasi tanlab olindi. (1-rasmga qarang)

Tikuv-trikotaj sanoatida parallel sakrovchi ignalarning choklashdagi nuqsonli bo‘lish yoki bo‘lmaslik muammosini xal qilishning asosiy manbasi raqobatbardosh zamonaviy matematik usullar hamda kompyuter texnologiyalardan foydalanishdir. Yangi texnologiyalarni qo‘llash natijasida jahon bozorida yuqori sifatli, raqobatbardosh mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarish tikuv-trikotaj sanoatining eng muhim vazifasidir [1].

1-rasm. JACK A4 B-C tikuv mashinasi mexanizimning ichki sxemasi

1. Mashinani harakatga keltiruvchi mexanizim bosh valik. Harakat yo‘nalishi.

2. Ilgarilanma harakat va moki iplarini harakatga keltiruvchi konussimon silindr mexanizimi.

3. Tikuv mashinasi harakatida choklashni amalga oshiruvchi parallel ignalarning sakrash mexanizimi.

4. Trikotaj matolarning choklashdagi ilgarilanma harakat mexanizimi. Harakat yo'nalishi.

Tikuv-trikotaj sanoatida parallel sakrovchi ignalarning choklashdagi nuqsonli bo'lish yoki bo'lmaslik muammosini xal qilishning asosiy manbasi raqobatbardosh zamonaviy matematik usullar hamda kompyuter texnologiyalardan foydalanishdir. Yangi texnologiyalarni qo'llash natijasida jahon bozorida yuqori sifatli, raqobatbardosh mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarish tikuv-trikotaj sanoatining eng muhim vazifasidir [1].

Shuningdek tikuv mashinasi bosh valigidagi aylanma harakat kuch ta'sirida paralel harakatlanayotgan ignalarni sakrashini moddiy nuqta deb olib, uning differensial tenglamasini integralasak. F kuchi ta'sirida harakatlanuvchi m massali ignaning moddiy nuqta uchun koordinata ko'rinishidagi nuqtaning harakat tenglamalarini aniqlaymiz. Tuzilgan fizik-matematik modellar yechimlaridan foydalanib choklash grafiklarini tasvirlanadi.

Bu yerda bizga ma'lumki F kuch vaqtga bog'liq, kuch nuqtaning fazodagi ignalarning holatiga bog'liq, kuch nuqtaning tezligiga ya'ni materiallarni choklashda ignalardan qoladigan teshikchalar harakatiga bog'liq.

Massasi m bo'lgan ignalar majburiy kuch ta'siri ostida T vaqt birligidagi harakatini quyidagi vector kuch formula bilan ifodalasak.

$$\vec{F} = \bar{i}b_1 \cos \alpha t + \bar{j}b_2 v_y + \bar{k}b_3 z \quad (1)$$

Bu erda b_1, b_2, b_3 boshlang'ich holatdagi ba'zi doimiy koeffitsientlar

$$x_0 = 0, y_0 = 0, z_0 \neq 0,$$

$$v_{x_0} = 0, v_{y_0} \neq 0, v_{z_0} = 0$$

Nuqtaning harakat tenglamalarini koordinata shaklida aniqlash kerak bo'ladi.

Buning uchun dekart koordinatalar o'qlariga T vaqt birligida sakrovchi ignalar qoldirgan eskizlarini proyeksiyasi, shu nuqtalar uchun differensial tenglamalar sistemasi tuzamiz

$$\begin{cases} m \frac{d^2 x}{dt^2} = a_1 \cos \alpha t \\ m \frac{d^2 y}{dt^2} = a_2 v_y \\ m \frac{d^2 z}{dt^2} = a_3 z \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

(2) differensial tenglamalar sistemaning birinchi tenglamasini ikkita birinchi tartibli tenglama sifatida ifodalansa quyidagi (3) tenglama kelib chiqadi

$$\begin{cases} m \frac{dv_x}{dt} = a_1 \cos \alpha t \\ \frac{dx}{dt} = v_x \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

(3) tenglamalar sistemasidagi birinchi tenglama ikkita o'zgaruvchili tenglama bo'lgani uchun tezlikning x o'qiga va T vaqtga proyeksiyasi bo'yicha o'zgaruvchilarni ajratib olamiz. Ya'ni

$$mdv_x = a_1 \cos \alpha t dt \quad (4)$$

(4) tenglamanbi integrallab yuboramiz va (5) tenglama hosil qilamiz.

$$\int mdv_x = \int a_1 \cos \alpha t dt \quad (5)$$

$$v_x = \frac{a_1}{m\alpha} \sin \alpha t + C_1 \quad (6)$$

(3) diferensial tenglamalar sistemasidan ikkinchi tenglamasini o'ng tomonidagi ifodaga (6) tenglamani o'ng tomonini tenglab X o'qiga proyeksiyasining vaqtga bog'liqliq. Tenglamani hosil qilamiz.

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{a_1}{m\alpha} \sin \alpha t + C_1 \quad (7)$$

(7) tenglamani o'zgaruvchilarini ajratib integrallab yuborsak natijada tenglamani yechimini aniqlaymiz

$$dx = \left(\frac{a_1}{m\alpha} \sin \alpha t + C_1 \right) dt \Rightarrow X = -\frac{a_1}{m\alpha^2} \cos \alpha t + C_1 t + C_2 \quad (8)$$

C_1 va C_2 o'zgaruvchilarni dastlabki shartlar asosida aniqlaymiz. (8) ifodaga X o'qi koordinatasining $t=0$ qiymatini qo'yib, C_2 ni hisoblaymiz.

$$0 = -\frac{a_1}{m\alpha^2} \cos \alpha 0 + C_1 0 + C_2 \quad \text{bundan} \quad C_2 = \frac{a_1}{m\alpha^2}$$

C_1 ni $t=0$ dagi v_x (6) tenglamadan aniqlaymiz $0 = \frac{a_1}{m\alpha} \sin \alpha 0 + C_1$

demak, $C_1 = 0$. Shunday qilib, (2) tenglamalar sistemaning birinchi tenglamasining yechimi quyidagi ko'rinishga ega $x = -\frac{a_1}{m\alpha^2} \cos \alpha t + \frac{a_1}{m\alpha^2}$

(2) tenglamalar sistemaning ikkinchi tenglamasi ham ikkita tenglama shaklida ifodalandi

$$\begin{cases} m \frac{dv_y}{dt} = a_2 v_y \\ \frac{dy}{dt} = v_y \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Birinchi tenglamadagi o'zgaruvchilarni ajratib, integrallab yuboramiz.

$$m \frac{dv_y}{dt} = a_2 v_y \Rightarrow \ln v_y = \frac{a_2}{m} t + \ln C_3 \text{ bundan } v_y \text{ ni topamiz}$$

(9) tenglamaning ikkinchi tengligini o'ng tomoniga olib borib qo'yamiz

$$\frac{dy}{dt} = C_3 e^{\frac{a_2 t}{m}}$$

tenglamani o'zgaruvchilarini ajratib, integrallab yuborsak

$$y = C_3 \frac{m}{a_2} e^{\frac{a_2 t}{m}} + c_4 \quad y = c_1 e^x + c_2 e^{-x} + c_3 \cos kx + c_4 \sin nx$$

yechimga ega bo'lamiz. C_3 va C_4 o'zgaruvchilarni dastlabki shartlar bilan aniqlanadi.

Yuqoridagi differensial tenglamalar sistemasining yechimlarini, bigalikda tasvirini matkad, geogebra ta'minot dasturi yordamida ko'rilsa ignalarni sakrashi natijasida quyidagi grafiklar hosil qilinadi.

$K=n=6$ $c_1=c_2=0$ $C_3=1, C_4=1$ Silindirsimon valni aylanish tezligi 3000 ayl/daq bo'lganda paralel ignalarning sakrashidan hosil bo'lgan orqa tomon chok grafigi ko'rinishi. Sakrash oralig'i 6-6.5 mm ga teng. Tasvirdan shuni ko'rish mumkinki choklar orasidagi masofa qisman uzoqlashi nuqsonsi lekin chok mustahkamligi yuqori emas. Elastiklik xususiyati yuqori bo'lgan mato uchun bunday choklash matoni tirishib qolish imkoniyatini beradi

$K=4.4$, $n=4.4$ $C_1=C_2=0, C_3=C_4=1$ silindirsimon valni aylanish tezligi 3000 ayl/daq bo'lganda paralel ignalarning sakrashidan hosil bo'lgan orqa tomon choki grafik ko'rinishi. Sakrash oralig'i 2-2.5. mm ga teng. Tasvirdan shuni ko'rish mumkinki dastlabki harakatdagi choklashda nuqson bilan boshlansada, tikuvning qolgan qismida choklar orasidagi masofa qisqa nuqsonsiz chok mustahkamligi yuqori. Elastiklik xususiyati yuqori bo'lgan mato uchun bunday choklash matoni tirishib qolishga imkoniyat beramadi. Chok tekis va chiroyli ko'rinishga ega.

$K=n=5$ $c_1=c_2=0, C_3=C_4=1$ Silindirsimon valni aylanish tezligi 3000 ayl/daq bo'lganda paralel ignalarning sakrashidan hosil bo'lgan orqa tomon chok grafigi ko'rinishi sakrash oralig'i 4-4.5 mm ga teng. Tasvirdan shuni ko'rish mumkinki choklar orasidagi masofa o'rtacha nuqsonsiz chok mustahkamligi yuqori. Elastiklik xususiyati yuqori bo'lgan mato uchun bunday choklash matoni tirishib qolishga imkoniyat beramadi. Chok tekis va chiroyli ko'rinishga ega.

Xulosa.

Tikuv vaqtida bosh silindirsimon valning aylanishi tezligi 4000 ayl/daq va undan yuqori bo'lganda paralel ignalarning sakrash oralig'i 2-2.5mm, 4-4.5mm, 5-5.5 mm bo'lganda silindrsimon valning tezligi hisobiga ilgarilanma vektorial harakat tezlashadi. Natijada tikuv mashinasida choklangan trikotaj matoning choklarida nuqsonlar soni ortib iplarning uzulishlari ortib boradi. Bu esa tikuv mashinasida choklangan matolarning nuqsonini ortishi bilan sifatsiz choklar nuqsonli bo'lishiga olib keladi.

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TUMORS OF THE FEMALE REPRODUCTIVE SYSTEM DURING DIABETES MELLITUS

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Relevance. *The article discusses various pathophysiological conditions and processes leading to the development of tumor diseases in diabetes mellitus. These include obesity, hyperglycemia, hyperinsulinemia, inflammation, and oxidative stress. Data from epidemiological studies are presented in which it was found that diabetes mellitus (both type 1 and type 2) increases the relative risk of developing tumors of the female reproductive system, such as ovarian and endometrial cancer, while for cervical cancer, vaginal cancer and vulvar cancer, such a relationship has not been clearly identified.*

Keywords: *diabetes; endometrial tumors; ovarian tumors; signaling pathways; neoplasm proteins.*

ОПУХОЛИ ЖЕНСКОЙ РЕПРОДУКТИВНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ ПРИ САХАРНОМ ДИАБЕТЕ

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Актуальность. В статье рассматриваются различные патофизиологические состояния и процессы, приводящие к развитию опухолевых заболеваний при сахарном диабете. К ним относятся ожирение, гипергликемия, гиперинсулинемия, воспаление и окислительный стресс. Представлены данные эпидемиологических исследований, в которых установлено, что сахарный диабет (как 1-го, так и 2-го типа) повышает относительный риск развития опухолей женской репродуктивной системы, таких как рак яичников и эндометрия, тогда как при раке шейки матки, раке влагалища и при раке вульвы такая взаимосвязь четко не выявлена.

Ключевые слова: диабет; опухоли эндометрия; опухоли яичников; сигнальные пути; белки новообразований.

Introduction. The assumption that there is a relationship between diabetes mellitus (DM) and malignant neoplasms was made more than 100 years ago [1]. The risk of developing cancer increases with both type 1 (DM1) and type 2 (DM2) diabetes [2]. Among all causes of death in patients with diabetes, cancer ranks second after cardiovascular diseases [3]. It should also be noted that approximately 8–18% of cancer patients suffer from diabetes [4]. Meta-analyses and large population-based studies have shown that diabetes is associated with an increased risk of mortality in cancer [5]. However, the underlying mechanisms of

the relationship between different types of diabetes and cancer (especially tumors of the female reproductive system) have not been summarized in detail. This review analyzes this relationship and describes the mechanisms of its occurrence.

Materials and methods. This literature review was carried out with the aim of critically assessing the collected material. The authors performed an electronic search for publications in the PubMed, Web of Science, ScienceDirect, and Scopus databases. The search terms included the words “diabetes mellitus”, “gynecologic cancers”, “ovarian cancer”, “endometrial cancer”, “cervical cancer”, “vaginal cancer” and “vulvar cancer”. The authors independently reviewed those articles whose titles and abstracts were relevant to the search terms. Disagreements between authors regarding eligibility were resolved by consensus. The review included studies published primarily within the last 15 years. Full texts of articles and their abstracts were analyzed.

Epidemiological aspects. The number of people with diabetes continues to increase worldwide, significantly increasing the burden on the healthcare system. According to the latest data, in 2021, the global prevalence of both types of diabetes among adults was 537 million people, and by 2045 it is expected to increase to 783 million people [6]. Diabetes is a fairly common disease among cancer patients, and is a proven risk factor for some solid malignancies, such as pancreatic, liver, colon, kidney, bladder and breast cancer [7]. Epidemiological studies have shown that cancers of the female reproductive system, including endometrial and ovarian (OC) cancer, are more common in people with diabetes. One meta-analysis showed a statistically significant association of T2DM with the risk of endometrial cancer (overall relative risk (RR) 2.10; 95% confidence interval (CI) 1.75–2.53). This meta-analysis also reported an association between T1DM and endometrial cancer (overall RR 3.15; 95% CI 1.07–9.29). In a study by Liu X. et al. provides data demonstrating that patients with T2DM have an increased risk of developing the types of cancer already mentioned above (colon, liver, pancreas, kidney), including endometrial cancer. The authors of the article suggest that the increased risk of developing cancer in patients with diabetes compared to their relatives is associated with various severe metabolic disorders [8]. It should be noted that many studies provide evidence that the incidence of cancer of the ovary, esophagus, endometrium, vulva and vagina, and thyroid gland is higher among women with T1DM.

Pathophysiological conditions and processes leading to the development of oncological diseases in diabetes mellitus

Hyperglycemia. Epidemiological data have shown that hyperglycemia is directly associated with an increased risk of colorectal, liver, gastric, lung and pancreatic cancer [10]. Cells of most types of malignancies predominantly express glucose transporter type 1, which has a high affinity for glucose. It is also worth mentioning the Warburg effect, in which in tumor cells glucose follows the energetically inefficient glycolysis pathway with a high level of lactate production. Increased glycolysis in tumor cells provides the materials necessary for the synthesis of nucleotides, amino acids and lipids [11]. Hyperglycemia stimulates the production of advanced glycation end products (AGEs). AGEs interact with a specific AGE receptor, which leads to activation of the NF- κ B (nuclear factor κ B) signaling pathway and the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in cells, thereby accelerating oxidative stress and leading to the activation of pro-inflammatory signaling pathways [10]. It has been demonstrated that AGEs and activation of downstream pathways promote tumor transformation of epithelial cells [12]. For example, hyperglycemia has been shown to stimulate the proliferation of pancreatic cancer cells through induction of epithelial growth factor (EGF) expression and transactivation of its receptor (EGFR) [13]. EGF and its receptor, in turn, play an important role in the pathogenesis of tumors of the female reproductive system, for example, ovarian cancer and cervical cancer (CC) [14]. In addition, hyperglycemia is responsible for DNA damage, which is the first stage of tumorigenesis [15].

Hyperinsulinemia. In T2DM, insulin resistance leads to the development of compensatory hyperinsulinemia. High concentrations of insulin in the blood play a key role in the pathogenesis of malignant neoplasms, which has been demonstrated in numerous studies both in vitro and in vivo [17]. Using endometrial cancer cell culture, it was found that, on the one hand, hyperinsulinemia leads to a slowdown in the process of mesenchymal-epithelial transition (as a consequence, metastasis and tumor invasion) by inhibiting the expression *COL1A1* (gene encoding the α 1 chain of type I collagen), *IRS2* (insulin receptor substrate-1), however, on the other hand, increases the level of expression *AMFR* (Autocrine Motility Factor Receptor), *FAF1* (FAS-associated factor 1), *MPP3* (Membrane Palmitoylated Protein 3), *PIP2* (phosphatidylinositol 4,5-diphosphate), *VEGFA* (vascular endothelial growth factor), as well as genes of other proteins that promote tumor development and progression [18]. It is assumed that the metabolic effects of insulin, which include the transport of

glucose into the cell, are mediated by activation of the PI3K/Akt signaling pathway, while the mitogenic effect is exerted on cells through Ras/Raf/MAPK (Rat sarcoma virus/RAF protooncogene serine/threonine-protein kinase/MitogenActivated Protein Kinase) signaling pathway, in this pathway the downstream kinases are MEK (Mitogen-Activated Kinase) and ERK (Extracellular signal-Regulated Kinase). Proinsulin and insulin have similar stimulatory effects on MAPK activation, proliferation and migration of breast cancer cells [19]. It is also necessary to note the importance of insulin-like growth factors (IGFs), which are involved in the development of malignant tumors [20].

Obesity. It is widely known that the majority of patients with prediabetes or T2DM are overweight or obese [23]. In obesity, according to the working group of the International Association for the Study of Cancer, there is an increased risk of developing 13 different neoplasms, including endometrial, esophageal, kidney and pancreatic cancer, hepatocellular carcinoma, cancer of the gastric cardia, meningioma; multiple myeloma, colorectal cancer, postmenopausal breast cancer, ovarian, gallbladder and thyroid cancer [24]. An umbrella review of systematic reviews and 204 meta-analyses also found an association between obesity and cancer. This association was especially pronounced for cancer of the gastrointestinal tract and cancer of the female reproductive system [25]. Data from 8 observational studies involving 635,642 patients suggest that bariatric surgery is associated with a reduced risk of all types of cancer (pooled odds ratio (OR) 0.72; 95% CI 0.59–0.87)), as well as obesity-related cancers (pooled OR 0.55; 95% CI 0.31–0.96), including breast cancer (pooled OR 0.50; 95% CI 0.25–0.99) [26].

Inflammation and oxidative stress. Inflammation is one of the key connecting elements between diabetes and cancer. Chronic low-grade inflammation in hypertrophied adipose tissue plays an important role in the pathogenesis of obesity-associated insulin resistance [34]. In turn, chronic inflammation is associated with increased levels of the already mentioned oxidative stress and ROS, which are critical for many processes in cancer development [35]. In addition, due to hyperglycemia, advanced glycation end products and their receptors lead to the development of oxidative stress and increased inflammation, which promotes cell growth, angiogenesis and metastasis [11]. Various studies have identified increased circulating levels of the proinflammatory cytokines IL-1 (interleukin-1), IL-6 (interleukin-6) and TNF- α (tumor necrosis factor-alpha) in patients with diabetes [36]. TNF- α promotes tumor development by activating NF- κ B and increasing the production of ROS

and reactive nitrogen species, which can cause DNA damage. This cytokine also stimulates the growth, proliferation, invasion and metastasis of tumor cells, as well as angiogenesis [37]. Elevated levels of IL-6 have been found in patients with pancreatic cancer, breast cancer, B-cell lymphoma and myeloma [38].

Conclusion. Tumors of the female reproductive system continue to be a serious problem for both patients and the healthcare system. The article provides a literary analysis to assess the influence of chronic hyperglycemia, hyperinsulinemia, systemic inflammation and oxidative stress, as well as changes in the level of sex hormones observed in diabetes on the formation of tumors of the female reproductive system.

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ВОЗРАСТНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ КАРДИРЕСПИРАТОРНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается комплексный подход в изучении возрастных особенностей изменения деятельности систем внешнего дыхания, газообмена и энергетического обмена детей и подростков в условиях жаркого климата Узбекистана при выполнении различных по характеру, объёму и интенсивности мышечных нагрузок.

Ключевые слова: адаптация, функциональная система, газообмен, кислород, мышечная деятельность, гибкость, подвижность.

AGE-RELATED FEATURES OF CHANGES IN THE ACTIVITY OF THE CARDIORESPIRATORY SYSTEM

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Annotation. This article examines a comprehensive approach to the study of age-related characteristics of changes in the activity of external respiration systems, gas exchange and energy metabolism of children and adolescents in the hot climate of Uzbekistan when performing muscle loads of different nature, volume and intensity.

Key words: adaptation, functional system, gas exchange, oxygen, muscular activity, flexibility, mobility.

Темпы изменения размеров тела, функциональных характеристик органов и систем не остаются постоянными на протяжении индивидуального развития организма, а закономерно изменяются(1). Изучение деятельности различных функциональных систем детей и подростков в изменяющихся условиях окружающей среды актуально не только потому, что развивающийся организм ребёнка большой степени подвержен её влиянию, но и потому, что эти воздействия во многом определяют ход его дальнейшего развития. Стрессовые раздражители

внешней среды, в том числе и мышечная работа, изменяют величину и характер приспособительных реакций детского организма.

Продолжают оставаться актуальными широкие и всесторонние исследования возрастных особенностей адаптации организма к условиям, возникающим при выполнении напряжённой мышечной работы, вытеснение путей расширения функциональных возможностей растущего организма и возможного диапазона его тренированности.

Адаптационные возможности организма детей и подростков к воздействиям нескольких жизненно важных систем, действующих по принципу саморегуляции, к числу которых относятся системы газо- и энергетического обмена и дыхания. Дыхание человека связано с физической работоспособностью и отражает общую активность центральной нервной системы, состояние напряжения организма, а максимальный расход воздуха при вдохе и выдохе позволяет косвенно судить о способности дыхательных мышц к интенсивной работе(2). В.И. Сергиевский, Ю.Н. Иванов отличают некоторые особенности внешнего дыхания(3).

Использован комплексный подход в изучении возрастных особенностей изменения деятельности систем внешнего дыхания, газообмене и энергетического обмена детей и подростков в условиях жаркого климата Узбекистана при выполнении различных по характеру, объёму и интенсивности мышечных нагрузок. Интенсивность обмена веществ и энергии связана с возрастом, питанием, мышечной работой и экологическими изменениями во внешней среде(4).

Мы исследовали возрастные особенности физиологического состояния школьников города Куvasая. Регистрированы антропометрические данные, показатели внешнего дыхания и физическая работоспособность у школьников 3-11 класса. Испытуемые были дети проживающих промышленного города Куvasая. Определяли максимальное потребление кислорода, частота дыхания, жизненная ёмкость лёгких и физическая работоспособность с помощью PWC170.

Результаты исследования показали, что частота дыхательных движений у школьников с возрастом уменьшается, ЖЕЛ увеличивается. Максимальное потребление кислорода при выполнении дозированной физической работы у школьников уменьшается после уроков.

Установлено что возрастные изменения показателей энергетического обмена и внешнего дыхания характеризуются последовательным

повышением их абсолютных значений в связи с увеличением длины и массы тела в возрастающей потребности организма в кислороде.

Таблица. Изменение физической работоспособности и максимального потребления кислорода у школьников разного возраста. n=166

ШКОЛЬНИКИ	класс	PWC ₁₇₀ кгм ³ /мин,		МПК мл/мин/кг	
		До уроков	После уроков	До уроков	После уроков
мальчики	11	819	531	48,29	42,36
	8	547	453	57,52	52,60
	3	396	339	69,41	62,15
девочки	11	423	327	35,97	33,98
	8	360	279	48,51	43,72
	3	296	217	65,35	62,48

Данные наших исследований подтвердили мнение о том, что с возрастом и повышением уровня подготовленности происходят закономерные сдвиги в респираторной системе, газообмене и энергетическом обмене, свидетельствующие о повышении их экономичности в условиях относительного покоя и при мышечных напряжениях.

В подростковом возрасте характеризующимся интенсивным развитием мускулатуры и эффективным влиянием на этот процесс физических упражнений, следует рекомендовать постепенное увеличение последних в режиме дня школьников, а также повышение их объёма и интенсивности на уроках физической культуры. Необходимо подчеркнуть, что указанное внедрение физических упражнений в режим дня и повышение двигательной активности должны происходить при обязательном учете возрастно-половых особенностей и уровня подготовленности школьников, а также при систематическом врачебном контроле за состоянием здоровья и степенью воздействия мышечных нагрузок повышенной напряженности.

В ходе исследования выявлены возрастные и половые границы ответных реакций растущего организма на предлагаемые мышечные нагрузки. Установлено направленность изменений этих реакций,

проявляющееся в том, что с возрастом ответные реакции организма детей и подростков на нагрузку одной и той же мощности становятся менее выраженными. Этот факт может расцениваться таким образом, что в процессе роста и развития организма совершенствуются его адаптационные способности и повышаются мобилизационные возможности. Кроме того это свидетельствует о совершенствовании нервно-гуморальной регуляции двигательных и вегетативных реакций как на уровне органов и систем, так и на уровне целостного организма. При этом необходимо подчеркнуть, что мальчики проявляют лучшие адаптационно-мобилизационные способности, выражающиеся в общей и специальной экономизации двигательных актов и меньших энергозатратах на их выполнение. Старший школьный возраст, отличающийся высоким уровнем развития энергообеспечивающих систем, устойчивостью к дефициту кислорода, что следует считать наиболее оптимальным для включения в режим дня продолжительных и достаточно интенсивных физических упражнений. Последнее особенно благоприятно отражается на воспитании выносливости.

Изучение возрастной и сезонной динамики внешнего дыхания и газообмена при выполнении учебно-тренировочных нагрузок повышенных объёмов и интенсивности позволяют отметить гибкость, подвижность и высокую вариативность адаптационных механизмов данных систем организма.

При этом процесс адаптации функциональных систем к интенсивной мышечной деятельности у физически более подготовленных школьников осуществляется не только путём расширения функциональных возможностей организма, но и путём повышения устойчивости его к недостатку кислорода, которая оказалась максимальной у школьников младшего возраста.

Полученный экспериментальный материал убедительно свидетельствует о том, что в онтогенезе определенным образом перестраивается энергообеспечение мышечной деятельности. Было подтверждено мнение И.А. Корниенко о том, что младший школьный возраст при выполнении мышечной работы отличается специфическими функциональными возможностями, проявляющимися высоким уровнем развития систем тканевого окисления и наличием адаптивных механизмов, позволяющим интенсивно снабжать работающие ткани кислородом.

Таким образом, исследование возрастных особенностей энергетического обмена и внешнего дыхания детей и подростков, проживающих в регионе жаркого климата, позволило охарактеризовать организацию метаболических процессов в покое и при мышечной деятельности.

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18. Ўринбоева, М. С., & Расулова, Ш. А. Экологик барқарор тараққиётни

INTERACTIONS OF GABA AND HYPOGLYCEMIC DRUGS***Davranova Aziza Davranovna****Samarkand State Medical University**Assistant of the Department of Endocrinology, Scientific adviser****Shermurodov Shehroz Shermurod****Samarkand State Medical University****Rabbimov Ortiqboy Yaxshiboy o'g'li****Samarkand State Medical University****Nosirova Madinabonu Abdurazzoq qizi****Samarkand State Medical University****Omonova Dilorom****Samarkand State Medical University*

Annotation. *Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a leading cause of premature mortality and disability. Despite a significant number of drugs, the effectiveness of therapy aimed at normalizing glycemic levels and preventing complications does not fully satisfy doctors and patients. Therefore, the search for new approaches for the prevention and treatment of diabetes and its complications continues. Significant resources are used to develop new drugs, but recently the possibility of using “old” widely available drugs with newly discovered pleiotropic properties has been justified. These may include gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) preparations and agents that directly or indirectly activate GABAergic transmission, which have a pronounced pancreoprotective effect, which has been widely discussed in foreign literature in the last 10–15 years. However, there are few such publications in the domestic literature. It has been established that the content of GABA in β -cells in patients with type 1 and type 2 diabetes decreases, and this correlates with the severity of the disease. Genetic suppression of GABA receptors causes a significant decrease in β -cell mass and glucose-stimulated insulin secretion, which confirms the importance of GABA in ensuring glucose homeostasis and the advisability of replenishing GABA deficiency in diabetes with its additional administration. It has been established that in animals with diabetes, GABA suppresses apoptosis and stimulates the regeneration of β -cells, increases β -cell mass and insulin production. Experimental data have been obtained indicating the synergistic effect of GABA when combined with glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) receptor agonists, dipeptidyl peptidase type 4 (DPP-4) inhibitors and sodium-glucose cotransporter 2 (SGLT-2) inhibitors, when a more pronounced pancreoprotective effect is observed, due to a decrease in oxidative and nitrosative stress, inflammation, an increase in the level of Klotho protein, Nrf-2 activity and antioxidant defense enzymes, suppression of NF- κ B activity and the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines. As a result, all this leads to a decrease in apoptosis and death of β -cells, an increase in β -cell mass, insulin production and at the same time a decrease in glucagon levels, insulin resistance.*

Keywords: *GABA; β cells, α cells, diabetes, insulin, enzymes, DPP-4.*

ВЗАИМОДЕЙСТВИЕ ГАМК И ГИПОГЛИКЕМИЧЕСКИХ ПРЕПАРАТОВ*Давранова Азиза Даврановна**Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет
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Аннотация. Сахарный диабет (СД) является ведущей причиной преждевременной смертности и инвалидности. Несмотря на значительное количество препаратов, эффективность терапии, направленной на нормализацию уровня гликемии и предотвращение осложнений, не в полной мере удовлетворяет врачей и пациентов. Поэтому поиск новых подходов к профилактике и лечению сахарного диабета и его осложнений продолжается. На разработку новых лекарств тратятся значительные ресурсы, но в последнее время обоснована возможность использования «старых», широко доступных препаратов с вновь открытыми плейотропными свойствами. К ним можно отнести препараты гамма-аминомасляной кислоты (ГАМК) и средства, прямо или косвенно активирующие ГАМКергическую передачу, обладающие выраженным панкреопротекторным действием, что широко обсуждается в зарубежной литературе в последние 10–15 лет. Однако подобных публикаций в отечественной литературе немного. Установлено, что содержание ГАМК в β -клетках у больных сахарным диабетом 1 и 2 типа снижается, и это коррелирует с тяжестью заболевания. Генетическая супрессия ГАМК-рецепторов вызывает значительное снижение массы β -клеток и глюкозо-стимулируемую секрецию инсулина, что подтверждает значение ГАМК в обеспечении гомеостаза глюкозы и целесообразность восполнения дефицита ГАМК при сахарном диабете с помощью ее дополнительного введения. Установлено, что у животных с сахарным диабетом ГАМК подавляет апоптоз и стимулирует регенерацию β -клеток, увеличивает массу β -клеток и продукцию инсулина. Получены экспериментальные данные, указывающие на синергический эффект ГАМК при сочетании с агонистами рецепторов глюкагоноподобного пептида-1 (ГПП-1), ингибиторами дипептидилпептидазы 4-го типа (ДПП-4) и ингибиторами натрий-глюкозного котранспортера 2 (SGLT-2). , когда наблюдается более выраженный панкреопротекторный эффект за счет снижения окислительного и нитрозативного стресса, воспаления, повышения уровня белка Клото, активности Nrf-2 и ферментов антиоксидантной защиты, подавления активности NF- κ B и экспрессии провоспалительные цитокины. В результате все это приводит к уменьшению апоптоза и гибели β -клеток, увеличению массы β -клеток, выработке инсулина и одновременно снижению уровня глюкагона, инсулинорезистентности.

Ключевые слова: ГАМК; β -клетки, α -клетки, диабет, инсулин, ферменты, ДПП-4.

Introduction. Diabetes mellitus (DM), due to its widespread prevalence and severity of complications, is a major medical, social and economic problem [1]. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the number of patients with diabetes has more than doubled over the past 20 years: according to the register of patients with diabetes, as of January 1, 2021, 4,799,552 (3.23%) patients were registered at the dispensary [2]. According to forecasts of the International Diabetes Association, the number of patients with diabetes will reach 642 million people by 2040 [2]. The use of modern drugs has significantly improved the quality of life of people suffering from diabetes. However, in more than 2/3 of patients it is not possible to achieve target glycemic values, and it is also not always possible to prevent the loss of pancreatic β -cells and numerous complications of diabetes. This encourages the search for new targets and new drugs, the use of combination therapy, and the development of new strategies and new technologies for the treatment of diabetes [1, 3, 4]. Types 1 and 2 diabetes are associated with progressive death of β -cells with the participation of the immune system and inflammation, oxidative and nitrosative stress, glucose and lipotoxicity. One of the areas of treatment for diabetes is the use of drugs that suppress apoptosis and death of β -cells and activate their proliferation and regeneration, increasing insulin production [5–9]. Such properties were noted in incretins, gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), inhibitors of sodium-glucose cotransporter type 2 (NGLT-2), etc., but with monotherapy it is not always possible to achieve normoglycemia, reduce apoptosis and death of β -cells, and enhance their regeneration and increase in β -cell mass, prevent the development of complications of diabetes [9]. In order to increase the effectiveness of antidiabetic therapy for diabetes, a combination of 2 or even 3 hypoglycemic drugs that give a synergistic effect is widely used [4, 10]. In recent years, a number of studies have been published on the synergistic effect of GABA and some hypoglycemic agents of the latest generation, reflecting their effect on glucose homeostasis, the functioning of β -cells, and the formation of additional positive therapeutic effects [9]. In this review, we present data demonstrating the synergistic interaction of GABA and drugs with GABAergic action in combination with drugs that have an incretin-like effect: glucagon-like peptide 1 receptor agonists (GLP-1R), dipeptidyl peptidase 4 (DPP-4) inhibitors and NGLT- 2, having previously considered their class-specific properties, including pleiotropic ones. The search was carried out in the Pubmed, eLibrary, Medline databases using the keywords: diabetes mellitus, gamma-aminobutyric acid, glucagon-like peptide-1, GLP-1R agonists, glucose-dependent insulinotropic peptide (GIP), dipeptidyl peptidase

inhibitors, sodium-glucose cotransporter 2 inhibitors. The search was carried out over the period from 2021 to 2023, but the review presents the results of studies published mainly over the last 3 years, which is due to the journal's requirements for the maximum volume of work and the number of sources.

Role of gaba in the regulation of carbohydrate metabolism. Since the discovery of GABA and its inhibitory properties in the brain (BM), much of our understanding of its physiological role has changed significantly. It was found that GABA is detected in almost all tissues and organs. In pancreatic tissues, the GABA content is comparable to that in the GM and is highly expressed in α - and β -cells of the islets of Langerhans [6, 11]. The GABA content in β -cells in patients with type 1 and type 2 diabetes decreases, and insulin secretion is impaired [12, 13]. This supports the contention that loss of GABA correlates with the pathogenesis of diabetes [8]. In the pancreatic islets, insulin-producing β -cells express GABAA and GABA B receptors, which are encoded by different intracellular pathways and form different signal transduction mechanisms [6, 12, 14, 15]. Once released, GABA influences the activity of α - and β -cells of the pancreas through ionotropic GABAA receptors and metabotropic GABAB receptors. The effect of GABA on α - and β -cells differs; on the former it has an inhibitory effect, reducing the production and release of glucagon, on β -cells it has a stimulating effect, increasing insulin secretion [15]. GABA in pancreatic β -cells through GABA A receptors activates calcium-dependent signaling pathways and voltage-dependent channels, triggers the PI3K/Akt, CREB-IRS-2 and SIRT-1 signaling cascades, which may be decisive in the regulation of mass and functions β -cells [11, 15]. Obesity plays a key role in the development of insulin resistance, diabetes and its complications [16, 17]. Therefore, reducing insulin resistance is an independent task for the prevention and treatment of diabetes. GABA has therapeutic potential against obesity, which is associated with the suppression of oxidative stress and endoplasmic reticulum (ER) stress. GABA reduced the expression of the adipogenic transcription factor PPAR- γ in the adipose tissue and liver of mice fed a fat-rich, high-calorie diet. GABA controls the activity of NADPH oxidase (NOX4) during dysmetabolism associated with high-fat and carbohydrate-rich foods, causing the breakdown of IRE-1a, which sulfonates RIDD-SIRT. Administration of GABA significantly increased AMPK and SIRT-1 levels in obese mice [17], decreased insulin resistance, increased liver glycogen levels, improved lipid profile, and decreased glucose and glycated hemoglobin levels [18, 19]. GABA significantly reduced insulin resistance by activating the expression of the glucose transporter gene (GLUT-4), suppressing

the gluconeogenesis pathway in the liver, reducing the expression of the FOXO1 and Pepck genes, and simultaneously increasing the expression of the IRS-2 and Akt2 genes [18]. GABA stimulates phosphorylation of CREB through cAMP element binding protein (AMPK), known as a key transcription factor responsible for insulin gene maintenance and β -cell survival, thereby promoting increased β -cell mass. The trophic effects of GABA are formed through the activation of the Akt and CREB signaling pathways independently of each other, but activation of both pathways is required for an optimal response. The involvement of Ca²⁺ and CREB and their glucose-dependent activation of β -cell IRS-2 is important for the plasticity of the β -cell response to increased insulin demand. GABA-induced activation of CREB is simultaneously associated with increased levels of IRS-2 transcript expression [6, 15, 20]. The role of the GABAergic system in the regulation of carbohydrate metabolism is also confirmed by the fact that genetic suppression of GABA receptors significantly reduced the mass of β -cells and glucose-stimulated insulin secretion, which led to disruption of glucose homeostasis [8, 9].

Conclusion. The development of innovative drugs requires significant resources. An alternative to this could be the identification of new targets for already known drugs, which open up other indications and prospects for their use in complex therapy. These may include GABA and drugs with GABAergic action, which, judging by many publications, can improve the functional state of β -cells, reduce oxidative stress and inflammation. Currently, data have accumulated on the synergistic effect of GABA when combined with GLP-1R agonists, DPP-4 inhibitors and SGLT-2 inhibitors with increased pancreatic protective action, which is due to a decrease in oxidative stress and inflammation, an increase in the level of Klotho protein, Nrf-2 activity and antioxidant defense enzymes, suppression of NF- κ B activity and the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines. This led to a decrease in β -cell death, an increase in β -cell mass, insulin production, and at the same time a decrease in insulin resistance.

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MA'NAVIY MADANIYAT JAMIYAT BARQARORLIGI OMILI

Rasulova Shaira Azizovna

O'zbekiston davlat jismoniy tarbiya va sport universiteti Farg'ona filiali katta o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada jamiyatning barqaror rivojlanishida ijtimoiy ong sakllari bo'lmish ma'naviy madaniyat tushunchasi va uni insonlar tomonidan boyitib borilishi xaqidagi dunyo olimlarining fikrlari yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: jamiyat, barqarorlik, madaniy jarayonlar, ma'naviyat, ijtimoiy ong, sinergetik, gnosyologik tahlil.

SPIRITUAL CULTURE SOCIETY STABILITY FACTOR

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Abstract. This article covers the opinions of world scientists about the concept of spiritual culture, which is a source of social consciousness in the sustainable development of society, and its enrichment by people.

Key words: society, stability, cultural processes, spirituality, social consciousness, synergistic, epistemological analysis.

Kirish. XXI asrga kelib ma'naviyat butun insoniyat uchun dolzarb ma'naviy ozuqaga aylanib ketdiki, natijada usiz har qanday qudratli jamiyat yoki davlat tanazzulga yo'l tutishi aniq bo'lib qoldi. Prezidentimiz Sh. M. Mirziyoyev alohida ta'kidlaganidek, bugungi kunga kelib xalqimiz va yurtimizning istiqbolini belgilashda, "...insoniyat dunyosining buyuk bir yoritgichi – ma'naviyat chirog'i bor. Bu chiroqning boshqalardan farqi shuki, u insonning ongi va tafakkurini yoritadi, qalbi, vijdonini uyg'otadi, odamiylik hissini kuchaytiradi.

O'zbekistonning yangi uyg'onish davrini yaratishga kirishar ekanmiz, har bir yurtdoshimizning qalbi va ongida ana shunday ma'naviyat shu'lasini porlashi va u bizni ezgu ishlarga undab, yuksak mas'uliyat tuyg'usi bilan yashashga da'vat etishi zarur".

Shunday ekan, har bir inson hamda kamol topib kelayotgan yosh avlod uchun ma'naviyat suv bilan havodek naqadar zarurligini unutmashimiz

darkor.Ma'lumki, masala va muammoning mohiyatini anglab yetish chog'ida uning mazmunini ochib berish maqsadida ishlatiladigan tushuncha va kategoriyalarning mazmun-mohiyatiga e'tibor qaratish juda muhim sanaladi. Shu ma'noda ma'naviyat va madaniyat tushunchalari ham alohida ilmiy tahlillarga muhtoj bo'lib, ayrim tadqiqotchilar tomonidan muayyan ko'lamda talqin etilgan.

Ma'naviyat tushunchasining ma'no-mazmuni haqida fikr yuritganda uning jamiyatda tutgan rolini teran anglamasdan turib ma'naviy madaniyat haqida so'z yuritib bo'lmaydi. Chunki ma'naviy madaniyat ma'naviyatning real hodisa sifatida yuzaga chiqishi, uning voqeiy bo'lish jarayonining yuzaga kelishidan iborat. Nazariy ongning bir qismi bo'lgan ma'naviy madaniyatning shakllari amaliyot bilan bog'liq. Voqelikka nisbatan yoshlar ongida ham ma'naviy madaniyatning elementlari shakllanib, milliylik bilan bog'liq ravishda ijtimoiy ong rivojlanadi.

Ma'naviyat asosiy tushunchalar izohli lug'atida "ma'naviyat – inson ruhiy va aqliy olamini ifodalovchi tushuncha" sifatida keltirilgan bo'lsa, O'zbekiston milliy entsiklopediyasida esa, "ma'naviyat – kishilarning falsafiy, huquqiy, ilmiy, badiiy, ahloqiy, diniy tasavvurlarini o'z ichiga oladi", deyilgan. Har bir ta'rifning funktsionallik va individuallik jihatlari mavjud bo'lib, inson vujudining ma'nosi, manfaatlar to'qnashuviga moyilligi, uning benazir va mukammal mavjudotligini ifodalaydi.

Birinchi Prezidentimiz Islom Karimov esa "Yuksak ma'naviyat – yengilmas kuch" asarida ushbu tushunchaga bergan o'zining quyidagicha mashhur ta'rifida: "Ma'naviyat – insonni ruhiy poklanish, qalban ulg'ayishga chorlaydigan, odamning ichki dunyosi, irodasini baquvvat, iymon-e'tiqodini butun qiladigan, vijdonini uyg'otadigan beqiyos kuch, uning barcha qarashlari mezonidir", deb ta'kidlaydi. Mazkur ta'rifning o'ziga xos tomoni shundaki, unda ma'naviyat insonning diniy va dunyoviy hayot bilan bog'liq ko'rinishlarning ifodasi sifatida falsafiy tarzda mohiyatini ilmiy muomalaga kiritishga yo'naltirilgan.

Ma'naviyat bilan madaniyatni tahlil etish chog'ida ular o'rtasidagi dialektik aloqadorlik, sinergetik tamoyillar mavjudligini ko'ra bilish juda muhim. Ma'lumki, ma'naviyat ham, madaniyat ham hech kimda tug'ma bo'lmaydi, instinktlar orqali tabiatan berilmaydi. U shaxsning jamiyatda ijtimoiylashuvi negizida ahloq, did, idrok, his-tuyg'ularning ta'siri ostida shakllanadi va, shunday deyish joiz bo'lsa, ongsizlikdan onglilik, anglanganlik tomon ulg'ayishida vujudga keladi. Har bir voyaga yetib kelayotgan yigit-qiz shaxsiy hayotiy tajribasi asosida, mustaqil ravishda bevosita tevarak-atrofdagi kishilarning, jamiyatning va

o‘t ‘gan ajdodlarning to‘plagan tajribalarini o‘zlashtiradi. Yoshlar ham ijtimoiy amaliyot mahsuli bo‘lgan madaniyatni o‘zlashtirish bilan birga, unga o‘z ta‘sirini o‘tkazadi. Yoshlar ijtimoiy ongining shakllanishi jarayonida moddiy va ma‘naviy madaniyatni boyita boradi.

Tadqiqot metodologiyasi. Tadqiqotning uslubiy asosini ilmiy bilishning ob‘ektivlik (xolislik), tarixiylik, sistemalilik, retrospektiv va qiyosiy tahlil usullari tashkil etadi.

Tahlil va natijalar. Fanda madaniyatga berilgan ta‘riflar ham juda ko‘p. Masalan, akademik E.Yusupovning fikricha, “madaniyat – bu kishilar faoliyatining jamiyat iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy-siyosiy va ma‘naviy hayot sohasida yaratgan, o‘zlarining ehtiyojlarini qondirish uchun ishlab chiqargan boyliklar tizimidir” . Ko‘rinib turibdiki, akademik olimimiz bergan bu ta‘rifda madaniyat asosan insonning yashash tarzi bilan bog‘liq madaniy faoliyatni o‘z ichiga olganligiga asosiy urg‘u berilgan.

Falsafa bo‘yicha qomusiy lug‘atda “madaniyat (so‘zning o‘zagi arabcha madina, ya‘ni shahar ma‘nosidan kelib chiqqan holda – madinalik, shaharlik, ta‘lim-tarbiya ko‘rganlik) – tabiat va o‘zaro munosabatlarda aks etadigan inson faoliyatining o‘ziga xos usuli” , - deb talqin etilgan. Bunda madaniyatning insonning tabiat bilan munosabatlarning uyg‘unlashuviga e‘tibor qaratilgan.

Madaniyatga ta‘rif bergan olimlar orasida turli soha xodimlari, jumladan, siyosatdonlarni ham ko‘rishimiz mumkin. Jumladan, G.V. Plexanov tomonidan, “madaniyat inson va jamiyat yaratgan moddiy va ma‘naviy boyliklar (qadriyatlar) yig‘indisi ekanligi ta‘kidlanadi” . Ko‘rinib turibdiki, uning ta‘rifida madaniyat bevosita inson faoliyati bilan bog‘liq ijtimoiy munosabatlarning mahsuli sifatida olib qaralgan va o‘z-o‘zidan ravshanki, unda marksizm falsafasining tarixni materialistik tushunish nazariyasining ta‘siri ko‘zga yaqqol tashlanib turibdi.

Madaniyat, mohiyatan, shaxs va jamiyat o‘rtasidagi bog‘liqlik bo‘lib, birinchi marta adabiyotda “madaniyat” so‘zi nazariy atama sifatida “Toskulian suhbatlari”da (mil. av. 45 y) qadimgi Rimning mashhur notig‘i va faylasufi, tarixchi Mark Tuliy Sitseron tomonidan qo‘llanilganligini alohida ta‘kidlash o‘rinlidir. Bu o‘rinda shuni ham ta‘kidlash lozimki, o‘sha paytda bu atama adabiyotda qishloq xo‘jaligi atamasi (qayta ishlash) vazifasini bajargan. Chunki dastlab madaniyatni majoziy ma‘noda tabiat va jamiyat hodisalarining inson ongiga ta‘siriga nisbatan, keyin esa inson ongi mahsuli va asosida yaratilgan falsafiy an‘analarning davomi sifatida ishlatishgan. Shuning uchun Suqrot ham madaniyatni falsafiy tarzda ifodalab, falsafaning inson hayotiga ta‘siri usullari tizimida «madaniyat aql – falsafa» degan tezisni maydonga olib chiqqan edi. Bu

esa madaniyatning falsafiy bilim ekanligiga qaratilgan ilmiy qarash ekanligini ta'kidlash borasidagi birinchi urinishlar edi. Shu vaqtdan boshlab ushbu so'zning ma'naviy jihati tarixiylik mazmuniga ega bo'lib, ijtimoiy jarayonga xos ma'no kasb eta boshladi.

XVII asrda kelib madaniyat inson tomonidan amalga oshiriladigan munosabatlarning ijobiy va salbiy natijasi, shaxsning tashqi va ichki mohiyatini ifodalovchi tushuncha sifatida keng qo'llanila boshlandi. Bu ham, tabiiyki o'z davriga xos ilm-fan va ijtimoiy ishlab chiqarish yutuqlarining ifodasi tarzida aks etgan mazmun va mohiyatdan iborat bo'lganligi bilan e'tiborga loyiq.

XIX asrda esa ko'plab madaniyatshunoslar yetishib chiqa boshlaganligi ko'zga yaqqol tashlanadi. Ayniqsa, Yevropada ilmiy-falsafiy tafakkur rivoj topganligi fan tarixida alohida sahifa ochdi va bu holat madaniyat kategoriyasini tushunishga nisbatan yondashuvlarda ham o'z aksini topmasdan qolmadi, deyishimiz mumkin. Rus olimasi E.A.Orlova aytganidek, "shu davrdan boshlab "madaniyat" tushunchasi "sivilizatsiya", "ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy formatsiya", global mintaqalashtirish" kategoriyalari bilan kesishadigan bo'ldi" [8].

XX asrda Yevropa madaniyatshunosligida T. Parsons madaniyatni ijtimoiy harakatni tahlil qilish sifatida, K. Levi-Strauss esa o'z asarlarida tabiiy jarayonlarga qarshi bo'lgan hodisalarning tanlangan maydoni, deb qaraydi. XX asrning ikkichi yarmidan boshlab bu tushunchaga ko'plab rus faylasuflari, jumladan, N. Berdyayev, V. Ivanov, L. Shestov, V. Rozanovlar yuqori madaniyatni anglash sohasidagi ko'plab qimmatli g'oya va ilmiy tasavvurlarni olib kirishdi.

Madaniyatning mohiyatini tushunishda rus faylasuflaridan biri V.S.Biblerning fikri, o'ylaymizki, o'ziga xosligi bilan e'tiborga molik. Uning fikricha:

- madaniyat insonga xos bo'lib, bir vaqtda borliqda mavjud bo'lishligi va odamlar uchun hamkorlik aloqasi shaklida namoyon bo'ladi;
- madaniyat – inson o'z mohiyati va shaxsiyatini aqliy anglab yetishi, ijtimoiy hayotda o'rnatilgan qoidalarga so'zsiz amal qilish holatidir. Madaniyat - bu o'z taqdiriga nisbatan erkin qaror qabul qilish va qayta belgilash, uning tarixiy va umumbashariy javobgarligini anglash shaklidir;
- madaniyat dunyoning birinchi ixtirosi.

Bunda V.S.Bibler madaniyatning bu uchta ko'rinishiga xos turli belgilarni o'z ichiga olgan noyob va universalligini emas, balki, madaniyatning alohida bo'limlarga ajratilishidir, deb ta'kidlaydi.

Bizning atrofimizdagi dunyoda mavjud bo'lgan ma'naviy madaniyatni ongli ravishda anglab yetish voqelik ikkilamchi tabiatga o'tishini shaxs

madaniyati sifatida qabul qilishi natijasida obyektivlikdan subyektivlikka erishiladi. Mazkur madaniyat inson uchun ijtimoiy va tarixiy tajriba, dasturlarni to'plash asosida ijtimoiy ehtiyojlarga asoslangan faoliyat va harakatni oldinga yo'naltiradi. Borliqni inson ongida aks etishi, shu asosda o'z ijod mahsulini yaratishi natijasida ma'naviy madaniyat paydo bo'ladi.

Ma'naviy madaniyat, aslida, kishilik jamiyati tarixida asrlar davomida shakllangan inson tafakkurining mahsuli bo'lib, unda insonning voqelikka stixiyali tarzda yondashuvi asosida ma'naviy dunyoqarash vujudga kelgan. Astasekinlik bilan tevarak-atrofdagi narsa va hodisalarga aqliy munosabatning rivojlanishi negizida ma'naviy madaniyat unsurlari ijobiy va foydali ahamiyat kasb etgan va shuning uchun avloddan-avlodga meros sifatida qoldirish uchun zarur deb topilgan. Bu esa, o'z navbatida insonning aql-zakovatida yangicha tafakkur tarzi shakllanishi bilan birga, borliqning narsa va predmetlari, hayvonot olami, koinot, megaolam va umuman dunyo to'g'risidagi qarashlarining kengayishiga olib kelgan.

Ma'naviy ishlab chiqarish jarayonida siyosiy va huquqiy mafkura, falsafa, ahloq, san'at sohasidagi erishilgan yutuqlar saralanib boradi. Ular ma'naviy boyliklarni yaratuvchi shaxslar tomonidan qayta ishlanib, sayqallanadi va odamlarning ehtiyojlarini qondirish tomonga yo'naltiriladi. Shu boisdan "ma'naviy madaniyat – insonning ma'naviy xususiyat va xislatlari, jamiyatning madaniy darajasini aks ettiruvchi tushuncha" sifatida olib qaraladi. Unda insonning oddiy yashashi bilan bog'liq kundalik turmushning muhim ehtiyojlari tizimi jamiyat bilan bog'liq holda ifodalangan.

S.Otamurodov fikriga ko'ra esa, "ma'naviy madaniyat voqelikni badiiy aks ettirish va o'zlashtirish vositasidir". Bunda voqelikda inson mehnati natijasida yaratiladigan moddiy va ma'naviy boyliklar, shaxs ma'naviy qiyofasining yuksalishiga xizmat qiladigan ahloq qoidalariga rioya etish masalalari aks etgan.

Biroq, ushbu o'rinda ta'kidlash lozimki, bizningcha, S. Otamurodovning bu fikri muhokama etilayotgan masala yuzasidan mutlaq haqiqat darajasi uchun da'vogarlik qila olmaydi. Chunki ma'naviy madaniyat voqelikni badiiy aks ettirish tushunchasidan ancha kengroq tushuncha. Binobarin, olimning badiiy aks ettirish jihatini mutlaqlashtiradigan bo'lsak, siyosiy, ilmiy, huquqiy aks ettirish kabi jihatlari ushbu yondashuv doirasiga sig'may qolishi tabiiydir. Shunday ekan, ma'naviy madaniyatni voqelikni badiiy aks ettirishga tenglashtirish asossiz, balki voqelikni badiiy aks ettirishni ma'naviy madaniyatni shakllantirish vositalaridan biri deyish to'g'riroq bo'ladi.

Ilohiyot nazariyasi nuqtai nazaridan yondashuvda insonning ma'naviy borlig'i uchun najot bilan muloqot orqali sodir bo'ladigan ilohiy inoyat, insonning ichki o'zgarishi va iymon orqali uning qadriyatlari va ma'naviy (ilohiy) ga bo'lgan munosabatining o'zgarishlari tushuniladi. Taniqli rus faylasufi I. Ilin bu to'g'rida shunday deb yozadi: "barcha ma'naviy madaniyatning asosiy manbai - bu bizga berilgan Ilohiylik. Xudo tomonidan beriladigan yaxshi va jonli narsalarda sevgi va iymon mavjud va uni e'zozlaymiz". Bu fikrlardan har bir dinda xudoga sig'inish ilohiylik kasb etishini ko'rishimiz mumkin va o'zimizning unga e'tiqodimiz orqali o'zligimiz, ichki hissiyotlarimizni bag'ishlaymiz.

Xulosa. Ma'naviy madaniyatga ta'sir qiluvchi omillardan biri jamiyatning ma'naviy yangilanishi jarayonida odamlar ma'naviyatni shakllantirishda muhim rol o'ynaydigan turli aloqalar, yangi avlodlarning o'z rivojlanishida yangi qadriyatlar to'plashi, bilim, g'oyalar, tajriba orttirishi bilan bog'liqligidir. Shu bilan birga kundalik an'analar bilan bog'liq diniy hamda dunyoviy tafakkur ham ana shu omillardan biri sanaladi. Diniy tafakkurda inson ma'naviy ongiga ta'sir qiladigan ilohiy hodisalar va jarayonlar asosiy o'rin egallaydi. Bunda ma'naviy madaniyatning rivojlanish jarayoni jamiyatning taraqqiyot yo'nalishini belgilaydigan ko'rsatkich vazifasini bajaradi.

Ma'naviyat subyektning barqaror holati darajasida to'liq namoyon bo'lib, ma'naviy madaniyatning yuqori darajasiga aylanadi. Ushbu jarayonning mohiyatini sharqning buyuk allomasi Abu Nasr Forobiy juda chiroyli va mantiqiy ta'riflaganligini keltirish juda o'rinli bo'ladi: "Bu esa tabiiy hayot ruhining yo'g'on tomirlar vositasi bilan qalbdan a'zolarga yuborilishi bilan bajo keladi", deb yozgan edi alloma.

Jamiyatda ma'naviy madaniyatni rivojlantirish uchun milliylikni saqlash bilan birga, undan yiroqlashish, insoniyat tarixiga chuqur kirib borish ham maqsadga muvofiq hisoblanadi. Shu tarzda yoshlar kamolotiga xizmat qiladigan ijtimoiy-falsafiy tafakkurni shakllantirish, jamiyatda ajdodlar yaratib qoldirgan moddiy va ma'naviy merosning naqadar buyuk xazina ekanligini anglab yetish mumkin bo'ladi. Har bir yosh avlod ongli ravishda o'zining ma'naviy-mafkuraviy olamini milliy va umuminsoniylik uyg'unligida kamol toptirishi ertangi kun uchun bevosita ma'naviy boylikka aylanadi. Ijtimoiy hayotda moddiylik va ma'naviylikning uyg'unligi va o'zaro ta'siri natijasida aqlan yetuk, ahloqan barkamol, jismonan sog'lom, e'tiqodi butun inson tarbiya topadi. Inson o'zining teran fikri, rang-barang qarashlari, boy tushuncha va tasavvurlari va g'oyalar dunyosi yordamida turlicha madaniyatlarni biri-biridan farqlab boradi.

Takliflar. Har bir xalq uchun ma'naviy madaniyatning o'ziga xos boshqa xalqlardan farqlanadigan jihatlari mavjud bo'lib, undan foydalanishda ijobiy tomonlarni olishi . Xalqimizning buyuk allomalari Forobiy, Beruniy, Ibn Sino, Navoiy, Bobur va boshqalarning asarlarida turli xalqlar madaniyatlarining o'zaro aloqasi va bir-biriga o'zaro ta'siri keng yoritilgan ulardan unumli foydalanish. Mutafakkirlarning asarlari bugungi kunda ko'plab tillarda tarjima qilinib, boshqa xalqlarning manfaatlari bilan mos bo'lganligi bois ularning ma'naviy boyliklari qatoridan ham mustahkam joy olish.

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THE MODERN METHODS OF TREATMENT OF DIABETIC NEPHROPATHY

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Abstract: *Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a disease that accompanies a person for a long period of time. The greatest danger of diabetes is undoubtedly associated with complications that develop due to its damaging effects on blood vessels, particularly diabetic nephropathy (DN), which develops in approximately 20.1% of patients with diabetes of the 1st type and 6.3% of patients with diabetes of the 2nd type. In patients with diabetes of the 2nd type, diabetic nephropathy ranks third among causes of death after diseases of the cardiovascular system and oncological pathologies. There are many mechanisms of damaging effects of various factors that play a key role in the development of renal pathology in diabetes. We focused on a more detailed examination of the effect of renin-angiotensin-aldosterone (RAAS), direct damaging effects of hyperglycemia, polyol glucose metabolism, and hyperlipidemia, endothelial growth factor (VEGF) and transforming growth factor β (TGF- β). Based on the knowledge of the pathogenesis of diabetic nephropathy, very promising targets have been identified for the correction of this pathology.*

Key words: *diabetic nephropathy, hyperglycemia, diabetic kidney disease.*

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ДИАБЕТИЧЕСКОЙ НЕФРОПАТИИ.

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Аннотация: Сахарный диабет (СД) – заболевание, сопровождающее человека в течение длительного периода времени. Наибольшую опасность СД, несомненно, связаны с осложнениями, развивающимися вследствие его повреждающего воздействия на сосуды, в частности с диабетической нефропатией (ДН), которая развивается примерно у 20,1% больных СД 1-го типа и у 6,3% больных СД 1-го типа и 6,3% больных СД 1-го типа. 2-й тип. У больных сахарным диабетом 2-го типа диабетическая нефропатия занимает третье место среди причин смерти после заболеваний сердечно-сосудистой системы и онкологических патологий. Существует множество механизмов повреждающего действия различных факторов, играющих ключевую роль в развитии патологии почек при сахарном диабете. Мы сосредоточились на более детальном изучении влияния ренин-ангиотензин-альдостерона (РААС), прямых повреждающих эффектов гипергликемии, метаболизма полиоловой глюкозы и гиперлипидемии, эндотелиального фактора роста (VEGF) и трансформирующего фактора роста β (TGF- β). На основании знаний о патогенезе диабетической нефропатии определены весьма перспективные цели коррекции этой патологии.

Ключевые слова: диабетическая нефропатия, гипергликемия, диабетическая болезнь почек.

Effects on biochemical and structural changes in renal membranes. At present, the search is underway for promising drugs that can affect the structure and biochemical composition of the basement membranes of the renal glomeruli. One of such drugs, which has already passed experimental and clinical trials, is sulodexide (Alfa Wassermann, Italy), which is a low-molecular-weight heparin. This drug, without affecting the blood coagulation system, is able to increase the content of heparan sulfate in the glomerular membranes, restore the selective permeability of the renal filter and prevent the development of sclerotic processes in the kidney tissue. We tested this drug in 18 patients with insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (9 people with microalbuminuria and 9 people with proteinuria). The drug was administered intramuscularly once a day, 5 days a week (with a 2-day break) for 3 weeks. In 89% of patients, a significant antiproteinuric effect was noted, reaching its maximum by the end of the treatment period, and protein excretion in the urine decreased in patients with both microalbuminuria and proteinuria. This effect persisted for the next 6 weeks after discontinuation of treatment, although there was some tendency to re-increase albuminuria. In addition, the antiatherogenic effect of sulodexide was noted: the atherogenic coefficient of serum decreased. When assessing the condition of the fundus of the eye in patients treated with sulodexide, a positive trend was revealed in the non-proliferative and preproliferative stages of diabetic retinopathy and stabilization of the process in the proliferative stage of retinopathy. Thus, this drug had a beneficial effect not only on the course of DN, but also on the wall of retinal vessels. Another inevitable consequence of hyperglycemia is non-enzymatic glycosylation of the structural proteins of the glomerular basement membrane, which also leads to disruption of their configuration and loss of normal selective permeability to proteins. To interrupt the non-enzyme glycosylation reaction, the drug aminoguanidine is successfully used in the experiment, which irreversibly reacts with glycosylation products, thereby stopping this process. However, no clinical trials of this drug have been conducted to date. Increased glucose metabolism along the polyol pathway under the influence of the enzyme aldose reduction leads to the accumulation of sorbitol (osmotically active substance) in insulin-independent tissues, also contributing to the development of late complications of diabetes mellitus. To interrupt this process, the clinic uses drugs from the group of aldose reductase inhibitors (tolrestat, statil). A number of studies have demonstrated a decrease in albuminuria in patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus receiving aldose reductase inhibitors. However, the clinical efficacy of these drugs is more pronounced in the treatment of diabetic neuropathy

or retinopathy and less so in the treatment of DN. This may be due to the fact that the polyol pathway of glucose metabolism plays a smaller role in the pathogenesis of diabetic kidney damage than the vessels of other non-insulin-dependent tissues.

Effects on vasoactive factors of vascular endothelium and platelets. The vascular endothelium and platelets are the cells most sensitive to the effects of high glucose concentrations. Endothelial cell dysfunction consists in the overproduction of biologically active substances involved in the processes of intravascular coagulation and regulation of vascular tone (endothelin-1, endothelial relaxation factor, prostacyclin). Platelet dysfunction in uncompensated diabetes mellitus is manifested by high production of coagulation factors, as well as excessive release of thromboxane A₂ (TCA₂), which causes vasospasm and platelet hyperaggregation. All of these endothelial and platelet factors, causing spasm and thrombotic occlusion of blood vessels, contribute to the development and progression of both micro- and macroangiopathies in diabetes mellitus. Therefore, drug correction of the activity of these factors could help prevent the rapid progression of late vascular complications of diabetes mellitus. Medications that correct the synthesis of vasoactive endothelial factors (endothelin-1 and endothelial relaxation factor) are at the stage of experimental development and in the future have a real chance to take a leading place in the treatment of diabetic angiopathies. At the same time, drugs that affect the prostacyclin-thromboxane system have already been developed and are widely used in nephrological practice for the treatment of chronic renal diseases. In the practice of diabetologists, these drugs have not yet been widely used, although their use for the treatment of diabetic angiopathies (and, above all, DN) is pathogenetically justified. For example, TCA₂ not only causes vasospasm and platelet hyperaggregation, but also has a direct damaging effect on the structure and function of the kidneys, provoking the development of proteinuria and accelerating the process of sclerosing of renal tissue. In this regard, it seemed expedient to investigate the effect of a drug that blocks excess production of TCA₂ on renal function in patients with DN. For this purpose, we used ibustrin (Pharmacia, Switzerland), which is an inhibitor of the enzyme cyclooxygenase, which is involved in the formation of TCA₂ from arachidonic acid. Treatment was provided to 16 patients with insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus with proteinuric stage DN (proteinuria did not exceed 1 g/day). All patients also had different stages of diabetic retinopathy and impaired blood supply to the lower extremities, diagnosed by Doppler sonography of the arteries of the feet. Ibustrin was prescribed 1 tablet 2 times a day (400 mg/day) for 3 months. At the end of the course of treatment, there was an improvement in renal function: glomerular

filtration rate increased in 13 (81%) patients, daily proteinuria decreased in 12 (75%) patients. The efficacy of treatment against retinopathy directly depended on the stage of pathological changes in the fundus vessels: among patients with the non-proliferative stage of retinopathy, improvement was noted in 83%, in the presence of the preproliferative stage — in 40% of patients, but in patients with the proliferative stage there was practically no positive dynamics. Increased blood flow in the lower extremities during treatment with ibustrin was observed in 62% of patients. Such a high efficacy of ibustrin in the treatment of vascular complications of diabetes mellitus, found in our study, can be explained by the timely initiation of the use of this drug, i.e., at relatively early stages of the development of angiopathies (in proteinuria not exceeding 1 g/day; in the non-proliferative or preproliferative stage of retinopathy; in the initial decrease in blood flow in the lower extremities). In the later stages of vascular complications, the efficacy of the drug would appear to be minimal. Thus, in our study. The assumption of the efficacy of the use of drugs blocking the synthesis of TCA2 in the complex treatment of diabetic angiopathies, especially when prescribed at the early stages of vascular complications, has been confirmed.

Purpose: to study common complications and preventive measures for diabetes mellitus in people of different ages.

Materials and methods: studying complications of the disease, data were collected from patients Endocrinological center for Samarkand the years. The data of 30 patients were studied, of which 14 were men and 16 women.

Study results: The most common complication among patients was diabetic nephropathy in 15 patients. According to the results of the study, untimely treatment of diabetic nephropathy leads to chronic renal failure. The initial signs of nephropathy were an increased amount of urination, frequent increases in blood pressure, swelling, and deterioration in health. Instrumental laboratory tests showed an increase in creatinine. Of the 15 patients with diabetic nephropathy, 5 patients are over 47 years old, 7 patients are from 30 to 45 years old and 2 patients are from 25 to 30 years old. Treatment began with a conservative method; in 4 patients, conservative treatment did not show results and hemodialysis was prescribed.

Conclusion. Summarizing all of the above, we can conclude that the pathogenesis of the development of DN is quite complex and has a number of its own features. This problem has spread all over the world and has not lost its relevance today. Treatment of the last stage of DN is not only a complex process, but also, due to some economic aspects, very expensive. It's much easier to do prevention of vascular complications and try to prevent the disease from progressing to end-stage renal failure, how to treat patients with chronic renal

failure using hemodialysis. Therefore, despite detailed study existing problem, question of correction nephropathy remains open to this day.

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STRUCTURE OF THE CAUSES OF INFERTILITY IN MEN AND WOMEN IN SAMARKAND AND SAMARKAND REGION

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Annotation. *The structure of the causes of infertility was studied in 100 couples (200 people) suffering from infertility in the city of Samarkandey, Samarkand region (50 families each). It was found that in the examined women, the main place in the genesis of infertility is occupied by hormonal dysfunction (diffuse goiter with subclinical hypothyroidism, ovarian failure with menstrual dysfunction, polycystic ovary syndrome, hyperandrogenism, luteal phase deficiency, impaired folliculogenesis), as well as inflammatory diseases of the genitourinary system (TORCH -infections). In the examined men, the main role in the genesis of infertility is occupied by hormonal dysfunction (androgen deficiency associated with excess body weight, impaired spermatogenesis, hypergonadotropic and hypogonadotropic hypogonadism).*

Keywords: *reproductive health, infertility, male and female hypogonadism.*

СТРУКТУРА ПРИЧИН БЕСПЛОДИЯ У МУЖЧИН И ЖЕНЩИН САМАРКАНДА И САМАРКАНДСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ

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***Аннотация.** Структура причин бесплодия изучена у 100 пар (200 человек), страдающих бесплодием в городе Самарканде Самаркандской области (по 50 семей). Установлено, что у обследованных женщин основное место в генезе бесплодия занимают гормональные дисфункции (диффузный зоб при субклиническом гипотиреозе, овариальная недостаточность с нарушением менструальной функции, синдром поликистозных яичников, гиперандрогения, недостаточность лютеиновой фазы, нарушение фолликулогенеза), а также а также воспалительные заболевания мочеполовой системы (TORCH-инфекции). У обследованных мужчин основную роль в генезе бесплодия играют гормональные дисфункции (андрогенная недостаточность, связанная с избыточной массой тела, нарушением сперматогенеза, гипергонадотропным и гипогонадотропным гипогонадизмом).*

***Ключевые слова:** репродуктивное здоровье, бесплодие, мужской и женский гипогонадизм.*

Introduction. The problem of infertility in marriage, despite significant advances in diagnosis and treatment, remains the most pressing medical and social problem of our time [3–10]. According to WHO (1993), with an infertility rate of 15% and above, its impact on demographic indicators significantly exceeds the total impact of miscarriage and perinatal losses, and therefore this problem has not only medical and biological, but also important social significance [8, 11]. In this regard, WHO has developed a special research program on human reproduction, the main directions of which are studying the frequency and causes of infertility, standardizing the examination of infertile couples [11]. According to WHO estimates, in Uzbekistan the frequency of infertile marriages significantly exceeds the critical level and is becoming a national problem. Despite the urgency of the problem, there is no unified methodology for identifying and examining infertile couples [1, 2]. In addition, a number of medical and social aspects of this problem have not yet become the subject of scientific analysis. The problem of individual prediction of the risk of female infertility has not been solved. Despite a significant number of publications devoted to various issues of infertility, insufficient attention is paid to the prevention of this pathology [3]. According to O.N. Petrushenkova [7], the frequency of infertility at a large industrial enterprise involved in the automotive industry was 15.1%, which exceeds the critical level determined by WHO experts (15%), at which infertile marriage represents a national problem due to its significant impact on demographic indicators. The prevalence of primary female

infertility was 4.5%, secondary - 10.6% [7]. It has been shown that infertility in marriage is caused by impaired reproductive function of women in 83.1% of cases. In 16.9% of married couples suffering from infertility, reproductive dysfunction was diagnosed in both spouses. The structure of the causes of female infertility is dominated by: tubal-peritoneal factor (38.5%), endocrine infertility (27.7%), genital endometriosis (23.0%). In 50.8% of women, infertility is caused by a combination of 2–4 factors. The most common causes of male infertility are: idiopathic oligozoospermia (36.3%), genital infection (27.3%) and varicocele (18.2%).

Purpose of the study— to study the structure of the causes of infertility in men and women in the city of Samarkand and the Samarkand region according to screening data.

Material and research methods. From October 2020 to June 2023, we conducted sociological and medical studies in a comparative aspect among families from rural and urban areas in the context of individual territories representing the corresponding regions of the country, in order to determine the causes of infertility (endocrine, non-endocrine, etc.) in spouses and selection of further management tactics and possible treatment (Samarkand and Samarkand region: Nurabad, Urgut and Pastdargom districts). A total of 100 married couples were examined - 200 people (100 men and 100 women of fertile age). The study material included men and women of reproductive age who are in infertile marriages and undergoing treatment for infertility or are registered in regional endocrinological dispensaries. The sample size is 200 people (100 men and 100 women), or 100 families. The study covered families in the city of Samarkand and the Samarkand region - 50 families each (Nurabad, Urgut and Pastdargom districts). Also, 50 individuals were examined using the Beck Anxiety Inventory (25 men and 25 women). The following methods were used during the study: the first stage - focus group, conversation, questionnaire for identifying depression and anxiety (Beck); as well as specially developed questionnaires for this medical study, etc.; the second stage is sampling. All study participants were divided into four groups. The first group is women suffering from infertility, aged 18 to 35 years. The second group is men suffering from infertility, aged 25 to 40 years. The third group is parents whose child (male or female) suffers from infertility. The fourth group is representatives of social institutions of the local community: leaders and activists of the mahalla committee, leaders and members of the mahalla women's council, doctors of the local medical institution. In mixed groups (third and fourth), the distribution of participants by gender was also taken

into account, i.e. the marginal ratio was 7:3. A total of 8 focus groups were conducted, with a focus group including 20 people. Sociological questionnaires have been developed for focus groups - separately for the husband, for the wife, and for the mother-in-law. During the study, 50 people (25 couples) out of 200 participants underwent psychological testing (Beck Anxiety and Depression Inventory). The answer in the first column is 0 points, the answer in the second column (slightly) is 1 point, the answer in the third column (moderate) is 2 points, the answer in the fourth column is 3 points. Then all points are summed up. The total score is interpreted as follows: 0–5 points—normal anxiety, 6–8—mild anxiety, 9–18—moderate anxiety, above 19—high anxiety. At the third stage, if necessary, patients were sent for further examination: CT/MRI of the pituitary gland, ultrasound of the genital organs, hormonal studies (LH, FSH, estradiol, progesterone, testosterone, TSH, prolactin), folliculometry (FM), spermogram, etc. FM was performed vaginally with ultrasound method starting from the 7th–8th day of the menstrual cycle (MC). For completeness of information, FM data were compared with BT and hormonal parameters.

Research results and discussion. The frequency of complaints of respondents on the Beck anxiety scale for the city of Samarkand and the Samarkand region is presented. According to the results of the analysis of the Beck scale, as can be seen from the table. 1, residents of Tashkent and the Samarkand region are not significantly susceptible to depression and anxiety in relation to infertility. Of the 200 men and women examined in Samarkand and the Samarkand region, 40 women and 40 men were examined, married from one to five years and suffering from primary or secondary infertility. In table. Figure 2 shows the structure of the causes of infertility in examined women aged 25 to 35 years suffering from infertility in Samarkand and the Samarkand region. As can be seen, in the examined women, the main place in the genesis of infertility is occupied by hormonal dysfunction (diffuse goiter with subclinical hypothyroidism, ovarian failure with menstrual dysfunction, polycystic ovary syndrome, hyperandrogenism, luteal phase deficiency, impaired folliculogenesis), as well as inflammatory diseases of the genitourinary system (TORCH - infections). The structure of the causes of infertility in examined men aged 25 to 40 years suffering from infertility in Samarkand and the Samarkand region is given. In the examined men from the city and village, the main place in the genesis of infertility is occupied by hormonal dysfunction (androgen deficiency associated with excess body weight, impaired spermatogenesis, hypergonadotropic and hypogonadotropic hypogonadism). Thus, in men with

infertility, significantly low values of average values of LH, FSH, free and total testosterone (hypogonadotropic hypogonadism) were found against the background of normoprolactinemia. Women were characterized by significantly low levels of LH, FSH, estradiol, progesterone on the 14th day of MC against the background of hyperprolactinemia, that is, anovulatory cycles. Infertility does not have a direct negative impact on the process of socialization of people with this diagnosis in the family, in the local community and at work [12]. This revealed fact indicates a deep transformation of values taking place in society. According to the modern understanding of the hierarchy of values, a person in himself is the highest value, without taking into account whether he is capable or incapable of childbearing. The reproductive function of a person is important, one might say the most important, for a person and for society, but it is not decisive, primary and decisive in determining the meaning of a person's life [13, 14]. Thus, for the normal and full socialization of a person diagnosed with infertility into public, social institutions, there are no objective or subjective obstacles. The socialization of people diagnosed with infertility depends critically on family members, and primarily on the husband or wife and their parents [16, 17].

Conclusions

1. According to the results of the Beck scale, residents of Tashkentai and the Samarkand region are not significantly susceptible to depression and anxiety regarding infertility.

2. In the examined women, the main place in the genesis of infertility is occupied by hormonal dysfunction, as well as inflammatory diseases of the genitourinary system.

3. In the examined men, the main role in the genesis of infertility is occupied by hormonal dysfunction (androgen deficiency associated with excess body weight, impaired spermatogenesis, hypergonadotropic and hypogonadotropic hypogonadism). 4. In men with infertility, significantly low values of average values of LH, FSH, free and total testosterone (hypogonadotropic hypogonadism) were found against the background of normoprolactinemia. Women were characterized by significantly low levels of LH, FSH, estradiol, progesterone on the 14th day of the menstrual cycle against the background of hyperprolactinemia (anovulatory cycles).

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OLIV TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA SOG'LOM TURMUSH TARZINI SHAKLLANTIRISH MASALALARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada oliy ta'lim muassasalarida inson salomatligi, jismoniy barkamolligi, sog'lom turmush tarzi madaniyatini shakllantirish hamda talaba yoshlarni jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlariga jalb qilish masalalari haqida so'z yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: sog'lom turmush tarzi, salomatlik, omil, meyoriy hujjat.

PROBLEMS OF DEVELOPING A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: This article discusses issues of human health, physical fitness, the formation of a healthy lifestyle culture in higher educational institutions, as well as the involvement of students and youth in physical culture and sports activities.

Key words: healthy lifestyle, health, factor, regulatory document.

Kirish. Salomatlik – insoniyat rivojining muhim tarkibiy qismlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Millat salomatligini ta'minlash sog'lom turmush tarzi tufayligina amalga oshiriladi. Sog'lom turmush tarzi - bu faol mehnat, ijod og'ushida yashash, kuchli jismoniy va ruhiy yuklamalarni, o'ta xavfli va zararli ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi omillarni yengil ko'tara oladigan har tomonlama taraqqiy etgan shaxsning shakllanish jarayonidir. Oliy o'quv yurti talabalari bo'sh vaqtini to'g'ri taqsimlash, kun tartibi, dam olishga va mehnat tartibiga rioya etishi sog'lom turmush tarzi ko'nikmalarining shakllanishida muhim ahamiyatga egadir.

Sog'lom turmush tarzi to'g'ri ovqatlanish bilan chambarchas bog'liq. Jahon sog'liqni saqlash tashkilotining ma'lumotiga ko'ra, jismoniy faollik hamda ovqatlanish me'yor va qoidalariga amal qilmaslik insonning erta o'limiga olib keluvchi qator kasalliklarning rivojlanishiga sabab bo'ladi. Bundan jiddiy xulosa

qilgan holda zararli odatlardan voz kechib, ommaviy sport bilan doimiy shug'ullanish, to'g'ri ovqatlanish tamoyillariga rioya qilish, xususan tarkibida tuz, qand va yog' miqdori ko'p bo'lgan hamda xamirli taom va shirinliklarni, non mahsulotlarini me'yoridan ortiq iste'mol qilmaslikni, bir so'z bilan aytganda, sog'lom turmush tarzini kundalik hayotga aylantirish zarur ekanligini bugungi davrning o'zi taqozo etmoqda. Sog'lom turmush tarzini hayotga keng tatbiq etish va ommaviy sportni yanada rivojlantirishning asosiy yo'nalishlari sifatida talabalar orasida sog'lom ovqatlanish madaniyatini keng targ'ib qilish zarur.

Respublikamizda sog'liqni saqlash hamda jismoniy tarbiya va sport sohalarini yanada isloh qilish bo'yicha qabul qilingan normativ-huquqiy hujjatlarda ushbu tizimlarni takomillashtirish bilan bir qatorda, aholi o'rtasida sog'lom turmush tarzini shakllantirish masalalari dolzarb hisoblangan. Jumladan, 2025 yilga qadar O'zbekiston Respublikasi sog'liqni saqlash tizimini, jismoniy tarbiya va sportni rivojlantirish konsepsiyalari hamda sog'lom turmush tarzini keng tatbiq etish va ommaviy sportni yanada rivojlantirish chora-tadbirlari tasdiqlandi va ijroga qaratildi [1,3,4].

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Sh. M. Mirziyoyev tomonidan 2020-yil 30-oktabrdagi PF-6099-son Farmoni qabul qilingan. Ushbu farmonning asosiy maqsadi jismoniy tarbiya va ommaviy sport bilan muntazam shug'ullanish hamda sog'lom turmush tarzi bo'yicha hayotiy ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish orqali har bir fuqaroda kasallikka qarshi kuchli immun tizimi paydo bo'lishini ta'minlash, zararli odatlardan voz kechish, to'g'ri ovqatlanish tamoyillariga amal qilish, tiklash va rehabilitatsiya ishlari hamda ommaviy jismoniy faollik tadbirlarini tizimli va samarali tashkil qilish, bu borada tegishli infratuzilma va boshqa zarur shart-sharoitlarni yaratishdan iborat.

Ma'lumki, oliy ta'lim muassasalarida inson salomatligi, jismoniy barkamolligi, sog'lom turmush tarzi madaniyatini shakllantirish uchun kurashar ekanmiz o'z maqsadimizga erishish uchun millatni sog'lom turmush tarzida yashashga o'rgatishimiz kerak bo'ladi. Sog'lom avlod deganda, biz faqat jismonan baquvvat farzandlarni emas, balki ma'naviy jihatdan ham boy va sog'lom avlodni nazarda tutishimiz lozim. Zero, ma'naviy sog'lom bo'lmasdan turib, jismonan sog'lom bo'lish mumkin emas. Har ikkala tushuncha bir biriga mos bo'lib, ham jismonan, ham ma'naviy sog'lom avlodga ega bo'lgan xalqni engib bo'lmaydi. Biz jismonan sog'lom, yuksak ma'naviyatli va yagona milliy g'oya asosida jipslashgan millatni shakllantirishni bosh maqsad qilib qo'yar ekanmiz uni sog'lom turmush tarzida yashashga o'rgatishimiz kerak bo'ladi.

Bugungi kunda jahonda inson salomatligi, jismoniy barkamolligi va imkoniyatlarini o'rganish, jismoniy yetuklikning inson aqliy va ijtimoiy faolligiga ta'sirini o'rganish, xususan, oliy ta'lim tizimi talabarlari ilmiy-amaliy pedagogik modellarini yaratish va ularni amalga oshirishda innovatsion usullar, texnologiyalarni qo'llash maqsadida ko'plab tadqiqot ishlari olib borilmoqda.

Oliy ta'lim muassasalari talabalarida jismoniy irodalilik, chidamlilik, g'alabaga intiluvchanlik kabi sifatlarning shakllanishida jismoniy tarbiya dars mashg'ulotlarini va sport to'garaklarining ahamiyati yuqoridir. Sababi, talabalarda sportchiga xos xarakter, xislatlar jismoniy tarbiya va sport faoliyatida, to'garaklar orqali asta-sekin shakllanadi hamda bu xislatlar uning doimiy sifatiga aylanadi. Hususan, jismoniy sifatlari yaxshi shakllangan talaba hayotiy faoliyatda ham jismonan baquvvat bo'ladi. Yoshlarni har tomonlama sog'lom, barkamol bo'lib yetishishida jismoniy madaniyat ta'limini milliy qadriyatlarga tayangan holda zamonaviy ko'rinishda tashkil etish, jismoniy tarbiya, sog'lomlashtirish, salomatlikni mustahkamlash, sog'lom turmush tarzini targ'ib qilishda yangicha yondashuv asosida o'tkazishni taqozo etmoqda.

Xulosa sifatida shuni aytish mumkinki, jismoniy barkamollik– ruhiy v aqliy yetuklikning asosi bo'lib, sog'lom tana sog'lom fikrlash qobiliyatiga ega bo'ladi. Shuning uchun, ta'lim tizimi yosh avlodning ham jismoniy, ham ruhiy rivojlanishi uchun qulay sharoitlarni yaratishi kerak. Har bir inson, har bir oila jismoniy tarbiya va sport bilan shug'ullanishni odat darajasiga chiqarishi bilan birga, qadriyat sifatida hurmat qilishi jamiyatning uzluksiz ravishda jismoniy tarbiya va sport bilan muntazam shug'ullanishiga sabab bo'ladi.

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SPORTCHI FAOLIYATIDA MOTIVATSIYANING O'RNI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada har qanday sohada, har qanday kasbda psixologiyaning o'rni, jumladan, sport sohasida ham psixologiyaning va eng asosiysi sportchi faoliyatida motivatsiyaning o'rni haqida fikrlar yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Psixologiya, motivatsiya, motiv, extiyoj, istak, xarakat, sportchi, malaka, sport.

THE ROLE OF MOTIVATION IN THE ACTIVITIES OF AN ATHLETE

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Abstract: This article examines the role of psychology in any field, any profession, including in the field of sports, and most importantly, the role of motivation in the activities of an athlete.

Key words: Psychology, motivation, motive, need, desire, action, athlete, skill, sport

Motivatsiya bu – maqsadga yo'naltirilgan hatti -harakatlarni boshlaydigan, boshqaradigan va saqlaydigan jarayon. Motivatsiya xulq- atvorni faollashtiradigan biologik, hissiy, ijtimoiy va bilim kuchlarni o'z ichiga oladi.

Asosan motivatsiya ikkita turga bo'linadi. Bular:

- 1) Tashqi turtki motivatsiya
- 2) Ichki motivatsiya.

Tashqi turtki motivatsiya bu – shaxsning tashqi tomonidan kelib chiqadigan va ko'pincha sovrinlar, pul, ijtimoiy tan olish, maqtash kabi mukofotlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Ichki motivatsiya bu – shaxsning ichidan kelib chiqadigan motivlar, masalan: muammoni hal qilishda shaxsiy qoniqish uchun murakkab krasvordlarni bajarish v.h.k. Psixologiya, motivatsiya, motiv, sport bu atamalarni o'zaro bir biri bilan bog'lar ekanmiz , sport va sportchi faoliyatida psixologiyaning va motivatsiyaning o'rni va ahamiyati juda katta albatta.

Yosh avlod salomatligini saqlash va mustahkamlash muammosi zamonaviy jamiyatning eng muhim muammolaridan biridir. Motivatsiya bu – kuch va xarakter sizga qiyinchiliklarni, muammolarni ko‘ngilsizliklarni, umidsizliklarni yengishdava kurashishda davom etishga imkon beradi. Motivatsiya cheksiz quvvatga ega bo‘lgan yoqilg‘idir, bu sportchilarni eng mashaqqatli mashq va yutuqlarga erishishiga undaydi. Motivatsiya har bir buyuk sportchi va har qanday katta sport yutug‘i uchun muvaffaqiyatningasosiy kalitidir.

Sportchi motivatsiyaning xususiyatlari, sportchi motivatsi amalda odatdagidek bir xil. Bir nechta o‘zgarishlar bilan sportchi motivatsiyasi ikki qismdan iborat. Bular:

- 1) Qisqa muddatli
- 2) Uzoq muddatli.

Qisqa muddatli motivatsiya bu – shu yerda va hozirda to‘siqni yengib o‘tish, muayyan vaqt ichida aniq maqsadga uchun qaror qilish. Uzoq muddatli motivatsiya bu – katta maqsadga erishish uchun qaror, bu yo‘l kichik muvaffaqiyatlardan iborat. Yuqoridagi fikrlarga asoslangan holda sport va sportchi faoliyatida motivatsiya. Biron bir bellashuv yoki mashg‘ulot oldidan ishtirokchilarga ya’ni sportchilarga murabbiy tomonidan motivatsiya beriladi. Bunda murabbiy yetarlicha bilim va ko‘nikmaga ega bo‘lgan o‘z ishining mutaxassisi bo‘lsa maqsadga muvofiq bo‘ladi. Yoki biron bir jamoaviy o‘yinlar oldidan ham bu hodisani yaqqol ko‘rishimiz mumkin. Ko‘pincha o‘yin oldidan (asosan raqib jamoa kuchli bo‘lsa) murabbiy jamoaning jangovor holatini ko‘tarish maqsadida jamoadagi motivni kuchaytirish uchun suxbat o‘tkazadi va jamoani jangga yani o‘yinga tayyorlaydi.

I.A.Djidaryanning fikriga ko‘ra “sportchi faoliyatining motivatsiyasi” tushunchasiga quyidagicha izoh berish mumkin: “Motivatsiya bu – sportchishaxsining o‘ziga xos holati bo‘lib, u o‘zining ehtiyoj va imkoniyatlarini sport faoliyati predmeti bilan o‘zaro bog‘liqligini ta’minlashi natijasida o‘sha vaqtdagi sport natijasini yuqori darajasiga erishish maqsadini amalga oshirish asosida namoyon bo‘ladi” .

Albatta, bu ta’rif motivatsiya to‘g‘risidagi yakuniy xulosa emas, uning mohiyati sportchini yuqori sport natijasiga intilishiga nima turtki berishining sababi to‘g‘risida sport mutaxassiga yo‘llanma berishi bilan izohlanadi.

Xulosa qilib aytadigan bo‘lsak sport va sportchi faoliyatida nafaqat kuch, mashq, mashg‘ulot va eng asosiysi psixologiya va motivatsiya ham juda katta o‘rin egallaydi. Jannatmakon yurtimizda sport va sportchilar faoliyatiga juda katta e’tibor qaratilgan. Sport turlari judayam ko‘p va ularning faoliyatida,

muvaffaqiyatidan psixologiya va motivatsiyaning o'zni ham beqiyos. Muhtaram yurtboshimiz ham yosh avlod va kelajak ravnaqi uchun sport sohasini rivojlantirish va yuksaltirish yo'lida juda katta islohatlar olib bormoqdalar Jumladan, futbol va futbolchi faoliyatida motivatsiyaning o'rniga keladigan bo'lsak, rivojlanib, o'sib borishar ekan albatta muvaffaqiyatga erishiladi va bu jarayonda ularga motivatsiya eng katta kuch bo'ladi desak adashmagan bo'lamiz nazarimda. Motiv va motivatsiyasiz hech qanaqa yutuq va muvaffaqiyatga erishib bo'lmaydi va insonni kuch g'ayratga to'la bo'lib yurishida motivatsiyaning alohida o'zni bor.

Mashhur "Real" futbol jamoasining murabbiysi Zinedin Zidan o'zining ikkinchi murabbiylik davridagi ilk mag'lubiyati futbolchilarda motivatsiya yetarli emasligi bilan ham qisman bog'liq ekanini ta'kidladi. Shunday ekan futbolchilar balki boshqa sport va sportchilar faoliyatida ham motivatsiyaning alohida o'zni bor. Maydonga yig'ilgan futbolchilar jamoasining motivatsiyasi ya'ni kuchi faqatgina ularning o'zlarida emas balki ularning kiygan kiyimlari, murabbiyning mahorati va futbolchilarga eng katta kuch va motivatsiya ularning maydonga yig'ilgan muhlislari ularning qichqiriqlar, qarsaklari va qo'llab quvvatlashlari futbolchilar uchun balki boshqa soha vakillari uchun ham katta motivatsiya bo'ladi. Futbolchilar o'yin jarayonida ularga bo'lgan ishonchni ko'taringki kayfiyatni o'qishlarni va eng asosiysi o'zlarining vatan bayrog'ini ko'rib, xalqning ishonchini oqlash uchun o'zlariga motivatsiya olib astoyidil harakat qilishadi. Shuni alohida ta'kidlash joizki yuqorida aytilganimizdek nafaqat futbol balki boshqa jamiki sohalarda faoliyat bilan birgalikda psixologiya va motivatsiyaning o'zni beqiyos va tugalmas o'rin olgan desak adashmagan bo'lamiz nazarimda. Insoniyat hayot kechirib istiqomat qilib borar ekan albatta mag'lubiyatlar ularning ketidan g'alabalar kelib ketaveradi. Inson mag'lubiyatga yuz tutgan vaqtlarida ham albatta psixologiyaga yuzlanadi va o'zi uchun kerakli bo'lgan motivatsiyani olib yana hayotda olg'a qadam tashlash uchun kuch yog'adi. Psixologiya, motiv va motivatsiya insoniyat hayotida juda katta o'rin egallagan desak hech ham adashmagan bo'lamiz albatta.

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MA'LUMOTLAR BAZASI MODELI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola ma'lumotlar bazasini tanlanlash va o'rnatib ko'rish. Tanlangan ma'lumotlar bazasi turini va tilini hisobga olish va ma'lumotlar bazasini o'rnatib ko'ring. bu, dasturni ishga tushirish va ma'lumotlarni saqlash uchun iloji bor bo'lgan platformani belgilashdir. Ma'lumotlarni yozish va o'qish uchun interfeysni yaratish. ma'lumotlarni qo'shish, o'qish, yangilash va o'chirish uchun foydalanuvchi interfeysini yaratish kerak. Bu interfeys, dasturning ma'lumotlar bazasi bilan qanday muloqot qilish haqida ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. Ma'lumotlar, baza, interfeys, madel, tur, qo'shish, ayirish

DATABASE MODEL

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Abstract. This article is about selecting and installing a database. Try installing the account and database for the selected database type and language. this is to specify the platform where it is possible to run the application and store the data. Create an interface for writing and reading data. you need to create a user interface to add, read, update and delete data. This interface describes how the application communicates with the database.

Key words. Data, base, interface, model, type, addition, subtraction

Kirish. Ma'lumotlar bazasi modeli qurish uchun bir nechta asosiy qadamlar mavjud. quyidagi jarayon ma'lumotlar bazasi modelini qurish uchun umumiy qadamlarni ta'riflaydi.

Kerakli ma'lumotlarni aniqlang. ma'lumotlar bazasining asosiy qadami, ma'lumotlar turi va strukturasi bo'yicha qanday ma'lumotlarni saqlash kerakligini aniqlashdir. bu qadamda, maqsad va talablarga muvofiq ma'lumotlarni tanlash juda muhim.

Ma'lumotlar strukturasi (schema) tuzing. ma'lumotlar bazasining tuzilishi yoki shema tuzilishi, saqlangan ma'lumotlarning turlari, ularning aloqasi va qanday xususiyatlarini o'z ichiga oladi. ma'lumotlar bazasining qo'llaniladigan tili (sql, nosql) va ma'lumotlar bazasining turlari (relational, document-based, graph, etc.) ham bu jarayonning bir qismini bildiradi.

Ma'lumotlar bazasini tanlang va o'rnatib ko'ring. tanlangan ma'lumotlar bazasi turini va tilini hisobga oling va ma'lumotlar bazasini o'rnatib ko'ring. bu, dasturni ishga tushirish va ma'lumotlarni saqlash uchun iloji bor bo'lgan platformani belgilashdir. Ma'lumotlarni yozish va o'qish uchun interfeysni yaratish. ma'lumotlarni qo'shish, o'qish, yangilash va o'chirish uchun foydalanuvchi interfeysini yaratish kerak. bu interfeys, dasturning ma'lumotlar bazasi bilan qanday muloqot qilishini belgilaydi.

Ma'lumotlarni kirishing va chiqarish uchun operatsiyalarni qo'llab-quvvatlash. ma'lumotlarni ma'lumotlar bazasiga kiriting va uningdan chiqarishni o'rganish juda muhim. buning uchun moslashtirilgan so'rov tili va metodlarni o'rganishingiz lozim. Xavfsizlik vaqti. ma'lumotlarni himoyalash juda muhim. ma'lumotlar bazasi xavfsizligi uchun xavfsizlik protokollari, autentifikatsiya va avtorizatsiya usullari qo'llanilishi kerak.

Indekslash va optimallashtirish. ma'lumotlar bazasining tez ishlashini ta'minlash uchun ma'lumotlar bazasini indekslash va so'rovni optimallashtirish zarur bo'ladi. Ushbu qadamlar, ma'lumotlar bazasi modelini qurishda asosiy elementlardir. har bir qadamni diqqat bilan bajarish, ma'lumotlar bazasining ishlashini saqlashga yordam beradi. Ma'lumotlar bazasi (mb) modeli, ma'lumotlar bazasini (mb) yaratish va uni qo'llab-quvvatlashda foydalaniladigan boshqa yordamchilar va usullar to'plamini aks ettiradi. mb modellari ma'lumotlarni saqlash, boshqarish va ularga kirishni tashkil etadi. ularning o'sishi va aks etishi uchun ma'lumotlarni qanday tashkil etish va ma'lumotlar orasidagi aloqalarni boshqarishga dair ko'p usullar mavjud bo'ladi.

Ma'lumotlar bazasi modelini qurishni o'rganishda quyidagi bosqichlar o'rinli. ma'lumotlar bazasini talab qilish (requirements analysis). bu bosqichda,

tizimning kerak bo'lgan ma'lumotlar turi va miqdori aniqlanadi. talablar tashkil etishning yo'l harakatlari shuni o'z ichiga oladi: ma'lumotlar bazasining turi (relational, nosql, graph, va h.k.), ma'lumotlar bazasining o'lchami, yozuvlar soni, xususiyatlari va boshqalar.

Ma'lumotlar bazasi skemasi (database schema) yaratish. skema, ma'lumotlar bazasidagi jadvallar (tables), ustunlar (columns), indekslar va boshqa obyektlarni belgilovchi bog'lanishlar tuzilishidir. mb modelini yaratishda skema shakllanadi va ma'lumotlar o'z joyini topadi.

Ma'lumotlarni qo'shish, o'zgartirish, o'chirish (crud) operatsiyalari. ma'lumotlarni qo'shish, o'zgartirish, o'chirish va ma'lumotlarni ko'rish (read) operatsiyalari mb modelini ishlatishning asosiy qismlaridan biridir.

Ma'lumotlar bazasini boshqarish. mb boshqarishda, ma'lumotlarni saqlash, ularga kirishni boshqarish, xavfsizlik va farq qiluvchi huquqni boshqarish kabi muammolarga duch keladi. bu qisimda, mb uchun interfeys tuzish, monitoring va tuning usullari, ma'lumotlar tarqatma va tiklama (backup and recovery) jarayonlarini belgilash kabi chora-tadbirlar amalga oshiriladi.

Integratsiya va boshqa sistemalar bilan aloqa. ko'p ma'lumotlar tizimlari boshqa tizimlar, xizmatlar, yoki ilovalar bilan integratsiya qilinishi kerak. mb modellari, boshqa sistemalar bilan to'lovlarni amalga oshirish va ma'lumot almashishni osonlashtirish uchun imkoniyatlarni ta'minlaydi.

Tizimni monitoring qilish va o'zgartirishlar kiritish. tizimning ishlash holatini nazorat qilish, monitor qilish va zarur bo'lgan o'zgartirishlarni kiritish, buning orqali tizimni mustahkamlashning muhim qismlaridan biridir.

Dastur tuzish bo'yicha ko'p texnologiyalarni, masalan, sql, nosql, mongodb, mysql, postgresql, firebase, va h.k. ishlatish mumkin. shuningdek, obyektory tuzilmalarda, entity-relationship (er) modellari va yoshlar uchun tuzilmalar uchun klass va jadvallar ishlatish mumkin.

Ma'lumotlar bazasi modeli qurish quyidagi bosqichlarni o'z ichiga oladi.

Malablar tushirish. ma'lumotlar bazasi modelini qurishdan oldin, talablarni tushirish kerak. bu, qaysi ma'lumotlar saqlanishi kerakligini, ularning formati, aloqador so'rovlarni qanday bajarish, va ma'lumotlarga qanday qo'shimcha operatsiyalarni amalga oshirish kerakligini o'z ichiga oladi.

Ma'lumotlar modelini rivojlantirish. ma'lumotlarni saqlash uchun kerakli tuzilmalar va algoritmlarni rivojlantirish. bu qadamda, ma'lumotlarni qanday kiritish, o'qish, yangilash, va o'chirish kerakligini belgilash kerak. Xa'lumotlar bazasini rivojlantirish. ma'lumotlar bazasini qanday saqlash va boshqarishni rivojlantirish. bunda, ma'lumotlarni strukturizatsiya qilish, indekslash,

bog'lovchilar, ma'lumotlar bazasiga so'rov yozish, va boshqa muhim jarayonlarni belgilash kerak.

Xavfsizlik. ma'lumotlar bazasining xavfsizligi muhimdir. ma'lumotlarni himoyalash, ruxsat berish vaqtlarini boshqarish, avtorizatsiya va autentifikatsiya tuzilmalari qo'llanish kerak.

Testlar va tahlil. modelni test qilish va tahlil qilish uchun testlarni yaratish. bu, modelning ishlashini tekshirish, muammolarni aniqlash va ularni tuzatish uchun muhimdir. Monitoring va optimallashtirish. ma'lumotlar bazasi va modelni monitoring qilish, ularning ishlashini to'g'ri kelish uchun kerak. muammolar aniqlanganida, modelni yangilash va optimallashtirish lozim.

Integratsiya. ma'lumotlar bazasi va modelni dasturlash tillari, frameworklari yoki boshqa dasturlash vositalari bilan integratsiya qilish.

Dokumentatsiya. barcha qadamlarni, ma'lumotlar bazasini, modelni, va dasturlashni tushunadigan dokumentatsiya yaratish. Bu bosqichlarni tuzish, modelni ishga tushirish va uning ishlashini ta'minlashda yordam beradi. har bir tashqi ma'lumotlarni integratsiya qilish, ma'lumotlar bazasini tozalash va tuzatish, hamda dastur tuzilishini rivojlantirish jarayonida o'zining o'ziga xos muammolari bo'ladi.

Asosiy qism. Ma'lumotlar bazalari bilan ishlash (yaratish, tanlash, o'chirish).

Dasturni ishga tushirish uchun u ishga tushirilganda u ishlaydigan ma'lumot bazasini yaratish kerak (barcha ma'lumotlar u erda saqlanadi). axborot bazasini yaratish rejimiga o'tish uchun dasturni ishga tushirish oynasida "qo'shish" tugmachasini bosish kerak. natijada, rasmda ko'rsatilgan oyna.

Ma'lumotlar modellari turli sohalarda, maqsadlari va platformalarda farqli bo'lishi mumkin. Ammo umumiy maqsadlar uchun, quyidagi jarayonni foydalanish mumkin:

Ma'lumot to'plash. Ma'lumotlar to'plangan va tarqalgan bo'lishi kerak. Bu ko'p o'chib ketishi mumkin, ammo boshqa uchun o'rganishda yoki dasturlar ustida tajribani oshirishda foydalanishingiz mumkin.

Tahlil va O'rganish. Ma'lumotlar analiz qilinishi, to'g'rilanishi, xilma-xil qismlarga bo'lishi kerak. Bu, asosiy maqbul narsalarni aniqlash va ularni ma'lumotlar modellari uchun yo'nalish bilan ta'minlashga yordam beradi.

Modelning O'rnatilish. Modelning o'rnatilishi o'rganilgan ma'lumotlar bo'yicha, masalan, kategoriyalar, eigenvectors, yoki ko'nikma. Modelni O'qish. Modelni yaratish uchun o'rganilgan ma'lumotlar asosida uni o'qish. Bu

algoritmlar uchun ma'lumotlarning bir qismini modelning biror qismini aniqlash uchun o'rganilgan ma'lumotlar asosida egallaydi.

Testlash va Baholash. Modelni tekshirish uchun mustahkam va mustahkam bo'lishi kerak. Bu to'g'ri natijalarni ta'minlash va uni optimallashtirishga yordam beradi.

Ommaviy Tarqatish. Modelni ishga tushirish uchun uni amalga oshirish uchun integratsiyaga tayyorlash. Bu xizmatning keng tarqalishi, API orqali qo'llanish yoki dastur tizimi ichida integratsiya qilishni o'z ichiga oladi.

Bu umumiy jarayonni tushuntirish uchun yordam beradi, ammo maqsadga mos holda ushbu jarayonni dastlabki qadamlariga o'zgartirishingiz mumkin. Maqsadlar, ma'lumotlar va dastur orqali platformalarga bog'liq bo'lgan ma'lumotlar modellari uchun o'zgarimoqchi bo'lgan turlicha muammolarni yechish uchun o'zingizga mos usulni tanlashni maslahat beraman.

Ma'lumotlar modellari kabi tushuncha bilan tanishishdan, ularning turlarini, tasniflarini o'rganishdan, shuningdek, batafsil tavsifni ko'rib chiqishdan oldin, ushbu tushunchalarni va barcha sohalarni o'z ichiga olgan informatikaning ma'nosini tushunishimiz kerak., o'rganan. Ushbu maqolada biz ushbu fanning asosiy atamalari va ustunlarini ko'rib chiqamiz, xususan, ma'lumotlar tuzilmalarining turlari, ulardagi munosabatlar va boshqalar haqida gapiramiz.

Ma'lumotlar modeli tuzilishini o'rganishga o'tish uchun siz ushbu ma'lumotlar va ma'lumotlarning printsiplial jihatdan nima ekanligini tushunishingiz kerak.

Mutlaqo insoniyat jamiyati mavjudligining har qanday daqiqasida ma'lumot juda katta rol o'ynadi, ya'ni inson tomonidan atrofimizdagi keng va xilma-xil dunyodan olingan ma'lumotlar. Misol uchun, hatto ibtidoiy odamlar ham bizga qoyatosh rasmlari yordamida o'zlarining oddiy turmush tarzi va an'analari haqida ma'lumot qoldirgan. O'shandan beri odamlar ko'plab ilmiy kashfiyotlar qilishdi, o'zlarining o'tmishdoshlari haqida ma'lumot to'plashdi va kundalik ma'lumotlarni to'plashdi.yangiliklar, shu tariqa tobora ko'proq hajmdagi ma'lumotlarga ega bo'lib, ularga qimmatlilik va ishonchlilik kabi sifatlarni beradi.

Vaqt o'tishi bilan ma'lumotlar miqdori shunchalik katta va ulkan bo'lib qoldiki, insoniyat uni mustaqil ravishda o'z xotirasida saqlash, uni qo'lda qayta ishlash va unda biron-bir amalni bajarishga qodir emas edi. Aynan shuning uchun ham bugungi kundagi fundamental fan - informatikaga ehtiyoj paydo bo'ldi, uning ko'lami axborotning turli xil o'zgarishlari bilan bog'liq bo'lgan inson faoliyati sohasini o'z ichiga oladi. Informatika hayotimizning deyarli barcha

sohalarini qamrab oladi: oddiy matematik hisob-kitoblardan tortib murakkab muhandislik va arxitektura dizaynigacha, shuningdek, animatsion va animatsion filmlar yaratishgacha. U o'z oldiga axborotni avtomatlashtirilgan qayta ishlash, tizimlashtirish, saqlash va uzatish kabi asosiy maqsadlarni qo'yadi.

Bugungi mavzuda biz ma'lumotlarning tuzilishiga alohida to'xtalamiz, ya'ni ma'lumotlar modeli haqida gapiramiz. Biroq, bundan oldin suhbatimiz mavzusiga bevosita bog'liq bo'lgan boshqa ba'zi fikrlarga aniqlik kiritish kerak. Ya'ni: ma'lumotlar bazalari va DBMS.

Ma'lumotlar bazalari (MB) tuzilgan ma'lumotlar turidir.

Bu atama mantiqiy bog'liq bo'lgan umumiy ma'lumotlar to'plamiga ishora qiladi. Ma'lumotlar bazalari - bu katta hajmdagi ma'lumotlarga ega bo'lgan dinamik saytlarda faol foydalaniladigan tuzilmalar. Masalan, bu turli xil onlayn-do'konlarning resurslari, mablag'lar portallari ommaviy axborot vositalari yoki boshqa korporativ manbalar.

Ma'lumotlar bazasini boshqarish tizimlari (DBMS) - ma'lumotlar bazalarini yaratish, ularni kerakli shaklda saqlash va ulardagi kerakli ma'lumotlarni tezkor qidirishni tashkil qilish uchun mo'ljallangan turli xil dasturiy ta'minot to'plami. Keng qo'llaniladigan DBMSga misol sifatida Microsoft Office-ning bir qatorida chiqarilgan Microsoft Access-ni keltirish mumkin. Ushbu ma'lumotlar bazasining o'ziga xos xususiyati shundaki, unda VBA tili mavjudligi tufayli Accessning o'zida ma'lumotlar bazalari asosida ishlaydigan ilovalar yaratish mumkin.

Ma'lumotlar bazalarini bir nechta turli mezonlarga ko'ra tasniflash mumkin:

- ✓ Model turiga ko'ra (ular muhokama qilinadi).
- ✓ Saqlash joyi bo'yicha (qattiq disk, operativ xotira, optik disklar).
- ✓ Foydalanish turi bo'yicha (mahalliy, ya'ni bir foydalanuvchi unga kirish huquqiga ega; o'rtacha, ya'ni ma'lumotlar bazasidagi ma'lumotlarni bir necha kishi ko'rishi mumkin; umumiy - bunday ma'lumotlar bazalari bir nechta serverlarda va shaxsiy kompyuterlarda joylashgan., ya'ni ulardagi ma'lumotlarni ko'rish imkoniyati juda ko'p odamlarga tegishli).
- ✓ Ma'lumotlar mazmuniga ko'ra (ilmiy, tarixiy, leksikografik va boshqalar).
- ✓ Bazaning aniqlik darajasi bo'yicha (markazlashtirilgan va taqsimlangan).
- ✓ Bir jinsliligi bo'yicha (mos ravishda heterojen va bir jinsli).

Shuningdek, boshqa ahamiyatsiz funksiyalar uchun.

Bunday ma'lumotlar bazasining asosiy qismi ma'lumotlar modellaridir. Ular ifodalaydixborot tuzilmalari va ularni qayta ishlash, kerakli ma'lumotlarni qidirishni tashkil etish jarayonini soddalashtirish va tezlashtirish bo'yicha operatsiyalar to'plami.

Ma'lumotlar bazalarining xilma-xilligi mavjud, ammo ularning barchasi yanada keng tarqalgan va fundamental modellarga asoslangan. Axborot ma'lumotlari modellarining tasnifi ham juda ko'p turli xil turlarga bo'linadi. Bu erda eng ko'p ishlatiladigan toifalar:

- ✓ ierarxik model;
- ✓ tarmoq diagrammasi;
- ✓ relational model;
- ✓ obyektga yo'n altirilgan sxemalar.

Bu turdagi ma'lumotlar modellarining barchasi bir-biridan ulardagi ma'lumotlarni taqdim etish va saqlash xususiyati bilan farqlanadi.

Foydalanuvchi yuqoridagi har qanday turdagi ma'lumotlar bazasini yaratishi mumkin. Ammo shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, ma'lumotlar modelini tanlash ba'zi omillarga bog'liqlikni aniqlaydi.

Eng muhim mezon - mijoz tomonidan foydalaniladigan DBMS ma'lum bir modelni qo'llab-quvvatlaydimi. Aksariyat DBMSlar shunday tuzilganki, foydalanuvchiga foydalaniladigan ma'lumotlar modeli taqdim etiladi, biroq ularning ba'zilari bir vaqtning o'zida bir nechta turli analoglarni qo'llab-quvvatlaydi. Keling, ularning xususiyatlarini birma-bir ko'rib chiqaylik.

Bu ma'lumotlarni taqdim etish modellarining turlaridan biri bo'lib, ularni umumiydan xususiya qarab tartiblangan elementlar to'plami sifatida tashkil qiladi.

Tuzilish - bu teskari daraxt. Muayyan faylga kirish uchunbitta yo'l bor.

Ierarxik model uchta asosiy shartga javob berishi kerak:

- ✓ Har bir quyi darajadagi tugunni faqat bitta yuqori darajadagi tugunga ulash mumkin.
- ✓ Ierarxiyada faqat bitta asosiy ildiz tugun mavjud bo'lib, u boshqa tugunlarga bo'ysunmaydi va yuqori darajada.
- ✓ Ierarxiyadagi har qanday tugunga ildiz tugunidan faqat bitta yo'l bor.

Munosabatlar turi birdan ko'pga.

U asosan ierarxiyaga tayanadi va u bilan juda ko'p umumiyliklarga ega. Ularning orasidagi asosiy farq havola turi bo'lib, u ko'pdan ko'pga munosabatni bildiradi, ya'ni havolalar turli tugunlar o'rtasida mavjud bo'lishi mumkin.

Tarmoq modelining afzalligi shundaki, u boshqa modellarga qaraganda xotira va tezlik jihatidan kamroq shaxsiy kompyuter resurslarini sarflaydi.

Ushbu sxemaning kamchiligi shundaki, agar siz saqlangan ma'lumotlarning strukturasi o'zgartirishingiz kerak bo'lsa, siz ushbu tarmoq modeli asosida ishlaydigan barcha ilovalarni o'zgartirishingiz kerak bo'ladi, chunki bunday tuzilma mustaqil emas.

Bugungi kunda eng keng tarqalgan. Ushbu ma'lumotlar modelidagi ob'ektlar va ular o'rtasidagi munosabatlar jadvallar bilan ifodalanadi va ulardagi munosabatlar ob'ektlar sifatida qaraladi. Bunday jadvaldagi ustunlar maydonlar, qatorlar esa yozuvlar deb ataladi. Har bir relyatsion model jadvali mos kelishi kerak quyidagi xususiyatlar:

- ✓ Uning barcha ustunlari mutlaqo bir xil, ya'ni bitta ustunda joylashgan barcha elementlar bir xil turdagi va ruxsat etilgan maksimal hajmga ega bo'lishi kerak.
- ✓ Har bir ustunning o'ziga xos nomi bor.
- ✓ Jadvalda bir xil qatorlar bo'lmazligi kerak.
- ✓ Jadvaldagi satrlar va ustunlarning paydo bo'lish tartibi ixtiyoriy bo'lishi mumkin.

Munosabat modeli, shuningdek, ushbu jadvallar o'rtasidagi munosabatlar turlarini, jumladan, birga-bir, bir-ko'p va ko'p-ko'p munosabatlarini hisobga oladi.

Jadvalli relyatsion modelga asoslangan ma'lumotlar bazalari moslashuvchan, moslashuvchan va yuqori darajada kengaytirilishi mumkin. Har bir ma'lumot obyektiga eng kichik va foydali bo'laklarga bo'lingan.

Obyektga yo'naltirilgan ma'lumotlarni qurish modelida ma'lumotlar bazalari tegishli funksiyalarga ega qayta foydalanish mumkin bo'lgan dasturiy ta'minot elementlari to'plami bilan belgilanadi. Bir nechta ob'ektga yo'naltirilgan ma'lumotlar bazalari mavjud:

- ✓ Multimedia ma'lumotlar bazasi.
- ✓ Gipermatn ma'lumotlar bazasi.

Birinchi media ma'lumotlarini o'z ichiga oladi. U turli xil tasvirlarni o'z ichiga olishi mumkin, masalan, aloqador modelda saqlanmaydi.

Gipermatnli ma'lumotlar bazasi har qanday ma'lumotlar bazasi ob'ektini istalgan boshqa ob'ekt bilan bog'lash imkonini beradi. Bu turli xil ma'lumotlar to'plamida aloqani tashkil qilish uchun juda qulaydir, ammo bunday model o'tkazishda idealdan uzoqdir. raqamli tahlillar.

Ehtimol, ob'ektga yo'n altirilgan model eng ommabop va qo'llaniladigan modeldir, chunki u munosabatlar kabi jadvallar ko'rinishidagi ma'lumotlarni o'z ichiga olishi mumkin, lekin undan farqli o'laroq, jadval yozuvlari bilan cheklanmaydi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

1. "Deep Learning" - Ian Goodfellow, Yoshua Bengio, va Aaron Courville tomonidan yozilgan bu kitob ma'lumotlar modellari, maxsus maqsadli neuron tarmoqlari, va shunga o'xshash muddatlarga bo'lgan intensiv tushunchalarni bermoqda.
2. "Pattern Recognition and Machine Learning" - Christopher M. Bishop tomonidan yozilgan bu kitob, ma'lumotlar modellari va moslashtirish uchun qo'llaniladigan asosiy tushunchalarni ta'lim etadi.
3. "Hands-On Machine Learning with Scikit-Learn, Keras, and TensorFlow" - Aurélien Géron tomonidan yozilgan bu kitob amaliy ma'lumotlar modellari va TensorFlow, Keras, va Scikit-Learn kutubxonalaridan foydalanishni o'rganishga yordam beradi.
4. "Python Machine Learning" - Sebastian Raschka va Vahid Mirjalili tomonidan yozilgan bu kitob Python kutubxonalarini yordamida ma'lumotlar modellari yaratishni o'rganishni maqsad qilgan.
5. "Data Science for Business" - Foster Provost va Tom Fawcett tomonidan yozilgan bu kitob, ma'lumotlar modellari va o'rganilgan ma'lumotlar bilan ishlashni biznes va ish tajribasiga taalluqli qiladi.

ZAMONAVIY YOSHLAR MA'NAVIY MADANIYATINI BOYIB BORISH OMILLARI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy jamiyat va uning istiqboli taraqqiyotidagi turli yondashuvlar va yoshlarda moddiy dunyoning o'tkinchiligi, ma'naviy madaniyatning asrlar davomida e'zozlanishi borasidagi tushunchalarni shakllantirishdagi fikrlar yoritilgan

Kalit so'zlar: yoshlar ma'naviy madaniyati, jamiyat, taraqqiyot, ma'naviy tarbiya, yangi zamon ma'naviyati, an'analar, qadriyatlar, salohiyat, sotsiogenez

FACTORS OF ENRICHING THE SPIRITUAL CULTURE OF MODERN YOUTH

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Abstract. In this article, various approaches to the development of modern society and its prospects, and thoughts on the formation of young people's understanding of the transitoriness of the material world and the appreciation of spiritual culture over the centuries are highlighted.

Key words: moral culture, society, development, moral education, modern culture, traditions, values, culture, sociogenesis

Bugungi kunga kelib yoshlar masalasi bilan shug'ullanish, ularning intellektual salohiyatini to'laqonli rivojlantirish, bu borada tadrijiylik negizida milliy strategiya va mexanizmlarni yaratish zamon talabiga aylanib qoldi. Bunda yoshlar davr ruhiyati, ma'naviy qiyofasi, ahloqiy ideallari bilan mavjud jamiyatdagi paradigmali holatlarni vujudga keltirib yuboradi. Bu jarayonda ular turli qarama-qarshiliklarga duch kelishi, rivojlangan davlatlar tajribasidan andoza olgan holda voqelikka falsafiy-madaniy nuqtai nazardan yondashishlari namoyon bo'ladi. "Jamiyatda insonning ilmiy tadqiqotlar natijasida olingan ma'lumotlar falsafaning obyektiv qonunlarni ochishi va umumiy kategoriyalarni ishlab

chiqishi uchun empirik ma'lumotlar bo'la oladi". Shu boisdan ulardagi kelajakka qaratilgan ma'naviy madaniyatning ba'zi masalalarini hisobga olish juda muhimdir.

Yoshlarning ma'naviy madaniyati tushunchasi quyidagi tarkibiy qismlarni qamrab kiradi: kognitiv madaniyat; siyosiy madaniyat; ahloqiy madaniyat; huquqiy madaniyat; estetik madaniyat. Ushbu asosiy qismlardan tashkil topgan yoshlar ma'naviy madaniyati insonning barcha ijtimoiy hayot sohalarida mujassamlashadi. Yoshlar ma'naviy madaniyati o'z tarkibiy qismiga ma'naviy tarbiyani ham qamrab oladi. Jamiyatda bu jarayon konsepsiya sifatida odamlarning ilm doirasini kengaytiradi. Maqsad va vazifalarni amalga oshirishda ma'naviy tarbiya tashabbuskorlik, vijdonlilik, poklik, adolat g'oyalariga sadoqat tuyg'ularini qaror toptiradi. Yoshlarda moddiy dunyoning o'tkinchiligi, ma'naviy madaniyatning asrlar davomida e'zozlanishi borasidagi tushunchalarni shakllantiradi. Yoshlarning moddiy madaniyatni o'zlashtirishi natijasi bo'lgan bevosita ma'naviy ishlab chiqarish jarayoni o'zining xilma-xil ko'rinishlari va qiyofalarini ham namoyon etib boradi. Unda yoshlar o'zining iqtidori, intilishi va tashabbuslari bilan ma'naviy jarayonlarni harakatga keltirib boradi "Moddiy madaniyatni ma'naviy madaniyatdan ajratib bo'lmaydi, ayni paytda ma'naviy madaniyat ham moddiy madaniyatsiz yuzaga kelmaydi, ular o'zaro bog'liq holda rivojlanib boradi". Natijada yoshlarning intellektual salohiyati doirasida ma'naviy munosabatlar ham betakror ko'rinishlarda boyib boradi. Shunday ekan, har bir inson hamda kamol topib kelayotgan yosh avlod uchun ma'naviyat suv bilan havodek naqadar zarurligini unutmasligimiz darkor. Ma'lumki, masala va muammoning mohiyatini anglab yetish chog'ida uning mazmunini ochib berish maqsadida ishlatiladigan tushuncha va kategoriyalarning mazmun-mohiyatiga e'tibor qaratish juda muhim sanaladi. Shu ma'noda ma'naviyat va madaniyat tushunchalari ham alohida ilmiy tahlillarga muhtoj bo'lib, ayrim tadqiqotchilar tomonidan muayyan ko'lamda talqin etilgan.

Ma'naviyat tushunchasining ma'no-mazmuni haqida fikr yuritganda uning jamiyatda tutgan rolini teran anglamasdan turib ma'naviy madaniyat haqida so'z yuritib bo'lmaydi. Chunki ma'naviy madaniyat ma'naviyatning real hodisa sifatida yuzaga chiqishi, uning voqeiy bo'lish jarayonining yuzaga kelishidan iborat. Nazariy ongning bir qismi bo'lgan ma'naviy madaniyatning shakllari amaliyot bilan bog'liq. Voqelikka nisbatan yoshlar ongida ham ma'naviy madaniyatning elementlari shakllanib, milliylik bilan bog'liq ravishda ijtimoiy ong rivojlanadi.

Ma'naviy madaniyat, aslida, kishilik jamiyati tarixida asrlar davomida shakllangan inson tafakkurining mahsuli bo'lib, unda insonning voqelikka stixiyali tarzda yondashuvi asosida ma'naviy dunyoqarash vujudga kelgan. Astasekinlik bilan tevarak-atrofdagi narsa va hodisalarga aqliy munosabatning rivojlanishi negizida ma'naviy madaniyat unsurlari ijobiy va foydali ahamiyat kasb etgan va shuning uchun avloddan-avlodga meros sifatida qoldirish uchun zarur deb topilgan. Bu esa, o'z navbatida insonning aql-zakovatida yangicha tafakkur tarzi shakllanishi bilan birga, borliqning narsa va predmetlari, hayvonot olami, koinot, megaolam va umuman dunyo to'g'risidagi qarashlarining kengayishiga olib kelgan.

Ma'naviy ishlab chiqarish jarayonida siyosiy va huquqiy mafkura, falsafa, ahloq, san'at sohasidagi erishilgan yutuqlar saralanib boradi. Ular ma'naviy boyliklarni yaratuvchi shaxslar tomonidan qayta ishlanib, sayqallanadi va odamlarning ehtiyojlarini qondirish tomonga yo'naltiriladi. Shu boisdan "ma'naviy madaniyat – insonning ma'naviy xususiyat va xislatlari, jamiyatning madaniy darajasini aks ettiruvchi tushuncha" sifatida olib qaraladi. Unda insonning oddiy yashashi bilan bog'liq kundalik turmushning muhim ehtiyojlari tizimi jamiyat bilan bog'liq holda ifodalangan.

S.Otamurodov fikriga ko'ra esa, "ma'naviy madaniyat voqelikni badiiy aks ettirish va o'zlashtirish vositasidir". Bunda voqelikda inson mehnati natijasida yaratiladigan moddiy va ma'naviy boyliklar, shaxs ma'naviy qiyofasining yuksalishiga xizmat qiladigan ahloq qoidalariga rioya etish masalalari aks etgan.

Biroq, ushbu o'rinda ta'kidlash lozimki, bizningcha, S. Otamurodovning bu fikri muhokama etilayotgan masala yuzasidan mutlaq haqiqat darajasi uchun da'vogarlik qila olmaydi. Chunki ma'naviy madaniyat voqelikni badiiy aks ettirish tushunchasidan ancha kengroq tushuncha. Binobarin, olimning badiiy aks ettirish jihatini mutlaqlashtiradigan bo'lsak, siyosiy, ilmiy, huquqiy aks ettirish kabi jihatlari ushbu yondashuv doirasiga sig'may qolishi tabiiydir. Shunday ekan, ma'naviy madaniyatni voqelikni badiiy aks ettirishga tenglashtirish asossiz, balki voqelikni badiiy aks ettirishni ma'naviy madaniyatni shakllantirish vositalaridan biri deyish to'g'riroq bo'ladi.

Ma'naviyat asosiy tushunchalar izohli lug'atida "ma'naviyat – inson ruhiy va aqliy olamini ifodalovchi tushuncha" sifatida keltirilgan bo'lsa, O'zbekiston milliy entsiklopediyasida esa, "ma'naviyat – kishilarning falsafiy, huquqiy, ilmiy, badiiy, ahloqiy, diniy tasavvurlarini o'z ichiga oladi", deyilgan. Har bir ta'rifning funktsionallik va individuallik jihatlari mavjud bo'lib, inson vujudining ma'nosi,

manfaatlar to‘qnashuviga moyilligi, uning benazir va mukammal mavjudotligini ifodalaydi.

Ma’naviyat bilan madaniyatni tahlil etish chog‘ida ular o‘rtasidagi dialektik aloqadorlik, sinergetik tamoyillar mavjudligini ko‘ra bilish juda muhim. Ma’lumki, ma’naviyat ham, madaniyat ham hech kimda tug‘ma bo‘lmaydi, instinktlar orqali tabiatan berilmaydi. U shaxsning jamiyatda ijtimoiylashuvi negizida ahloq, did, idrok, his-tuyg‘ularning ta’siri ostida shakllanadi va, shunday deyish joiz bo‘lsa, ongsizlikdan onglilik, anglanganlik tomon ulg‘ayishida vujudga keladi. Har bir voyaga yetib kelayotgan yigit-qiz shaxsiy hayotiy tajribasi asosida, mustaqil ravishda bevosita tevarak-atrofdagi kishilarning, jamiyatning va o‘tgan ajdodlarning to‘plagan tajribalarini o‘zlashtiradi. Yoshlar ham ijtimoiy amaliyot mahsuli bo‘lgan madaniyatni o‘zlashtirish bilan birga, unga o‘z ta’sirini o‘tkazadi. Yoshlar ijtimoiy ongining shakllanishi jarayonida moddiy va ma’naviy madaniyatni boyita boradi.

Har bir voyaga yetib kelayotgan yoshlarning oilada, mehnatda, o‘qishda, odamlar orasida va jamiyat ijtimoiy-falsafiy hayotidagi harakatlari ma’naviy madaniyat mezonlari bilan o‘lchanadi. Agarda yoshlar tarbiyasida ana shu umumiy zanjirning birorta bo‘g‘inida uzilish ro‘y bersa, bunda voyaga yetayotgan yoshga ham, jamiyatga hamda oilaga ham ma’lum darajada zarar yetadi. Yoshlarning dunyoqarashi, didi, ilm-fan va kasb-hunarga nisbatan munosabati yordamida ahloqini ham tarbiyalash muhim ahamiyatga ega. Ma’naviy madaniyat har bir yoshning birinchi qadamidan, “qush uyasida ko‘rganini qiladi” deganidek, oilada, ota-ona, aka-uka, opa-singil namunasidan boshlanadi. Sekin-asta bog‘cha va maktabda beriladigan ahloqiy saboqlar natijasida jamiyatdagi aloqalarning tobora kengayib borishi orqali butun umri davomida sayqallanib boradi.

Ma’naviy madaniyat aslida ma’lum miqdor, sifat va ma’naviy munosabatlarning to‘plami, inson ongi va ma’naviy faoliyatining mahsuli sanaladi. Unda ma’naviy ong va faoliyat bilan bog‘liq ijtimoiy jarayonlar qonuniy tarzda mavjud jamiyatda o‘sib kelayotgan yosh avlodni ham ruhan, ham ma’nan, ham jismonan kamol topishiga xizmat qilishi oddiy hayot tarzi ta’sirida amalga oshadi. Bu jarayonda yoshlar voqelikka o‘zlarining zavqli munosabatlarini in’ikos ettirib, borliqdagi narsa va hodisalarning mohiyatini anglab boradi. Yoshlar ma’naviy madaniyati deyarli jamiyatning ideallarini qamrab oladigan ma’naviy munosabat, ong, faoliyatning mazmun-mohiyatini o‘zida ifodalaydi. “Binobarin, odamzodning ongiga qanday fikr, g‘oya, nuqtai nazar, olam va unda odamning o‘rni qarashlar to‘g‘risidagi bilim singigan bo‘lsa, shunga muvofiq,

uning fe'l-atvori, hatti-harakati, butun faoliyati tus oladi". Bularning barchasi pirovard oqibatda har bir shaxsning o'zligini tezroq anglashida namoyon bo'ladi.

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O'SPIRINLARNING AXBOROTDAN FOYDALANISH MADANIYATINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING AXAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada yoshlar o'rtasida axborotlardan foydalanishda mavjud muammolar va axborot madaniyatini shakllantirishning o'ziga xos uslublari, uning yoshlar kamolotidagi tutgan o'rni haqida qarashlar bayon etilgan

Kalit so'zlar: yoshlar, axborot, axborot madaniyati, internet, ta'lim

THE IMPORTANCE OF FORMING A CULTURE OF USING INFORMATION AMONG ADOLESCENTS

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Annotation: This article describes the existing problems of the use of information among young people and approaches to the formation of information culture, its role in the development of youth.

Keywords: the youth, information, information culture, the Internet, education

Har qanday mamlakat o'z taraqqiyot yo'lini belgilashda avvalo kelajak rejalarini qurib, unda albatta yoshlarga e'tiborni kuchaytiradi. Shundan kelib chiqadigan bo'lsak bugungi kun jahon hamjamiyati oldida turgan eng muhim masalalardan biri yoshlar masalasidir. Yoshlarga bugungi kun rivojlangan texnologiyalar asri va axborot makoni juda keng imkoniyatlar yaratib berishi bilan birgalikda zararli axborot shaklidagi katta xavfni shakllantirmoqda. Bunday yoshlar kelajagiga o'zining salbiy ta'sirini o'tkazuvchi omillardan ularni asrabavaylash uchun yoshlar o'rtasida axborot madaniyatini rivojlantirish zarur bo'lib, o'z navbatida bu jamiyat siyosiy savodxonligi darajasiga ham yuqori darajada o'zining ijobiy ta'sirini ko'rsatadi. Insoniyat ertangi kuni uchun kurashar ekan bunda yosh avlodning munosib davomchi sifatida shakllanishi uchun har tomonlama chuqur islohotlar amalga oshirib borishi va bunda yoshlarning mas'ullik hissini ham shakllantirib borishi talab etiladi. Sababi yoshlar oldiga qo'yilayotgan maqsadlar ularda qat'iy rioya qilinishi talab etiladigan me'yorlarni

ham yuzaga keltiradi. Yoshlar axborot iste'molchisi sifatida avvalo axborot tasnifini anglashi, ulardan foydalanish imkoniyatlarini to'liq anglab yetishi, zararli axborot maydoni ta'siridan o'zini himoya qilish prinsiplarini anglab yetishi, zamonaviy axborot vositalaridan foydalanganda talab etiladigan me'yorlarni to'liq anglab yetishi bo'yicha ilmiy asoslangan xulosalar bugungi kun talabidir.

Axborot asri insoniyatga tezkor axborot taqdim qilish bilan birgalikda undan noo'rin foydalanish tufayli ko'plab muammolarni shakllantirmoqda, bu o'z navbatida eng katta ta'sirini yoshlar o'rtasida namoyon etmoqda. Shu sababli yoshlar o'rtasida axborotdan to'g'ri foydalanish, ayniqsa o'smir davri yoshlarida axborotdan samarali foydalanish yoki ijtimoiy xavfli axborotlardan ularda immunitet shakllantirish talabi ortib bormoqda.

Mazkur masalada, davlat tomonidan olib borilayotgan islohotlar esa taxsinga loyiqdir. Zero, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Sh.M.Mirziyoyev "Biz yoshlarga doir davlat siyosatini hech og'ishmasdan, qat'iyat bilan davom ettiramiz. Nafaqat davom ettiramiz, balki bu siyosatni eng ustuvor vazifamiz sifatida bugun zamon talab qilayotgan yuksak darajaga ko'taramiz. Yoshlarimizning mustaqil fikrlaydigan, yuksak intellektual va ma'naviy salohiyatga ega bo'lib, dunyo miqyosida o'z tengdoshlariga hech qaysi sohada bo'sh kelmaydigan insonlar bo'lib kamol topishi, baxtli bo'lishi uchun davlatimiz va jamiyatimizning bor kuch va imkoniyatlarini safarbar etamiz"[1] deb ta'kidlaganida yoshlar orasida har qanday ijtimoiy xavf keltirib chiqaruvchi omillarga qarshi kurashish nazarda tutilgan desak mubolag'a qilmaymiz.

Bugungi jamiyat a'zolari qaysidir ma'noda telekommunikatsiyalar ta'sirida hayot kechirar ekan buning o'z navbatida ham salbiy ham ijobiy xususiyatlari mavjuddir. Ilmiy tahlillarga ko'ra, tezkor axborot va kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining rivojlanishi natijasida dunyodagi turli xalqlar va elatlar orasida globallashuv jarayonlari sodir bo'layotgan vaqtda butun insoniyat, jumladan xalqimiz ma'naviyatiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatish mumkin bo'lgan turli mafkuraviy tahdidlar asosida yashamoqda.[2]

Butun dunyoda bo'lgani kabi mamlakatimizda ham ta'lim sohasiga zamonaviy qarash va texnologiyalarning keng jalb qilinishi rivojlanib bormoqda. Bu esa o'z navbatida ta'lim sohasida ham axborot iste'moli xususiyatlarini ilmiy tadqiq qilish va uning yoshlarga ta'sirini har tomonlama chuqur tahlil qilingan xulosalar shakllantirishni talab etmoqda. Aynan malakatimizda ham axborot olami aynan internet va kommunikatsiya sohasi texnologiyalaridan foydalanish ko'lami ham kun sayin oshib borib, kundalik zaruriy ehtiyoj sirasiga kirib

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bormoqda. Statistik ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, O'zbekistonda internet xizmatidan foydalanuvchilar soni - 22,1 milliondan oshdi. Shundan mobil internet foydalanuvchilari soni - 19 millionni tashkil etmoqda. Mamlakat bo'yicha aholi punktlarining mobil aloqa bilan qamrab olinishi darajasi 97 foizni, mobil internet qamrovi esa 87 foizni tashkil etdi. 26 mingga yaqin "uz" domenidagi veb-saytlar faoliyat olib bormoqda. 200 dan ortiq veb-sayt ommaviy axborot vositasi sifatida ro'yxatga olingan. Internetning ta'sir kuchi beriladigan materiallarning tezkorligi, ko'tarilayotgan masalalarning dolzarbligi hamda tahliliylik darajasi va mavjud muammolarning samarali yechimlarini taklif etishiga ko'p darajada bog'liq.[3] Bu raqamlar o'z navbatida jamiyatning ajralmas qismiga aylanib qolgan axborot olamini yanada chuqurroq anglashga imkon beradi.

Mustaqil O'zbekiston yoshlari rivojlangan texnologiyalar asrida munosib ishtirokchi bo'lib, mazkur sohaga taalluqli mahsulot va vositalardan keng foydalanmoqda. Bu esa o'z navbatida axborotdan foydalanish bo'yicha madaniy ko'nikmalarni ijtimoiylashtirish orqali ularning yosh va dunyoqarashidan kelib chiqib axborot iste'molini rivojlantirishni talab etadi. Ta'limni axborotlashtirish strategiyasi va taktikasi ishlab chiqilayotgan bir vaqtda, axborot-resurs markazlarining o'zni ham beqiyosligicha qolmoqda. Unda axborot-resurslarining shiddat bilan kirib kelishi esa axborotlashuv jarayonini yana ham jadallashtirmoqda. Shunga qaramay, badiiy asarlar, qomuslar, lug'atlar, gazeta va jurnallarning tobora katta qismi matnli fayllar ko'rinishida tarqalmoqda. Elektron va bosma nashrlar bir-birini mustasno etmaydi, balki bir-birini to'ldiradi, binobarin, kelajakda kutubxonalarda ham virtual, ham an'anaviy kitobga o'rin topiladi. Kuzatishlarimiz shuni ko'rsatmoqdaki, kitobxon texnik va ma'lumotnoma adabiyotlardan ko'proq elektron shaklda foydalanadi.[4]

Shuningdek bugungi kunda yoshlar ayniqsa ular klassifikatori (yosh darajasi)ga ko'ra axborotdan foydalanish ko'nikmalari, ularni ma'naviy dunyosini boyitishda axborot vositalarining o'zni, axborotlarning asnifi va ulardan foydalanish chegaralarini aniqlashda echimini topmagan va ijtimoiy ahamiyati yuqori bo'lgan ilmiy ishlar olib borish zaruratligicha qolmoqda. Yoshlar o'rtasida axborotlardan samarali foydalanishni tashkil etish uchun fanlararo integratsiya rivoji ham alohida o'rin tutadi va bunda aynan pedagogika sohasi bilan axborot texnologiyalari sohasini o'zaro integratsiya qilish orqali ularning pedagogik hamda texnik xususiyatlari bo'yicha iste'molchi bo'lgan yoshlarga ta'sirchan imkoniyatlar yaratish mumkin. Aynan bunda pedagogic tarbiya nuqtai nazari birlamchi omil bo'lib xizmat qilishi lozim.

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DIFFUZ TOKSIK BUQOQDA IMMUNOLOGIK O'ZGARISHLAR

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Annotatsiya. Maqolaning ushbu sharhi DTB kabi endokrinologiya sohasidagi dolzarb kasallikka bag'ishlangan. Kasallikning klinik ko'rinishlari bir vaqtning o'zida bir nechta tizimlarga ta'sir qiluvchi qalqonsimon bez gormonlarning ko'p ajralishi bilan bog'liqligi ko'rsatilgan. Kasallik shakllanishining immunologik mexanizmlari ko'rsatilgan Yurak-qon tomir tizimining shikastlanishi DTB ning tez-tez uchraydigan jiddiy asoratlari bo'lib, u ko'pincha yurak-qon tomir kasalliklarida birinchi o'rinda turadi. Uning klinik ko'rinishi va kasallikning borishi va natijasini aniqlash yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Diffuz toksik buqoq, klinik ko'rinishlari, immunopatogenezi

IMMUNOLOGIC CHANGES IN DIFFUSE TOXIC GOITERS

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Abstract. This review of the article is devoted to an actual disease in the field of endocrinology, such as DTB. It has been shown that the clinical manifestations of the disease are associated with multiple secretions of thyroid hormones that affect several systems at the same time. The immunological mechanisms of the formation of the disease are indicated. Damage to the cardiovascular system is a frequent serious complication of DTB, and it often ranks first among cardiovascular diseases. Its clinical presentation and determination of the course and outcome of the disease are explained.

Key words: Diffuse toxic goiter, clinical manifestations, immunopathogenesis.

Kirish. Diffuz toksik buqoq - bu qalqonsimon bezning autoimmun kasalligi. Qalqonsimon bezda anti-rTTH va aylanib yuruvchi autoantitanalarning, va ularni rag'batlantiruvchi autoantitanalar gipertiroidizmga olib keladi. DTB qalqonsimon bez antigenlariga, xususan, retseptorlarga nisbatan immunitetning tolerantligining buzilishi natijasida yuzaga keladi. DTB xavfi ayollar uchun 3% va keksa erkaklar uchun 0,5% ni tashkil qiladi. Kasallik 30 yoshdan 60 yoshgacha ko'p hollarda G'arb mamlakatlari aholilarida uchrashi aniqlangan. Qalqonsimon bez kasalliklarining klinik ko'rinishi qalqonsimon bez gormonlarining ko'pligi bilan bog'liq bo'lib, bir vaqtning o'zida bir nechta turli xil kasalliklarga olib keladi. Shuning uchun DTB bilan bog'liq belgilar va alomatlar juda katta farq qilishi va umumiy holatga sezilarli darajada ta'sir qilishi mumkin.

Umumiy simptomlar: titroq, yuqori haroratga sezgirlik, odatiy ovqatlanish bilan ham vaznning yo'qolishi, asabiylashish, qalqonsimon bezning kengayishi (buqoq), tartibsiz hayz sikli, erektil disfunktsiya yoki libidoning pasayishi, charchoq, tez-tez yurak urishi va boshqalar. Tireotoksikoz bo'lgan 3000 dan ortiq bemorlarni o'rganishda bemorlarning 50% dan ortig'i 61 yoshdan oshganligi ma'lum bo'ldi va kasallikning har uchtadan 1 tasi kamroq klassik belgilariga ega. Ko'pchilik bemorlarda atriyal fibrilatsiya tez-tez kuzatiladigan belgi sifatida kuzatilgan.

Tadqiqotning maqsadi: Diffuz toksik buqoqda immunologik o'zgarishlarni va bez gormonlarining boshqa kasalliklar kelib chiqishidagi rolini o'rganish.

Tadqiqotning borishi : Tireotoksikoz kamdan-kam hollarda davriy falajlikga olib kelishi mumkin (o'tkir mushaklarning falaji va og'ir gipokaliyemiya). Osiyolik erkaklarda ko'proq uchraydi va ko'pincha infeksiya, spirtli ichimliklar, qiyin hazm bo'luvchi uglevodlar yoki og'ir jismoniy faoliyat tufayli paydo bo'ladi. Tireotoksikozli bemorlarda kamdan-kam hollarda jigar faoliyatining buzilishi bilan bog'liq bo'lgan "qalqonsimon bo'ron" deb ataladigan hayot uchun xavfli holat kuzatiladi, ruhiy holatdagi o'zgarishlar, isitma, qo'zg'alish, yurak etishmovchiligi va taxikardiya belgilari ko'proq uchraydi. Jarrohlik amaliyotlari, tug'ish, infeksiya, travma kabi hodisalar vaziyatni yomonlashtirishi mumkin. DTB oftalmopatiya bemorlarning taxminan 30-50% da mavjud. Bemorlarda: ko'zda qum yoki begona narsa hissi, haddan tashqari qichishish hissi, (ko'pincha shamol, sovuq havo, yorqin yorug'lik ta'sirida yomonlashadi), diplopiya, retrookulyar og'riq yoki noqulaylik, loyqa ko'rish, rangni ko'rishning desaturatsiyasi, ba'zida ko'rishning yo'qolishi kuzatiladi. DTB oftalmopatiyasining xarakterli belgilari ekzoftalmos (ekzoftalmos), lakrimatsiya

va periorbital shish. Orbital chuqurlik, retrokulyar mushaklarning o'sish darajasi, retrokulyar tolalar va yog 'to'qimalari ekzoftalmos darajasiga ta'sir qiladi. Ekzoftalmos odatda assimetrikdir, lekin simmetrik ham bo'lishi mumkin, bunda ko'z qovoqlari orqasida bosim hissi kuzatiladi. Periorbital shish odatda ekzoftalmozga hamroh bo'lib, uni niqoblab keladi. Ko'p kuzatiladigan yana bir holat bu yurak urishining tezlashishi hisoblanadi. Asosan fibrillatsiya, taxikardiya kabi o'zgarishlar bilan uchrashi aniqlangan. Boshqa autoimmun kasallik bilan assotsiatsiya DTB bilan og'rigan bemorlarning taxminan 20 foizida mavjud. Tadqiqot natijalari DTB bilan og'rigan bemorlarning 16,7 foizida boshqa autoimmun kasallik ham borligini ko'rsatdi: Shegren kasalligi (0,8%), tizimli qizil yuguruk va sarkoidoz (<0,1%), 1-toifa qandli diabet (0,9%), glyuten kasalligi (1,1%), ko'plab sklerozlanishlar (0,3%), revmatik polimiyalgiya (1,3%), revmatoid artrit (1,9%), surunkali autoimmun gastrit (2,4%), vitiligo (2,6%).

DTB ning immunopatogenezi :Yuqorida ta'kidlab o'tilganidek, qalqonsimon bez kasalliklarining boshlanishi qalqonsimon bezga nisbatan immunitetga chidamlilikning buzilishi bilan bog'liq.

Genetik jihatdan ekologik va endogen omillarni o'z ichiga olgan autoimmun multifaktorial jarayon orqali kasallik yuzaga keldi. Ko'p sonli tadqiqotlar qalqonsimon bez kasalliklarining faol bosqichi Th1 ustunligi bilan bog'liqligini ko'rsatdi. Immun javob DTB ning nofaol yoki keyingi bosqichlari Th1dan Th2ning immun javobiga o'tish bilan bog'liq. Qizig'i shundaki, xavf bilan bog'liq bo'lgan genlarni hisobga olsak, ma'lum ta'sirga ega bo'lgan taxminan 70% T hujayralarida o'zgarish yuzaga kelishi mumkin. Kasallik patogenezida T limfotsitlarining ahamiyatini katta. DTB da autoimmun reaksiya bezga infiltratsiya qiluvchi B hujayra klonlari tomonidan pTTH ga autoantitalarning ishlab chiqarilishiga olib keladi. Ularning harakatlariga ko'ra, antitanalar TSH-R ni quyidagicha tasniflash mumkin: qalqonsimon bezni ogohlantiruvchi antitanalar (TSAb), tiroid blokirovka qiluvchi antitanalar (TBAb) va neytral antitanalar. pTTH ga antikorlar DTB patogenezida va uning qalqonsimon bezdan tashqari ko'rinishlarida ishtirok etadi. Gipertiroidizm TSAb bilan bog'liq, bunda TSH ning TSH-R ga bog'lanishi bilan bir xil quyi oqim ta'siriga olib keladi, masalan, adenilat siklaza faollashishi keyingi siklik adenozin monofosfat (cAMP) ishlab chiqarishga olib keladi. Bu esa tirotsitlarning ko'payishiga, qalqonsimon bezning o'sishiga va sekretsiyaga olib keladi. Qalqonsimon bez gormonlari (T4 va T3). T4 (va ayniqsa T3) salbiy teskari aloqa orqali oldingi gipofiz bezidan TSH sekretsiyasini ingibatsiya qiladi. Qalqonsimon bez kasalliklarida TBAb va neytral antitalarning roli unchalik aniq emas. TBAblar TSH-R ning A bo'linmasi bilan

bog'lanib, TSH ta'sirini va uning follikulyar hujayralarga ta'sirini bloklaydi. Neytral antitanalar cAMP shakllanishiga yoki TSH bog'lanishiga ta'sir qilmasdan retseptorga bog'lanadi. Shu asosida bez giperplaziyasi, gormon sekretsiyasidagi buzulishlar kelib chiqadi. TG darajasining oshishiga javoban eng erta yurak-qon tomir o'zgarishlar periferik qon tomirlarda qon tomir qarshiligi va venoz tomirlarning siqilishining kuchayishi hisoblanadi. Ushbu o'zgarishlar natijasida qonning teskari oqimi tufayli o'ng bo'lmachada diastolik bosim pasayadi, yurakdan qonning chiqishi refleksli ravishda o'zgaradi. Bir qator tadqiqotlarga ko'ra, DTB da aylanuvchi qon hajmining 30-50% ga kamayishi kuzatiladi. Ushbu o'zgarishlarning molekulyar asoslari to'liq aniq emas. Vazoaktiv omillar (masalan. katexolaminlar, prostatsiklinlar, endotelinlar) tomirlarning silliq mushaklari qisqarishining muhim regulyatorlari bo'lib, ular tizimli qon tomir qarshiligi ta'minlaydi. Nazariy jihatdan, T3 to'g'ridan-to'g'ri silliq mushaklarga ta'sir qilishi mumkin, hujayralar yoki o'z harakatlarini endotelial hujayralar orqali amalga oshiradi, vazoaktiv moddani chiqarishi mumkin. Qisqarish mexanizmi miyokarddagiga o'xshaydi, lekin silliq mushak hujayralarida Ca^{2+} bog'lanadi va kalmodulin deb ataladigan molekulyar kompleks, miyozin yengil zanjirlarini fosforlashtiradigan fermentni faollashtiradi. Bu o'z navbatida, aktinomiozin kompleksida qisqarishni keltirib chiqaradigan o'zaro bog'lanishlarning shakllanishini faollashtiradi. Tizimli qarshilik va yuqoridagi sabablar taxikardiya va aritmiyaga sabab bo'ladi. Bu yural qon tomir tizimida kuzatiladigan asosiy o'zgarishlar hisoblanadi.

Xulosa. Shunday qilib, DTB klinik jihatdan, qon zardobida ATA ning mavjudligi va infiltratsiya bilan tavsiflanadi. Qalqonsimon bezdagi patalogik jarayon autoreaktiv limfotsitlar, autoimmun reaksiyada B hujayra klonlari tomonidan TSAb ishlab chiqarishni keltirib chiqaralishi tufayli sodir bo'ladi. Ushbu antitanalar qalqonsimon bez kasalliklarining patogenezida va uning ekstratiroidal namoyon bo'lishida hal qiluvchi ahamiyatga ega. DTB uchun xavf omillari genetik moyillik va endogen omillar o'rtasidagi o'zaro ta'sirlarni o'z ichiga oladi. DTG ning immunopatogenezida Th1 immun javobi ustunlik qiladi, bunda Th1 xemokinlari asosiy rol o'ynaydi. DTB tomonidan jalb qilingan hujayralarda Th1 limfotsitlari IFN-g va TNF-a ishlab chiqarishini ko'payishiga olib keladi, bu esa Th1 ximokinlarining sekretsiyasini rag'batlantiradi, qalqonsimon bez hujayralari, autoimmun jarayonni qo'llab-quvvatlaydi. Arteriolalarning silliq mushak hujayralariga ta'sir qiluvchi TG, to'g'ridan-to'g'ri diastolik bosimga va tomirlar qarshiligiga, jumladan, aylanuvchi qon hajmi o'zgarishiga, taxikardiya va aritmiya paydo bo'lishiga olib keladi. Bu taxmin

boshqa tadqiqotlar tomonidan ham tasdiqlanadi . Fenilefrin infuziyasidan keyin DTB bilan og'rigan bemorlarda kasallik va uning asoratlari sezilarli pasayish kuzatildi. Masalan, yurak mushaklarida va boshqa to'qimalarda gipoksiya ancha kamaygan.

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BO'LAJAK JISMONIY MADANIYAT O'QITUVCHILARINI TURISTIK FAOLIYATGA TAYYORLASH METODIKASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH

Fazliddin Boqiyev

O'zbekiston davlat jismoniy tarbiya va sport universiteti Farg'ona filiali o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada bo'lajak jismoniy madaniyat o'qituvchilarini turistik faoliyatga tayyorlash metodikasini takomillashtirish ta'limga turli yondashuvlarni birlashtirish hamda amaliy tajribaga sinab ko'rish ko'nikmalarini tarbiyalash va zamonaviy texnologiyalarni qo'llash bo'yicha ko'rsatlalar berilgan

Kalit so'zlar: Sayyohlik faoliyatini rejalashtirish, nazariy bilimlar, amaliy bilimlar, turizm menejmenti, jismoniy tarbiya, jismoniy mashq, bilim, ko'nikma, malaka

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF TRAINING FUTURE PHYSICAL CULTURE TEACHERS FOR TOURIST ACTIVITIES

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Abstract: This article provides instructions on improving the methodology of training future physical culture teachers for tourism activities, combining different approaches to education, training skills to test practical experience, and using modern technologies

Key words: Tourism planning, theoretical knowledge, practical knowledge, tourism management, physical education, physical exercise, knowledge, skills, competence

Jismoniy madaniyat o'qituvchilarini turistik faoliyatga tayyorlash metodikasini takomillashtirish ta'limga turli yondashuvlarni birlashtirish, amaliy tajribaga urg'u berish, tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini tarbiyalash va zamonaviy texnologiyalarni o'z ichiga qamrab olishni nazarda tutadi. Bo'lajak jismoniy madaniyat o'qituvchilarini turistik faoliyatga tayyorlashni kuchaytirish bo'yicha tuzilgan reja.

Yaxlit o'quv rejasini ishlab chiqish

Nazariy bilimlarni turistik faoliyat bilan bog'liq amaliy ko'nikmalar bilan birlashtirgan o'quv dasturini ishlab chiqish, jumladan, ochiq havoda yetakchilik, navigatsiya, xavflarni boshqarish va atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilish. Turistik

tajribani har tomonlama tushunish uchun geografiya, ekologiya, turizm menejmenti va madaniyatshunoslik kabi fanlarni o'quv dasturiga kiritish.

Tajribali o'rganish imkoniyatlari.

Sayyohlik faoliyatini rejalashtirish, yetakchilik qilish va baholashda amaliy tajriba bilan ta'minlash uchun ekskursiyalar, amaliyotlar va ochiq havoda ekspeditsiyalarni amalga oshirish.

Mahalliy sayyohlik agentliklari, milliy bog'lar va ochiq havoda ta'lim markazlari bilan hamkorlik qilib, talabalar uchun real dunyoda o'rganish imkoniyatlarini taklif qiling.

Simulyatsiya va stseneriy asosidagi trening.

Favqulodda vaziyatlarga javob berish mashqlari, guruhni boshqarish muammolari va qaror qabul qilish simulyatsiyasi kabi haqiqiy turistik vaziyatlarni taqlid qilish uchun simulyatsiya mashqlari va stseneriy asosidagi treninglardan foydalaning.

Talabalar uchun chuqur o'rganish tajribasini yaratish uchun virtual haqiqat (VR) va kengaytirilgan haqiqat (AR) texnologiyalarini qo'shing.

Fanlararo yondashuv.

Ta'lim tajribasini boyitish uchun turli kafedralar, jumladan, jismoniy tarbiya, turizmshunoslik, psixologiya va ekologiya fanlari professor-o'qituvchilari o'rtasida fanlararo hamkorlikni rag'batlantirish.

Turistik faoliyat bilan bog'liq murakkab muammolarni hal qilish uchun talabalardan turli sohalardagi bilim va ko'nikmalarni qo'llashni talab qiladigan fanlararo loyihalarni rivojlantirish.

Madaniy kompetensiya va xilma-xillikka o'rgatish

Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni turli xil madaniyatlarga ega bo'lgan turistlarning turli guruhlari bilan ishlashga tayyorlash uchun madaniy kompetensiya va xilma-xillikdan xabardorlik bo'yicha treninglarni ta'minlash.

Talabalarning turli til va madaniy kelib chiqishi bo'lgan sayyohlar bilan samarali muloqot qilish qobiliyatini oshirish uchun til kurslari yoki madaniy immersion tajribalarini taklif qiling.

Texnologiyalar integratsiyasi.

GPS-navigatsiya qurilmalari, sayohatni rejalashtirish va xavfsizlik uchun mobil ilovalar, virtual sayohatlar va interaktiv o'quv modullari uchun onlayn platformalar kabi texnologiya vositalarini birlashtirish.

Talabalarga mas'uliyatli va barqaror turizm amaliyotlarini targ'ib qilish uchun ijtimoiy media va raqamli marketing strategiyalaridan qanday foydalanishni o'rgatish.

Axloqiy va barqaror turizm amaliyotlari.

Axloqiy va barqaror turizm amaliyotlarining muhimligini ta'kidlash, jumladan, atrof-muhitga ta'sirni minimallashtirish, mahalliy hamjamiyatlarni hurmat qilish va mas'uliyatli turizm tashabbuslarini qo'llab-quvvatlash. O'quv dasturiga axloqiy dilemmalar va barqaror turizm strategiyalari bo'yicha amaliy tadqiqotlar va muhokamalarni kiritish.

Doimiy baholash va fikr-mulohazalar.

O'quvchilarning o'zlashtirishlarini nazorat qilish va ularning mashg'ulotlari davomida takomillashtirish yo'nalishlarini aniqlash uchun uzluksiz baholash va qayta aloqa tizimini joriy etish. Uzluksiz o'rganish va kasbiy rivojlanishga yordam berish uchun o'z-o'zini aks ettirish va tengdoshlarni baholashni rag'batlantirish.

Ushbu strategiyalarni amalga oshirish orqali ta'lim muassasalari bo'lajak jismoniy madaniyat o'qituvchilarini turistik faoliyatga tayyorlash metodikasini oshirish, ularni mas'uliyatli va barqaror turizm amaliyotini targ'ib qilish uchun zarur bo'lgan bilim, ko'nikma va munosabatlar bilan qurollantirish, shu bilan birga sayyohlar uchun esda qolarli va boyituvchi tajribalarni taqdim etishi mumkin.

Bo'lajak jismoniy madaniyat o'qituvchilarini turistik faoliyatga tayyorlash nazariy bilimlarni ham, amaliy ko'nikmalarni ham qamrab oluvchi ko'p qirrali yondashuvni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu yerda foydalanish mumkin bo'lgan nazariy asos:

Turizm industriyasi haqida tushuncha.

Talabalarni turizm industriyasining tushunchalari, tamoyillari va tendentsiyalari bilan tanishtirish. Bu turizmning har xil turlari (ekoturizm, sarguzasht turizmi, madaniy turizm va boshqalar), turistlarning xulq-atvori, turizmning mahalliy jamoalar va atrof-muhitga ta'siri haqida umumiy ma'lumotni o'z ichiga oladi.

Ochiq havoda ta'lim va sarguzasht turizmi.

Ochiq ta'lim tamoyillari, sarguzasht turizmi faoliyati va xavfsizlik protokollari haqida bilim berish. Bunga xavflarni boshqarish, favqulodda vaziyatlarda tartib-qoidalar, navigatsiya qobiliyatlari va atrof-muhitni boshqarishni tushunish kiradi.

Jismoniy tayyorgarlik va salomatlik.

Turistik faoliyat kontekstida jismoniy tayyorgarlik va salomatlik muhimligini ta'kidlash. Turistlar uchun ham, gidlar uchun ham muntazam jismoniy faollik, to'g'ri ovqatlanish, suvni namlash va dam olishning afzalliklari haqida talabalarga o'rgatish.

Geografiya va madaniyatshunoslik.

Turizm faoliyatiga tegishli geografik ob'ektlar, diqqatga sazovor joylar va madaniy ob'ektlarni o'rganish. Bu mahalliy hudud geografiyasini, tarixiy diqqatga sazovor joylarni, madaniy meros ob'ektlarini va mahalliy bilimlarni tushunishni o'z ichiga oladi.

Muloqot va shaxslararo muloqot qobiliyatlari.

Sayyohlar, hamkasblar va mahalliy jamoalar bilan muloqot qilish uchun zarur bo'lgan muloqot va shaxslararo munosabatlarni rivojlantirish. Bunga samarali og'zaki va og'zaki bo'lmagan muloqot, faol tinglash, nizolarni hal qilish va madaniy sezgirlik kiradi.

Etakchilik va guruh boshqaruvi.

Turistik faoliyat davomida o'quvchilarni yetakchilik qobiliyatlari va guruhlarni boshqarish usullariga o'rgatish. Bunga guruh dinamikasi, qaror qabul qilish, muammolarni hal qilish va tashqi muhitda nizolarni hal qilish kiradi.

Ekologik ta'lim va barqarorlik.

Talabalarga atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilish, barqaror turizm amaliyoti va ochiq havoda mas'uliyatli dam olish haqida ma'lumot berish. Bunga hech qanday iz qoldirmaslik tamoyillari, ekologik ta'sirni minimallashtirish va barqaror turizm tashabbuslarini ilgari surish kiradi.

Birinchi yordam va favqulodda vaziyatlarga javob berish.

Turistik faoliyat davomida yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo'lgan favqulodda vaziyatlarga talabalarni tayyorlash uchun birinchi tibbiy yordam, CPR va cho'l tibbiyoti bo'yicha treninglar o'tkazish. Bu umumiy jarohatlar, kasalliklar va atrof-muhit xavf-xatarlarini tan olish va ularga javob berishni o'z ichiga oladi.

Huquqiy va axloqiy mulohazalar.

Turistlarni yo'naltirish bilan bog'liq huquqiy va axloqiy mulohazalar, jumladan, javobgarlik masalalari, risklarni boshqarish va turistlar, mahalliy jamoalar va atrof-muhitga nisbatan axloqiy xatti-harakatlarni muhokama qilish.

Kasbiy rivojlanish va sertifikatlash.

Talabalarni sayyohlik sanoati bilan bog'liq professional sertifikatlar, masalan, cho'lda birinchi yordam, ochiq havoda etakchilik yoki ixtisoslashtirilgan rahbarlik sertifikatlarini olishga undash.

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ARTERIAL GIPERTONIYADA BUYRAK USTI BEZINING MORFOLOGIK O'ZGARISHI

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Annotatsiya. Maqola arterial gipertenziyada buyrak usti bezlaridagi morfologik o'zgarishlarni o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Buyrak usti bezining patomorfologik xususiyatlari tanatogenezning miya va yurak variantlari bilan vafot etgan odamlarda bezlardagi arterial gipertenziya bilan bog'liq o'zgarishlarni aniqlashga asoslangan.

Kalit so'zlar: buyrak usti bezlari, arterial gipertenziya, morfologiya, limfoid infiltratsiya, insult, monositlar

MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES OF THE ADRENAL GLAND IN ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION

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Abstract. The article is devoted to the study of morphological changes in the adrenal glands in arterial hypertension. The pathomorphological characteristics of the adrenal gland are based on the detection of changes associated with arterial hypertension in the glands in people who died with cerebral and cardiac variants of thanatogenesis.

Key words: adrenal glands, arterial hypertension, morphology, lymphoid infiltration, stroke, monocytes.

Kirish. Hozirgi vaqtda yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari dunyoda yetakchi o'rinni egallaydi o'lim sababi bo'yicha birinchi o'rinda turadi Arterial gipertenziya kasallanish va o'lim prognozini belgilovchi asosiy xavf omillaridan biridir. Uzoq muddatli yuqori qon bosimi muhim hayotiy organlarda bir qator asoratlarni rivojlanishiga sabab bo'ladi.

Tadqiqot maqsadi: Morfologik parametrlarni qiyosiy o'rganish, buyrak usti bezlarining morfofunktsional holatini arterial gipertenziyada turlicha aks etishini kuzatish.

Materiallar va tadqiqot usullari. Morfologik tadqiqot ob'ekti sifatida 50 yoshdan 84 yoshgacha bo'lgan 102 erkak va ayolning buyrak usti bezlari olindi. Bemorlar Respublika ixtisoslashtirilgan endokrinologiya ilmiy-amaliy tibbiyot markazi Samarqand viloyati filiali arxividan kasallik tarixi tahlil qilib olindi. Arterial gipertenziya bilan hayot kechirganlar va turli sabablarga ko'ra vafot etganlar - hayotga mos kelmaydigan mexanik shikastlanishlar: miyada qon ketishi ("Insult" guruhi) va o'tkir chap qorincha yetishmovchiligi, sof arterial gipertenziya olindi. Materiallar to'plami davlat muassasasi klinikalarining patologik bo'limi ma'lumotlari negizida amalga oshirildi. Seksiyonal materialni gistologik tekshirish uchun buyraklar o'rtasidan, kapsula mavjud bo'lgan buyrak usti bezlarining qismlari, shuningdek, barcha uchta zonadan material olingan Gematoksilin va eosin bilan bo'yalgan, kapsulaning holati, korteksning glomerulyar, fasikulyar va retikulyar zonalar va medulla o'rganilgan. Lipidlarning taqsimlanishi va miqdorini aniqlash maqsadida glomerular zona bo'yalgan, tashqi qismini tekshirish uchun Sudan bilan bo'yashdan foydalanilgan. Fasikulyar zonaning o'rta va ichki qismlari, shuningdek, retikulyar zonada har bir holatda buyrak usti bezlarining har birida, fokusning mavjudligi va diffuz mononuklear infiltratsiya, limfotsitlar, monotsitlar, plazma hujayralari soni va korteksning tegishli zonalarida joylashgan fibroblastlar va medulla, qon sirkulatsiyasi va turli strukturaviy shishlar, kortikal zonalardagi o'zgarishlar o'rganilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, har xil arterial gipertenziyaning o'limdan oldingi ko'rinishlari va natijada o'limga olib keladigan asoratlari, morfologik holatning o'zgarishiga turli xil tekshirilgan buyraklarda turlicha aniqlangan. Avvalo shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, bu barcha ko'rsatkichlar insult yoki yurak yetishmovchiligidan o'lgan bemorlar buyragida farq qiladi. O'lgan gipertensiv bemorlarda shikastlanishdan, sababi aniqlanmagan va boshqa yurak kasalliklaridan o'lganlarga nisbatan morfologik o'zgarishlar ancha rivojlangan. Ro'yxatga olingan na'munalarda o'ng buyrakka nisbatan chap buyrak usti bezining retikulyar zonasida lipid tarkibining kamayishi yoki ortishi glomerular

zona va buyrak usti bezining medullasini qon bilan ta'minlashidagi chuqur patalogik o'zgarishlar aniqlangan . Mexanik shikastlanishdan vafot etgan bir guruh gipertenziv bemorlar bilan solishtirganda, insult va o'tkir chap qorincha yetishmovchiligidan vafot etganlarda kortikal zonalarda sezilarli darajadagi qon ta'minoti buzulishi va chap va o'ng buyrak usti bezlarining medullasidagi o'zgarishlar aniqlangan. Chap buyrak usti bezida yadro-sitoplazmatik nisbat ortishi va medullaning fokal limfotsitar infiltratsiyasining kuchayishi; o'ngda ko'proq - retikulyar zonaning lipodistrofiyasi aniqlangan. Shunday qilib, tanatogeneznining yurak varianti ko'proq morfologik o'zgarishlarga sabab bo'ladi. Fasikulyar va retikulyar zonalarda qon ta'minoti buzulishi o'limning yurak variantida miya bilan solishtirganda ko'proq kuzatilgan. Bundan tashqari, tanatogeneznining yurak varianti, ko'proq aniq fokal limfoid infiltratsiya va buyrak usti hujayralarining vakuolizatsiyasi bilan kechgan jarayon. Buyrak usti bezi po'stloq qismining morfologik o'zgarishi har bir bemorda kuzatildi 10% bemorda sezilarli o'zgarish sezilmadi bunga sabab 10 % bemorlar Antigipertenziv dori vositalarni regular qabul qilib yurgan shu sababli strukturaviy o'zgarish yuzaga kelmagan.

Xulosa: Shunday qilib, buyrak usti bezlarining morfologik parametrlari, uning funktsional holatini aks ettirish maqsadida arterial gipertenziya bilan kasallanishdagi o'lim natijalari olindi, nafaqat kasallikning mavjudligi kasallanish , balki o'lish mexanizmlaridan biri ekanligi asoslandi.

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DORIXONA MALUMOTLAR BAZASINI AVTOMATLASHTIRISH

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Annotatsiya. *Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish - bu retsept bo'yicha dori-darmonlarni tarqatish, saralash, qadoqlash va hisoblashning elektron jarayoni. Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish ko'plab turli maqsadlarga ega, jumladan, samaradorlikni oshirish, mehnat xarajatlarini minimallashtirish va aniqlikni oshirish. Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish bozorida, dorixonani avtomatlashtirish birinchi marta mashhur bo'lganida, tabletkalarni hisoblash yagona usullardan biri edi. Endi ko'proq foydalanish mumkin bo'lgan avtomatlashtirish mashinalari mavjud.*

Kalit so'zlar: *ma'lumotlar bazasi, avtomatlashtirish, dorixona, samaradorlik*

PHARMACY DATABASE AUTOMATION

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Abstract. *Pharmacy automation is the electronic process of dispensing, sorting, packaging and counting prescription drugs. Pharmacy automation has many different goals, including increasing efficiency, minimizing labor costs, and increasing accuracy. In the pharmacy automation market, when pharmacy automation first became popular, pill counting was one of the only methods. There are now more accessible automation machines.*

Key words: *database, automation, pharmacy, efficiency*

Polaris Market Research & Consulting ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, global dorixona avtomatlashtirish bozori 2023 yilda 5,24 milliard dollarga baholangan va 2030 yilga kelib 10,4 milliard dollarga yetishi kutilmoqda, bu prognoz davrida CAGR darajasida 8,02 foizga o'sadi [1].

Dori-darmonlarni tarqatish : Dori-darmonlarni tarqatish dorixonalar uchun katta muammodir, chunki u ko'plab xatolar va ifloslantiruvchi moddalarni keltirib chiqarishi mumkin. Dori-darmonlarni qulay paketlarga, shu jumladan blister paketlarga va tasmali qadoqlarga tarqatadigan mashinalar mavjud.

Yozuvlarni sinxronlashtirish : Dori vositalaridan foydalangan holda, farmatsevtlar bemorlarning dori-darmonlarini qo‘lda kiritmasdan sinxronlash va kuzatib borish imkoniyatiga ega. Endi bulutli tahlillar inventarizatsiyani kuzatib boradi, talabni bashorat qiladi va ushbu hisobotlarga bulutga asoslangan kirishni ta’minlaydi.

Dorixonani avtomatlashtirishda aqlli texnologiyaning roli

Ishlab chiquvchilar dorixonani avtomatlashtirish qurilmalari va dasturlarini yaratishda ko‘p jihatdan sun‘iy intellektdan foydalanadilar. AI jo‘natish va qadoqlash mexanizmlarida muhim sifat nazorati funksiyasini bajaradi. U dorini suratga olish, uni tortish va ma’lumotlar bazasidagi rasm va vazn ma’lumotlari bilan solishtirish orqali to‘g‘ri dori yuborilganligini ikki marta tekshiradi[2].

Dorixonani avtomatlashtirishning afzalliklari

Aniqlik va xavfsizlikning oshishi : Dori vositalarining noto‘g‘ri o‘lchanishi yoki ifloslanishi dorixonalar uchun ham, ularning mijozlari uchun ham katta xavf tug‘diradi, shuning uchun farmatsevtlar uzoq vaqt hushyor turishlari kerak, bu soliqqa tortuvchi vazifadir. Boshqa tomondan, mashinalar operatsiyalar sonidan qat’i nazar, aralashmalarning aniq og‘irligi va nisbati va dori vositalarining sterilligini ta’minlashi mumkin.

Yaxshilangan samaradorlik va resurslarni taqsimlash : Amerika farmatsevtlari assotsiatsiyasi jurnali o‘z tadqiqotida ta’kidlaganidek, farmatsevtlar an’anaviy hisoblash va quyish usuliga nisbatan robotli tarqatish moslamalari bilan to‘ldirilgan 100 ta retsept uchun 46,5 daqiqadan ko‘proq vaqtni tejashlari mumkin. Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish bozorida dorixona xodimlari bu

vaqtni mijozlarga yaxshi xizmat ko'rsatish yoki dori-darmonlarni tadqiq qilish va ishlab chiqishda ishtirok etish uchun ajratishlari mumkin.

Geriatrik populyatsiyaning ko'payishi, dori-darmonlarni ishlab chiqarish xarajatlarining qisqarishi va bir nechta shifoxonalarda ish jarayonini yaxshilangan va to'g'ri boshqarish, ayniqsa Xitoy, Hindiston va Indoneziya kabi rivojlanayotgan iqtisodiyotlarda bozor eksponentsial o'sishini ta'minlaydigan asosiy omillardir[3].

Farmatsevtika sanoati jadal rivojlanmoqda, eskilari avtomatlashtirilgunga qadar yangi ish o'rinlari paydo bo'ladi. Robotlar odatiy va zerikarli vazifalarni bajaradilar, mutaxassislar esa ijodkorlik, empatiya va nuanslarga e'tibor berishni talab qiladigan murakkab vazifalarni bajarishlari mumkin. Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish bozorida, avtomatlashtirish mavjud bo'lgan holda, farmatsevtlar bemorlar bilan ko'proq shug'ullanishlari va kichik sog'liq muammolari, shu jumladan ruhiy salomatlik va giyohvand moddalarni suiiste'mol qilish bo'yicha ma'lumot, maslahatlar, diagnostika va davolashni taqdim etishlari mumkin.

Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish deganda dorixonada dori-darmonlarni saqlash va tarqatishdan tortib inventar va yozuvlarni boshqarishgacha bo'lgan turli vazifalarni soddalashtirish va yaxshilash uchun texnologiyadan foydalanish tushuniladi. U keng doiradagi vositalar va tizimlarni o'z ichiga oladi, ularning har biri ish jarayonining muayyan sohalariga qaratilgan.

Dorixonada avtomatlashtirish, shuningdek, shtrix-kodlarni skanerlash va tekshirish tizimlarini joriy etish orqali inson xatolarini kamaytirish va dori vositalari xavfsizligini oshirishda, bemorlarga to'g'ri dori-darmonlar berilishini ta'minlashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Bundan tashqari, elektron retseptlash (elektron retseptlash) tizimlarining integratsiyasi tibbiyot xodimlari va dorixonalar o'rtasida retsept bo'yicha ma'lumotlarning uzluksiz va xavfsiz almashinuvini osonlashtiradi, bu esa yanada soddalashtirilgan va bemorga yo'naltirilgan sog'liqni saqlash tajribasiga hissa qo'shadi.

Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish, shuningdek, farmatsevtlar uchun qimmatli vaqtni ochib beradi, bu ularga shaxsiylashtirilgan bemorlarni parvarish qilish va dori-darmonlar bo'yicha maslahat berishga e'tibor qaratishga imkon beradi va natijada hamma uchun yaxshi sog'liq tajribasiga olib keladi.

Dorixonalarni kengaytirish va kelajakka ishonch hosil qilishda mijozlarimizning aksariyati dasturiy ta'minotning bevosita va bilvosita afzalliklarini tushunishni talab qiladi. Albatta, bu investitsiyalar bo'yicha ongli ravishda qaror qabul qilishga yordam beradi va sizning e'tiboringizni yaxshilash uchun barcha imkoniyatlarga qaratadi. Shuning uchun, dorixonani avtomatlashtirish tizimlarining ba'zi asosiy afzalliklari[4].

Yaxshiroq ishlash tezligi va aniqligi

Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish insonning aniqligi bilan solishtirganda mahsulotlarni tez va aniq qayta ishlashni ta'minlaydi. Bu xatolarni kuzatish, ifloslanishni kamaytirish va saqlash yoki tarqatish uchun aniq tortish bilan to'g'ri dori-darmonlarga o'z vaqtida kirish imkonini beradi.

Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish tizimlari vazifalarni mukammal bajarish, aniqlik va izchillikni ta'minlash va har safar to'g'ri natijalarni ta'minlash orqali ushbu xavfni yo'q qiladi, xizmat ko'rsatish zarur bo'lgan kamdan-kam holatlar bundan mustasno.

Haqiqiy vaqtda inventarni kuzatish

Albatta, javonlarni qidirish yoki inventar darajasini taxmin qilish uchun vaqtingiz yo'q. Yaxshi rejalashtirilgan dorixonani avtomatlashtirish tizimi har bir dori-darmonni real vaqt rejimida kuzatib boradi, vaqt va xarajatlarni tejaydi va mavjudligini ta'minlaydi, shunda siz zaxiralar, muddati o'tgan dori-darmonlar va o'g'irlik bilan xayrlashishingiz mumkin.

Ushbu dasturiy ta'minot barcha ma'lumotlarni, jumladan, xaridlar, sanalar, amal qilish muddati, belgilangan dozalar va mijozlar ma'lumotlarini saqlaydi. Siz bir nechta joylarda inventarizatsiyani osongina boshqarishingiz va bemorlarga ishonchli xizmatlarni taqdim etishingiz mumkin.

Ish yukini va mehnat xarajatlarini kamaytirish

Avtomatlashtirish sizning jamoangizning ko'nikmalarini odatiy vazifalardan yuqori mas'uliyatli vazifalarga o'tkazish orqali optimallashtiradi. Aqlli ravishda rejalashtirilgan dorixonani avtomatlashtirish tizimlari tibbiyot mutaxassislariga bemorlarni parvarish qilish va dori-darmonlarni sinxronlashtirish, yulduzlar reytingi va maslahat savdolari kabi biznesni rivojlantirish tashabbuslariga e'tibor qaratish imkonini beradi.

Siz bemorlar va strategik sa'y-harakatlarga ko'proq vaqt ajratish uchun xodimlaringizni bo'shatib, operatsiyalarni soddalashtirishingiz mumkin. Shunday

qilib, sizning dorixonangiz qo‘shimcha ish haqi yoki yollashsiz murakkabroq vazifalarni hal qilishi mumkin.

Masalan, dorixonani avtomatlashtirish Walgreensga (Amerikadagi ikkinchi yirik dorixonalar tarmog‘i) ish yukini kamida 25 foizga kamaytirishga va har yili 1 milliard dollardan ko‘proq tejashga yordam berdi .

Bemorlarni parvarish qilish, konsultatsiyalar va bemorlarni o‘qitish va emlash kabi foyda keltiradigan faoliyatga ko‘proq sarmoya kiritish samaradorlikni oshiradi va operatsion xarajatlarni yo‘q qiladi va daromad va foyda marjasini oshiradi.

Ishtirok etish va bemorni parvarish qilishni yaxshilaydi

Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish ma‘muriy vazifalardan qimmatli vaqtni tejaydi, shuning uchun siz bemorlarga yaxshiroq yordam ko‘rsatishga e‘tibor qaratishingiz mumkin. Bu bemorlar bilan mazmunli muloqot qilishni, ularning muammolarini hal qilishni va ularga salomatlik va salomatlik haqida ma‘lumot berishni osonlashtiradi.

Avtomatlashtirilgan retseptlar va boshqa texnologik integratsiyalashgan xizmatlar bemorlarga 24/7 aniq xizmat ko‘rsatishni osonlashtiradi va sizni yanada ishonchli qiladi. Bemorlar retseptlar va kerakli tibbiy yordamga qulay foydalanishlari mumkin, bu ularni qoniqtiradi va mijozlaringizga ijobiy ta‘sir ko‘rsatadi.

Ma‘lumotlar xavfsizligi va maxfiyligi

Bemor haqidagi ma‘lumotlar va dori vositalari bilan ishlash xavfsizligini ta‘minlaydigan turli qonun va qoidalar mavjud. Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish, xuddi avtomatlashtirilgan retseptlarni bajarish kabi, ushbu talablarga muammosiz mos keladi.

Bu nafaqat mijozlarning salomatligi va ma‘lumotlar xavfsizligi to‘g‘risida ishonch hosil qiladi, balki jarayonlarni soddalashtiradi va xavfsizlikni oshiradi. Dorixona menejrlari giyohvand moddalar yoki mijozlar ma‘lumotlarini noto‘g‘ri ishlatishning oldini olish uchun avtomatlashtirishga ishonishlari mumkin.

Ma‘lumotlar bilan ishlash, dori-darmonlarni inventarizatsiya qilish va dori-darmonlarni tarqatish kabi takrorlanadigan vazifalarni avtomatlashtirish uchun texnologiyadan foydalanish vaqtni tejaydi va aniqlikni ta‘minlaydi. Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish tizimlari yuzlab muntazam vazifalarni bir martalik hal qilish imkonini beradi.3

Mijozlarning buyurtmalari va dori-darmonlar tafsilotlarini kuzatish va boshqarish haqida gap ketganda, avtomatlashtirish aqlli yozuvlarni saqlashga yordam beradi. Nafaqat bu, dorixonani avtomatlashtirish tizimlari sizga retseptlar, buyurtmalar, inventar ma'lumotlari va bemor ma'lumotlariga bir joyda kirish va boshqarish imkonini beruvchi to'liq huquqli boshqaruv panelini taqdim etadi.

Bu qalam-qog'oz yozuvlariga qaraganda ancha aniqroq va murakkabroq. Bundan tashqari, bemorlarga sifatsiz dori-darmonlarni sotib olishga majbur bo'lmasligi uchun retseptlangan dori vositalarining inventarizatsiyasini kuzatish osonroq bo'ladi.

Dori-darmonlarni qadoqlash va etiketlash ajralmas, ammo oddiy vazifalardir. Bu nozik masala bo'lsa-da, avtomatlashtirilgan qadoqlash va etiketkalash xatolar uchun kamroq joy qoldiradi. Bundan tashqari, qadoqlash paytida har qanday ifloslanishni kamaytirishga yordam beradi.

Dorixona ma'lumotlarini boshqarish tizimini qadoqlash va etiketkalash mashinalari bilan ulash ishni osonlashtiradi va murakkablashtiradi. Bu bemorning ismlarini, dori tafsilotlarini, dozasini va hatto shoshilinch telefon raqamini dori-darmonlarni yetkazib berish paketida muammosiz chop etishning ishonchli usuli.

Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish dasturiy ta'minot, robototexnika va mashinalarni o'z ichiga olgan to'liq tizim integratsiyasi bilan dori vositalarini tayyorlashni osonlashtiradi. Bu hamma narsa steril muhitda amalga oshirilishini ta'minlaydi, xatolar va ifloslanishni yo'q qiladi.

Sun'iy intellekt (AI) dorixonani avtomatlashtirishning muhim jihati bo'lib, dori-darmonlarni tarqatishda aniqlikni ta'minlaydi. U dori-darmonlarni suratga olish va saqlangan ma'lumotlarga solishtirish orqali o'zaro tekshiradi va aniqligini kafolatlaydi[5].

Bemorga yo'naltirilgan sun'iy intellekt chatbotlari simptomlar asosida birjadan tashqari dori vositalarini tanlashda yordam beradi va onlayn yoki qo'ng'iroqlar orqali retsept bo'yicha buyurtmalarni osonlashtiradi. Bundan tashqari, AI farmatsevtika kompaniyalariga muhim iste'molchi ma'lumotlarini to'plash va tahlil qilish imkonini beradi, bu esa biznesning mustahkam o'sishiga yordam beradi.

Dori vositalarining uzluksiz kuzatilishini ta'minlash uchun blokcheyndan foydalanish mumkin. Har bir dori ishlab chiqarishda noyob kodni oladi, keyin u blokcheynga kiritiladi. Dori-darmonlarni ulgurji sotuvchidan tortib to

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
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dorixonagacha, bemorni kasalxonaga yetkazishgacha sotish, shifokor yoki bemorni qaytarish yoki yaroqlilik muddati tugaganligi sababli yo‘q qilish bilan bog‘liq har bir keyingi harakatlar qayd etiladi.

Dorixona boshqaruvi va boshqa sog‘liqni saqlash dasturlarini ishlab chiqishda RPA dori vositalarini avtomatlashtirilgan saqlash, shtrix kodlar yordamida qidirish, buyurtmalarni joylashtirish va qaytishni kuzatish kabi jarayonlar uchun aniqlikni ta‘minlaydi. Bundan tashqari, u bemorlar ma‘lumotlarini boshqarishni soddalashtiradi, tez yangilanishlar, saqlash va olish imkonini beradi, shu bilan birga parvarish qiluvchilar, shifokorlar va boshqa organlar uchun hisobotlarni osonlikcha ishlab chiqaradi[6]. Ushbu texnologiyalarni dorixonani avtomatlashtirish tizimlariga integratsiyalash ularni chinakam ilg‘or va kelajakka moslashtirishi mumkin. Dorixonalarni avtomatlashtirish bozori 2024 yil holatiga ko‘ra 4 697,67 million AQSh dollarini tashkil etadi. 2028 yilga kelib CAGR 7,80% bo‘lgan holda 6 983,16 million dollarga yetishi kutilmoqda.

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O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA TA'LIM TIZIMIDAGI ISLOHOTLAR (OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMI MISOLIDA)

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola O'zbekiston Respublikasida Oliy ta'lim tizimidagi islohotlar, kamchiliklar va yutuqlar haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Ta'lim to'g'risidagi qonun, oliy ta'lim muassasalari, strategik amaliyotlar, modernizatsiya, akkreditatsiya, Axborot kommunikatsiya texnologiya (AKT), inklyuziv ta'lim,

REFORMS IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN (IN THE EXAMPLE OF THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM)

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Abstract. This article provides information about reforms, shortcomings and achievements in the system of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Key words: Law on education, higher education institutions, strategic practices, modernization, accreditation, information communication technology (ICT), inclusive education,

O'zbekistonda oliy ta'lim tizimida 2024-yilgacha bir qator yutuqlarga erishildi. Maktab bitiruvchilarini oliy ta'lim bilan qamrab olish darajasi 9 foizdan 28 foizga ko'tarildi. 2030 yilda esa 50 foizga etkazish rejalashtirilmoqda. Shu bilan birga, davlat grantlari 2 barobarga ko'paytirish mo'ljallangan.

Ikkinchidan, Respublikamizda 2020-yil 23-sentabr kuni Ta'lim to'g'risidagi qonunni yangi tahriri kuchga kirdi. Unga ko'ra, Oliy ta'lim tizimida talabalarni qamrovini kengaytirish masalasi alohida e'tirof etildi. Qonunning 57-moddasida Nodavlat ta'lim tashkilotlarining faoliyatini litsenziyalash va ularni sonini yana ham oshirishga doir chora tadbirlar alohida takidlangan. Ta'lim sifatini nazorat qilish davlat inspeksiyasining 2023-yil 23-avgustda bergan ma'lumotiga ko'ra Respublikamizda xususiy oliy ta'lim muassasalari soni 65 ta,

Davlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari soni 115 ta, Xorijiy oliy ta'lim muassasalari soni 30 tani tashkil qilmoqda.¹ Umumiy ta'lim olayotgan talabalar soni 1 029 522 nafar bo'lsa, hundan xotin-qizlar soni 492 580 nafar, erkaklar soni esa 537 700 nafarni tashkil etadi.²

O'zbekistonda oliy ta'lim tizimida 2024-yilgacha bir qator kamchiliklarga ham yo'l qo'yildi. Birinchidan, ta'lim sifati: Ko'pgina muassasalar eskirgan o'quv dasturlari, cheklangan resurslar va malakali professor-o'qituvchilarning etishmasligi tufayli yuqori akademik standartlarni saqlab qolish uchun kurashmoqda.

Ikkinchidan, infratuzilma: Ba'zi universitetlar talabalar uchun o'qish tajribasiga to'sqinlik qiladigan eskirgan xonalar, kutubxonalar va laboratoriyalar kabi jihozlarning etarli emasligidan aziyat chekmoqda.

Uchinchidan, resurslardan foydalanish: Talabalar ko'pincha darsliklar, tadqiqot materiallari va texnologiyalar kabi muhim manbalarga kirishda qiyinchiliklarga duch kelishadi, bu ularning o'qishlari bilan to'liq shug'ullanish qobiliyatini cheklaydi.

To'rtinchidan, tadqiqot va innovatsiyalar: Akademik mukammallikni oshirish va ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishga hissa qo'shish uchun oliy ta'lim muassasalarida tadqiqot va innovatsiyalarga ko'proq sarmoya kiritishga ehtiyoj bor.

Beshinchidan, boshqaruv: byurokratik qog'ozbozlik, korrupsiya va shaffoflikning yo'qligi kabi muammolar universitetlarni samarali boshqarishga to'sqinlik qilishi mumkin.

Oltinchidan, ishga joylashish: Diplomlarga ega bo'lishlariga qaramay, bitiruvchilar ba'zan oliy ta'limda olgan ko'nikmalari va mehnat bozori talablari o'rtasidagi nomuvofiqlik tufayli ish topishda qiynaladilar.

O'zbekiston taraqqiyot sari intilayotgan bir paytda, muhim o'zgarishlarni boshdan kechirayotgan muhim tarmoqlardan biri oliy ta'lim tizimidir. O'zbekiston Respublikasida bir qator strategik amaliyotlar va islohotlar orqali oliy ta'lim tizimini zamonaviy metodlar, o'qitish tizimi va innovatsiyalar, mukammallikni rivojlantirish maqsadida qayta shakllantirmoqda. Bunga misol qilib turli xil yo'nalishlarni misol qilib olishimiz mumkin:

O'quv dasturlari va o'qitish metodlarini modernizatsiya qilish:

Oliy ta'lim tizimini tubdan isloh qilishda o'quv dasturlari va o'qitish uslublarini modernizatsiya qilish asosiy o'rin tutadi. O'zbekistonda ta'lim

¹ <https://fledu.uz/uz/ozbekistondagi-oliy-talim-muassasalari-soni-va-unda-qancha-talaba-talim-olishi-statistikasi/>

² <https://www.google.com/search?q=o%27zbekistonda+nodavlat+oliy+ta%27lim+muassasalari+soni+nechta>

dasturlarini jahon standartlari va turli sohalardagi rivojlanayotgan tendentsiyalarga moslashtirish asosiy maqsadlardan biri hisoblanadi. O'quv dasturlarini yangilash, fanlararo yondashuvlarni joriy etish va amaliy o'rganish tajribalarini o'z ichiga olish orqali universitetlar talabalarni bugungi rivojlanayotgan mehnat bozorida muvaffaqiyatga erishish uchun zarur bo'lgan ko'nikma va bilimlar bilan tarbiyalanmoqda.

Sifat kafolati va akkreditatsiya

O'zbekistonda oliy ta'lim dasturidagi ta'lim sifatini ta'minlash birinchi o'rinda turadi. Universitetlar va dasturlarning samaradorligini baholash va monitoring qilish uchun mustahkam, sifatli va kafolatli mexanizmlar hamda akkreditatsiya jarayonlari yaratilgan. Ushbu chora-tadbirlar orqali institutlar akademik mukammallikning yuqori standartlari, professor-o'qituvchilar malakasi va infratuzilmani ta'minlash uchun javobgar bo'ladi, bu esa O'zbekiston oliy ta'lim tizimining umumiy ishonchi va obro'sini oshiradi.³

Tadqiqot va innovatsiyalarni rag'batlantirish O'zbekiston iqtisodiy o'sish va jamiyat taraqqiyotida tadqiqot va innovatsiyalarning muhim rolini tan oladi. Shu bois oliy ta'lim muassasalarida tadqiqot va innovatsiyalar madaniyatini yuksaltirishga katta e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Moliyaviy yordam, tadqiqot markazlarini tashkil etish va sanoat hamkorlari bilan hamkorlik qilish orqali universitetlarda zamonaviy o'quv metodik usul yaratish va texnologik taraqqiyotga hissa qo'shib, tabiiy, aniq va ijtimoiy fanlar bo'yicha ilg'or tadqiqot ishlarida faol ishtirok etmoqda.

Xalqaro hamkorlik

Global raqobatbardoshlik va madaniyatlararo almashinuvni rivojlantirish uchun O'zbekiston oliy ta'lim tizimida modernizatsiyalash sa'y-harakatlariga ustuvor ahamiyat qaratilmoqda. Dunyo bo'ylab taniqli universitet va muassasalar bilan hamkorlikdagi talabalar va professor-o'qituvchilar almashinuvini, qo'shma ilmiy loyihalarni amalga oshirish hamda xalqaro konferensiya va seminarlarda ishtirok etishni osonlashtiradi. Bunday hamkorlik nafaqat akademik tajribani boyitadi, balki talabalar va o'qituvchilar o'rtasida madaniyatlararo tushunish va global fuqarolikni rivojlantirishga yordam beradi.

Axborot Kommunikatsiya Texnologiya integratsiyasi va elektron ta'lim

Axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining (AKT) transformatsion salohiyatini e'tirof etgan holda, O'zbekiston raqamli vositalar va elektron ta'lim

³ Shamsiev, A.. Globallashuv sharoitida O'zbekistonda oliy ta'limning muammolari va istiqbollari. // Yevroosiyo tadqiqotlari jurnali, 2019.10(2), B-132

platformalarini oliy ta'lim tizimiga integratsiya qilmoqda. Texnologiyalar kuchidan foydalangan holda universitetlar ta'lim resurslaridan foydalanish imkoniyatlarini kengaytirmoqda, masofaviy ta'lim imkoniyatlarini osonlashtirmoqda, o'qitish va baholash usullari samaradorligini oshirilmogda. Ushbu raqamli transformatsiya ta'lim tizimini inqilob qilishga va o'quvchilarga istalgan vaqtda va istalgan joyda bilim olish imkoniyatini berishga tayyorlanmogda. Axborot Kommunikatsiya Texnologiyalari rivojlanishi natijasida oliy talim tizimida online darslar tashkil qilinib, online platformalar yaratildi. Bu orqali offline darslarga qatnasha olmaydigan talabalar malakali ta'lim olishlari uchun qulay shart sharoitlar yaratildi.

Inklyuziv ta'lim va foydalanish imkoniyati

Ijtimoiy tenglik va inklyuzivlikni ta'minlash bo'yicha O'zbekiston jamiyatning barcha qatlamlari uchun oliy ta'limdan keng foydalanish imkoniyatini ta'minlashga intilmogda. Inklyuziv ta'limni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan sa'y-harakatlar nogiron talabalar uchun qo'llab-quvvatlash xizmatlarini ko'rsatish, stipendiyalar va moliyaviy yordam dasturlarini kengaytirish va kam ta'minlangan hududlarda ta'lim imkoniyatlarini kengaytirishni o'z ichiga oladi. Turli va inklyuziv ta'lim muhitini yaratish orqali O'zbekiston o'z inson kapitalining to'liq salohiyatidan foydalanishga, ijtimoiy hamjihatlik mustahkamlashga intiladi.⁴

Xulosa qilib aytganda, O'zbekiston oliy ta'lim tizimida amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar va islohotlar mamlakatning ta'limda mukammallik, innovatsiyalar va inklyuzivlikni qo'llab-quvvatlashga bo'lgan qat'iy intilishidan dalolat beradi. O'quv dasturlarini modernizatsiya qilish, o'quv sifatini ta'minlashni kuchaytirish, tadqiqot va zamon talablariga mos ravishda rag'batlantirish, AKTni integratsiyalash va inklyuziv ta'limni rivojlantirish orqali O'zbekiston bilim, ijodkorlik va inson kapitalini rivojlantirish asosidagi yorqin kelajak uchun zamin yaratmogda.

Ushbu kamchiliklarni bartaraf etish siyosatchilar, ta'lim muassasalari va boshqa manfaatdor tomonlardan O'zbekistonda oliy ta'lim sifati, foydalanish imkoniyati va dolzarbligini oshirish uchun birgalikdagi sa'y-harakatlarni talab qiladi.

⁴ Akramov, K.. O'zbekistonda oliy ta'lim tizimini isloh qilishning muammolari va imkoniyatlari. // Ta'lim va amaliyot jurnali, 2019.10(20), B - 18-23.

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